

SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE IN SLEEP DEPRIVATION DETECTION

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by

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This thesis, entitled:

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submitted by Gian Frans D. Araneta, Christian L. De la Torre, and Rafael Jacov C. Medel, has been examined and is recommended for Oral Defense.

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The Faculty of the College of Information Technology of the University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos accepts the project entitled:

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Support Vector Machine in Sleep Deprivation Detection

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ABSTRACT

Sleep Deprivation (SD) is a growing issue that impairs cognitive, physical, and mental health and increases the risk of accidents and chronic diseases. Conventional detection methods are often intrusive, costly, or impractical for daily use. Aligned with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3 (UN SDG 3), this study aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being. The development of cost-effective, non-invasive, and accessible tools for SD detection is essential to integrate sleep health into public health approaches. The study developed a Support Vector Machine (SVM) trained by the researchers to classify their mild SD status through voice analysis. The researchers trained the model on an open-access dataset from the Open Science Framework (OSF), which was extracted through Spectro-Temporal Modulation (STM) features. To have a solution, the study evaluated the performance of SVM through STM features. It analyzed its performance across different dimensions of STM features, sessions, and Balanced Accuracy (BACC) at the population and individual levels. The SVM achieved a training and testing BACC of 0.8588 and 0.7476, respectively, which indicates sufficient performance and generalization. Statistical analyses are applied to determine the differences between the other trained models in different dimensions of STM: frequency-rate (FR), frequency-scale (FS), and scale-rate (SR). Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA), and t-tests proved those hypotheses.

COMPUTER SCIENCE CONCEPT

•Binary Classification •Feature Extraction •Machine Learning
•Model Evaluation Metrics •Statistical Analysis •Signal Processing •Supervised Learning

KEYWORDS

Balanced Accuracy (BACC), Binary Classification, Feature Extraction, Machine Learning, Sleep Deprivation (SD), Signal Processing, Spectro-Temporal Modulation (STM), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Voice Analysis

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1 INTRODUCTION

Sleep Deprivation (SD) is one of the most concerning issues in public health, resulting in various problems in individuals, both physically and mentally.^[1] SD is linked to a heightened risk of chronic illnesses, including cardiovascular conditions, obesity, and diabetes, attributable to prolonged SD and metabolic dysregulation.^[2] People with SD are likely to develop mental health problems. These are mostly linked to anxiety, depression, and other cognitive problems.^[3]

In reference to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3 (UN SDG 3), individuals must promote the well-being of others and live a healthy life at all ages.^[4] Therefore, the main goal of this research is to ensure that those individuals have access to those tools that help monitor their health condition in a non-intrusive and accessible way. One possible approach is to develop a mobile application that only uses the microphone of the smartphone for SD status classification. Only audio is required for the classification process, with a minimum duration of 15 seconds.

This research revolves around the development of the Support Vector Machine (SVM) to use for binary classification between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived. This is done by the use of Spectro-Temporal Modulation (STM) features, which capture the necessary vocal patterns of a human being that are linked to changes in cognitive and physical states.^[5] However, this becomes overly complex for the model to handle; therefore, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is implemented to ensure that the model only captures the most significant features. The trained SVM is the foundation of the SD detection. Combining these approaches ensures that research not only addresses a public health issue but also provides an accessible and non-intrusive solution in alignment with UN SDG 3.

1.1 Scope of the Study

The study encompasses a comprehensive method of SD that uses the SVM with STM to detect mild SD. The study of annotated data “sleepy voices”, as deployed in OSF (Open Science Framework).^[6] This dataset is provided to make the detection of the model efficient.

The SVM analyzes the generic auditory features of the STM. The scope of the detection is to detect mild SD, also referred to as partial SD, through voice analysis. The two languages that are most competent for Filipinos to read are Filipino and English American, which are utilized in the mobile application.

The application is built through React Native to have easy accessibility in a mobile application that is implemented across a diverse range of users. The goal is to provide a non-invasive method for SD detection that is easily deployable among professionals, students, and the general public.

2 METHODOLOGY

The research follows a structured approach to develop the SVM model for detecting SD through voice. The dataset used is the “sleepy voices” dataset in OSF, which consists of audio recordings from 24 female participants in both pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) and post-session (sleep-deprived) conditions. The recordings are cleaned, converted to Waveform Audio File or WAV format, downsampled to 16 kHz, and segmented into 15-second chunks. Feature extraction is done through STM, which captures vocal patterns across frequency, scale, and rate. The features are extracted, then normalized and reduced using PCA to remove noise and reduce dimensionality. The dataset is then split into training, validation, and testing sets; this utilized an 80:10:10 ratio. The SVM with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel is then trained and improved with Grid Search using stratified 5-fold cross-validation. This is to determine the optimal hyperparameters. The performance of the model is evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and Balanced Accuracy (BAcc); whereas, further analysis is conducted through the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) and learning curves. Finally, statistical tests such as Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA), and t-tests are applied to the results. Thus, to validate the findings at both the individual and population levels.

2.1 Research Design

The study focused on both quantitative and experimental approaches. The researchers tested, analyzed, and compared the three key dimensions of the STM which are frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate. These three dimensions are compared to one another alongside the STM and population and individual levels. This is to determine whether the one dimension alone is sufficient for the classification process. Thus, to prove whether the hypotheses of the researchers are correct.

2.2 Dataset

The dataset is found on OSF, published by Etienne et al., which also serves as their dataset in their research “Sleep Deprivation Detected Through Voice Analysis”.^[5] The nature and characteristics of the dataset are mainly in the form of an Audio Interchange File Format or AIFF. A file that is similar to WAV, but it is closed-source as it was developed by Apple. The reason for the choice of file type is the use of an Apple portable recorder (Zoom H1/MB), which was used for stereo-recording and mono-recording.^[5] The total number of female participants was originally 24, yet two of the participants had audio recording issues; hence, their recordings were discarded, leaving 22 female participants for the experiment. Primarily, the language used is French. Among all participants, they were instructed to read a book named “Le Comte de Monte Cristo” (The Count of Monte Cristo) by Alexandre Dumas.^[7] The total number of audio recordings is 144, each of which has an average duration of five minutes and 16 seconds (see Table 1).

Dataset	“sleepy voices”
Dataset Source	Open Science Framework (OSF)
Sampling Rate (kHz)	44.1 kHz
Type	Excerpt reading
Categories	Sleep-deprived (post-sessions) and non-sleep-deprived (pre-sessions)
Language	French
Format of Audio	Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF)
Total Number of Subjects	24
Total Number of Audio	144
Number of Sessions	6
Average Audio Duration	5 minutes and 16 seconds
Total Number of Segmented Samples	2,720

Table 1. Sleepy Voices Dataset Characteristics

In Table 2, the type of audio records is pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) on day one and post-session (sleep-deprived) on day three; 1397 in pre-sessions, and 1323 in post-sessions across six sessions on day one and day two. The six sessions in pre-sessions and post-sessions were separated into three different times, which are session one (9:00 am), session two (3:00 pm), and session three (5:00 pm). Specifically, there are 890 in the session one segmented sample, 909 in the session two segmented sample, and 903 in session three, with a total of 2720 segmented samples across three sessions

Sessions	Pre-session	Post-session	Total Recordings
Session 1	470	420	890
Session 2	475	452	909
Session 3	452	451	903
Total	1397	1323	2720

Table 2. Sleepy Voices Annotation Count Per Session.

Shown in Figure 1 are the recording sessions across three days. The first day consists of three recording sessions which are 9 AM, 3 PM, and 5 PM. The same goes on day three. Within those sessions, the 22 non-sleep-deprived female participants had their speech recorded. After those sessions, they were only given three hours of sleep (3 AM to 6 AM the day after one and two). No recordings were conducted on day two, and they followed their routine outside the laboratory. After the day, the sleep of the participants was restricted to no more than 3 hours of sleep, the same as on day two. By then, the participants were sleep-deprived, and their speech was recorded after day three.^[5]

Figure 1. Sleepy Voices Schedule.

The dataset was split into three, with a proportion of 80:10:10, training, validation, and testing sets, respectively. The training has a total of 2,176 segments, validation is 272 segments, and testing is 272 segments. The total number of segments is sufficient for the SVM model to train, validate, and test.

Activity	Percentage Distribution	Number of annotations
Training	80%	2,176
Validation	10%	272
Testing	10%	272
Total	100%	2720

Table 3. Data Splitting of Sleepy Voices.

2.3 Measures and Statistical Treatment

The researchers use metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and Balanced Accuracy (BAcc) to evaluate the performance of the SVM classifier in mild SD detection based on STM features. These measures provide a comprehensive insight into the classification ability, generalization, and reliability across pre- and post-sleep-deprived classes. Each metric captures a particular aspect of the predictive performance of the classifier, which allows for comparison and validation of results.

Accuracy measures the overall performance of the classifier by computing the ratio of correctly predicted samples to the total number of predictions.^[8]

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FN+TN+FP}$$

However, accuracy itself does not completely represent model performance, especially in the context of class imbalance.

Precision quantifies the proportion of correctly identified positive cases, such as sleep-deprived, among all instances predicted as positive. High precision indicates that the SVM model makes few false positive predictions, which ensures the reliability of positive classifications.^[9]

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

Recall measures the percentage of actual positive cases the model correctly identifies over the total number of actual positive cases. High recall indicates that the model successfully captures most of the actual sleep-deprived cases, minimizing false negatives.^[10]

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

F1 score serves as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, which balances both metrics to provide a single measure of the efficacy of the model. This is useful to evaluate the performance of the model on a dataset that exhibits an imbalanced class, as it penalizes extreme values of precision or recall.^[11]

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Specificity measures the performance of the model to identify the actual negative rate correctly. It minimizes false positives, which ensures that the classifier does not incorrectly label both classes. High specificity indicates the model is sufficient at avoiding misinterpretation and correctly identifies negative conditions.^[12]

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN+FP}$$

Balanced Accuracy is used to evaluate the SVM, mainly with imbalanced data. It combines the average sensitivity obtained for each class, together with the specificity. It

ensures that both binary classes are equally represented in the evaluation.^[13]

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Recall} + \text{Specificity}}{2}$$

2.4 Procedures

There are seven stages in the development of this approach which are Data Collection, Data Cleaning, Processing, Model Training and Validation, Model Evaluation, Statistical Treatment, and Mobile Application Integration. The researchers first collected data from OSF, consisting of 22 female participants. The data collected are then organized into two categories, pre-session and post-session. The researchers reviewed the labels associated with the data. After data collection, the researchers utilized Python libraries, specifically librosa and pydub, to automate audio cleaning for every file in the dataset. This is done by having the “.aiff” files converted to “.wav” format, as it is a lossless and widely supported format for voice analysis tasks.

The recordings are then downsampled from 44.1 kHz to 16 kHz. This standardizes the audio quality and reduces computation complexity. Therefore, it aligns with standard speech processing practices, making the steps faster without compromising quality.^[5]

Afterward, segmentation is done, wherein an average of 5-minute audio is segmented into 15-second units. Segmentation enables appropriate analysis with localized speech features and enhances the model to detect subtle variations in generic auditory features associated with SD. In this study, a single 15-second segment was used for the trained SVM model to provide an optimal balance between temporal resolution and vocal stationarity.

The researchers computed STM features over 40-ms temporal windows, then averaged 3,841 successive windows, which corresponds to approximately 15 seconds of audio. In the Formula, the number of successive windows in short-time analysis is applied during STM feature extraction. In this process, the 15,000-ms (15-second) audio segment was divided into overlapping frames, each with a 40-ms window length and a 4-ms hop size.

$$\text{Successive Windows} = \left\lfloor \frac{\text{Total Duration} - \text{Window Length}}{\text{Hop Size}} \right\rfloor + 1$$

Where Total Duration is 15,000-ms, Window Length is 40-ms, and Hop Size is 4-ms. Each window captures temporal modulation in the speech signal, which allows

the STM to analyze both rapid and slow modulation in patterns across time and frequency. The average of 3841 frames provides a constant representation for spectro-temporal, which balances temporal resolution that reduces computational cost and ensures reliable feature extraction for SVM.

After data cleaning, the next significant step is to process the data. Feature extraction is done by extracting Spectro-Temporal Modulation (STM) features from each of the 2,720 audio segments. Each 15-second WAV file is processed through a STRF-like model that simulates human auditory perception, producing a high-dimensional matrix of values representing the STM features. These raw features are then normalized using global scaling and StandardScaler of scikit-learn to ensure uniformity, and finally reduced with PCA to retain the most significant patterns while minimizing complexity.^[5]

Figure 2. Data Collection, Data Cleaning, and Processing.

The dataset of 2,720 feature sets is split into training, validation, and testing using an 80:10:10 ratio. Hyperparameter tuning for the SVM’s C and Gamma (γ) values was then performed with grid search and stratified 5-fold cross-validation to identify the best hyperparameters (C=1000, γ =0.001).

The final SVM model was then trained on the train and validation split for cross-validation. The 10% of the unseen data was used to evaluate and test the model. Performance metrics are calculated for the Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and Balanced Accuracy of the model. For the model performance evaluation, the researchers used Learning Curve, Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC), and Validation Curve to evaluate classifier performance under various thresholds.

Performance scores were compiled and analyzed using one-way ANOVA, one-way MANOVA, and Welch’s t-test. In this study, one-way MANOVA is employed to determine whether the SVM classifier exhibits statistically significant multivariate differences in performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and BAcc, between the STM, such as frequency-rate (FR), frequency-scale (FS), scale-rate (SR), and frequency-scale-rate (combined dimensions). The researchers utilized one-way ANOVA to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the average STM features between pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) and post-session (sleep-deprived)

conditions. Independent Two-Sample T-test, or Welch's t-test, was utilized to differentiate population-level and individual-level SVM classification model BAcc measures statistically. Lastly, in Mobile Application Integration, the foundations are then implemented into a mobile application.

Figure 3. Model Training and Validation, Model Evaluation, Statistical Treatment, and Mobile Application Integration.

3 RESULTS

This section provides a detailed analysis of the performance of the SVM in the detection of mild SD using generic auditory features derived from voice analysis. The evaluation focuses on the various evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and BAcc. The outcomes are examined in terms of both individual and population-level categorizations, considering how the model differentiates between non-sleep-deprived and sleep-deprived states. The outcome of the one-way MANOVA is also presented to statistically confirm the significance of the classification performance of the model under different conditions. The train+validation vs testing process is examined to verify performance consistency and the ability to generalize.

3.1 Training Results

The training results of the SVM classifier on the STM features show consistent performance across 5-fold cross-validation (see Tables 3 and 4). The performance on the iterations demonstrates that the model generalizes well, as evidenced by the highly consistent performance metrics across the training, validation, and testing stages. The dataset was split into a proportion of 80:10:10, which results in a total of 2,176 for training, 272 for validation, and 272 for testing. The following subsections provide a detailed performance analysis

based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and balanced accuracy.

3.1.1. Model Accuracy. It achieved an average of 0.8588, which indicates a reliable and consistent classification performance across five iterations of repeated training and validation using stratified 5-fold cross-validation. The gap between train and test is 0.8588 and 0.7476, respectively, which shows that the model is not overfitting (see Table 3). The model obtained accuracy values in pre-session and post-session that were always close to 0.7050 and 0.7924, respectively (see Table 4). These values show that while the classifier performed slightly better in detecting sleep-deprived (post-session) speech compared to non-sleep-deprived (pre-session), both conditions were captured with reasonable reliability. The results are an indication of the model being effective in reflecting vocal variations during various sleep conditions in a well-balanced manner in various test splits.

3.1.2. Model Precision. The SVM classifier was both consistent and highly precise during training, validation, and testing iterations, which achieved an average precision of 0.8591 in all classes (see Table 3). Precision measure, for the pre-session test set evaluation, achieved a perfect score of 1.00, consistent in each of the five iterations (see Table 4). This seemingly perfect performance is attributed to the nature of the subset utilized, where no instances of the 'post' class (sleep-deprived) were present. Thus, there were also no false positives predicted for the 'pre' class (not sleep-deprived), thus resulting in a high precision measure of 1.0 for that particular class; the same goes for the 'post' class (non-sleep-deprived).

3.1.3. Model Recall. The SVM classifier achieved a strong performance in the identification of relevant instances, with an average of 0.8588 across the stratified 5-fold cross-validation (see Table 3). This indicates that the model showed an equal ability for the detection of both non-sleep-deprived (pre) and sleep-deprived (post) vocal samples. In the pre-session test set, the recall was around 0.7050, whereas in the post-session test set, it increased to 0.7924, which shows a negligible loss of sensitivity while switching from one session to another (see Table 4). These values confirm the stability of the model in detecting true positive cases under varied testing conditions. The slightly lower recall detected during the pre-session reflects the negligible loss in the capability for the detection of sleep-deprived vocal states.

3.1.4. Model F1-score. The F1-score metric, which balances both precision and recall, stayed consistent across the stratified 5-fold cross-validation, with an average of 0.8588 in all classes (see Table 3). This metric is important in imbalanced datasets, especially in

practical situations where both false positives and false negatives carry significant weight. The F1-score of the pre-session test remained at 0.8270, and the post-session score at the average of 0.8842, both demonstrating a high harmonic mean between the precision and recall (see Table 4). The high F1-scores are a reflection of the perfect precision values (1.0) that were obtained in both sessions, with high recall performance.

3.1.5. Model Balanced Accuracy. The SVM classifier achieved an average of 0.8590 in all classes of BAcc, which exceeds the baseline balanced accuracy (without cross-validation) of 0.7664 by a margin of approximately 10% (see Table 3). It is important for the datasets with possible class imbalance since it provides equal weight to the recall of both classes. This demonstrates that the SVM model showed improved ability to correctly classify pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) and post-session (sleep-deprived) compared to the baseline model without the hyperparameter tuning.

Train Performance Metrics					
iteration	accuracy	precision	recall	f1	BAcc
1	0.8591	0.8594	0.8591	0.8592	0.8593
2	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587	0.8589
3	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587	0.8589
4	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587	0.8589
5	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587	0.8589
average	0.8588	0.8591	0.8588	0.8588	0.8590
Test Performance Metrics of Both Classes					
iteration	accuracy	precision	recall	f1	BAcc
1	0.7502	0.7502	0.7524	0.7491	0.7487
2	0.7502	0.7502	0.7524	0.7491	0.7487
3	0.7465	0.7465	0.7483	0.7454	0.7451
4	0.7465	0.7465	0.7483	0.7454	0.7451
5	0.7502	0.7502	0.7524	0.7491	0.7487
average	0.7487	0.7487	0.7508	0.7476	0.7473

Table 3. Five-Iteration Train and Test of the SVM Classifier.

Test Performance Metrics of Pre-Session					
iteration	accuracy	precision	recall	f1	BAcc
1	0.7050	0.7050	1.000	0.7050	0.8270
2	0.7050	0.7050	1.000	0.7050	0.8270
3	0.7050	0.7050	1.000	0.7050	0.8270
4	0.7050	0.7050	1.000	0.7050	0.8270
5	0.7050	0.7050	1.000	0.7050	0.8270
average	0.7050	0.7050	1.000	0.7050	0.8270
Test Performance Metrics of Post-Session					
iteration	accuracy	precision	recall	f1	BAcc
1	0.7955	0.7955	1.000	0.7955	0.8861
2	0.7955	0.7955	1.000	0.7955	0.8861
3	0.7879	0.7879	1.000	0.7879	0.8814
4	0.7879	0.7879	1.000	0.7879	0.8814
5	0.7955	0.7955	1.000	0.7955	0.8861
average	0.7924	0.7924	1.000	0.7924	0.8842

Table 4. Five-Iteration Pre- and Post-Session Test of the SVM Classifier.

3.2 AUC-ROC Curve

Figure 4 shows the performance metrics of how well a binary classifier distinguishes between two classes (pre-session vs. post-session). Notably, the feature dimension combined features (Strf) has the highest Area Under the Curve or AUC of 0.84 (1.0 - 0.16), which is closer to 1.0, indicating a very good separation between classes. The second feature dimension with the high AUC is the frequency-rate, with an AUC of 0.82, which is also within the very good range. The third feature dimension that aligns the value of AUC in SR is the FS, which is satisfactory with an AUC of 0.64. While the scale-rate performs satisfactorily that lies with an AUC of 0.64. Hence, the dimension, combined feature, or the STRF, is the correct decision to be used in SD detection.

Figure 4. Model AUC-ROC Curve

3.3 Model Learning Curve

Figure 5 depicts the feature dimension frequency-rate or FR as the dimension with the least margin between the train score and the endpoint of the dimension; it overfits by around 5%. This indicates that frequency-rate (FR) had the least overfitting among the other plots. Despite FR having the lowest percentage of overfit, the AUC-ROC curve depicts that it performs slightly lower than the STRF feature (see Figure 5). It also shows that the FR is significantly worse than STRF with ~9% difference. The two remaining dimensions, scale-rate or SR, and frequency-scale or FS, significantly overfit, indicated by having large gaps between the train score and the cross-validation score. Thus, the STRF dimension is the state-of-the-art choice for sleep deprivation detection.

Figure 5. Model Learning Curve of Four Features.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section of the study provides a comprehensive summary of the research findings. The conclusion of the study addresses the research problems by evaluating the model using performance metrics. Additionally, it presents the results of statistical analysis comparison of pre- and post-sleep-deprived sessions, and represents both individual and population-level results. Furthermore, this section discusses key recommendations to guide future improvements.

4.1 Conclusion

It presents the final interpretation of the results obtained from the SVM classification results. It discusses the SVM performance in the detection of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived using STM features, which evaluates the model across multiple sessions, and analyzes its performance to generalize both at the population and individual levels. The insights gained from these evaluations prove the success of using STM for SD detection.

4.1.1. Determine the accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc of SD detection using the SVM based on generic auditory features, with a focus on the dimension of STM representation. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 0.8588. The Precision and Recall achieved average values of 0.8591 and 0.8588, respectively, indicating the effectiveness of the SVM in detecting optimistic predictions and all actual positive cases. The F1-score remained consistent at 0.8588, which confirms a balanced trade-off between precision and recall. Importantly, the BAcc reached 0.8590, which balances the baseline BAcc of 0.7664. These results indicate the

strong discriminative power of STM-derived features and confirm the suitability of SVM for this task, particularly to capture subtle vocal shifts due to cognitive fatigue.

4.1.2. Determine the performance metrics and statistical analysis of the SVM classification results based on the pre-session and post-session. Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference in overall classification accuracy between the pre-session and post-session results. Despite minor variations, such as a slight decline in post-session recall, the global metrics remained stable, which indicates consistent model performance before and after SD. The high and consistent precision across both sessions suggests that the model avoided false positives effectively. Meanwhile, the slightly lower recall in the post-test indicates a conservative classification approach. The overall results confirm that SVM generalizes well across different cognitive states induced by sleep conditions.

4.1.3. Determine the BAcc of the SVM classification results based on population and individual levels. On a population level, the model achieved an overall BAcc of 0.8590, while individual-level analysis also achieved 0.8300, which indicates that the SVM model adapts well to inter-subject variability. The performance remained consistent even when applied to individuals not included in the training fold, which suggests good generalization across participants. However, slight variations in individual accuracy hint at possible influences from personal vocal characteristics or environmental recording differences. These findings indicate that while the model performs strongly at a general level, personalized fine-tuning further improves classification accuracy.

4.1.4. Overall Model Performance. The SVM model trained on STM features derived from vocal recordings exhibited sufficient performance in the classification of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived conditions. It achieved highly consistent performance across five iterations, with consistent patterns during cross-validation. The overall performance metrics of the model achieved an average of 0.8588 and 0.7486 in training and testing, respectively. The model demonstrated strong generalization capabilities, as indicated by consistently high values in both pre-session and post-session test results. These findings confirm that SVM, when combined with STM-based auditory features, serves as an effective classifier for SD detection. The performance is further reinforced by low variance across five iterations, which validates the reliability of the STM in unseen scenarios.

4.2 Recommendations

This study focused on improving the efficacy of the model and STM features, as well as enhancing the accessibility of SD detection through voice using an

SVM classifier with STM features. It emphasizes improvements in feature extraction, model evaluation, and real-world deployment strategies to support broad applicability.

Future research should aim to address gender and demographic limitations—such as inclusion of diverse participants—to enhance the generalizability of the model across populations. To further improve the performance of the SVM model, future research must focus on model optimization through hyperparameter tuning—such as kernel selection and regularization parameters of C and gamma—to avoid overfitting and strengthen model reliability.

Moreover, the deployment on mobile or embedded systems using frameworks like TensorFlow Lite or ONNX enables real-time, offline detection in practical environments such as the workplace or educational contexts. Additionally, developing a Progressive Web Application (PWA) improves accessibility and user interaction by allowing voice-based assessments, real-time feedback, and historical tracking across multiple devices without requiring installation.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Sleep Deprivation (SD) is increasingly recognized as a significant public health concern that crosses multiple categories, such as health, mental well-being, and safety [HJ2023]. From a health perspective, SD is associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, obesity, and diabetes, due to protracted sleep insufficiency and metabolic imbalances [SS2024]. Mental health problems are also common among those with SD, and the affected populations are more prone to anxiety, depression, and other cognitive impairments [KW2010]. Furthermore, SD has been associated with safety, particularly in the workplace, as it relates to increased possibilities of work accidents and injuries due to cognitive conditions and loss of alertness [SS2024]. All of these factors indicate the different approaches to SD consequences.

These health issues are directly related to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3 (UN SDG 3), which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being. SD also contributes to an increase in chronic disease burdens that include cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and obesity. This also consists of an increase in risk of mental health risks as well as the cases of workplace accidents, which hinders the achievement of UN SDG 3 goals [UN2023]. Chronic SD worsens the difficulties of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), a main concern of UN SDG 3, which aims to reduce premature mortality by one-third, addressing preventable NCDs, such as heart and stroke diseases [WH2023]. Currently, diagnostic approaches for SD, such as subjective self-assessment by the patient and clinical evaluation using expensive equipment, are not accessible to the general population. The

development of cost-effective, non-invasive, and accessible tools for SD detection is important to integrate sleep health into public health approaches in the foundation of UN SDG 3.

This research focuses on mild SD detection through voice analysis based on generic auditory features such as the spectro-temporal modulation (STM), and the utilization of a Support Vector Machine (SVM) based machine learning model. The two distinct effects of voices in SD through vocal biomarkers are prosody (pitch, intensity, rhythm, pause pattern, and speech rate) and voice quality (breathy, tense, sharp, hoarse, or modal voice), which are both related to temporal and spectral modulations, respectively [TE2024]. The SVM is trained to accurately detect and classify complex patterns within high-dimensional data, which is suitable for vocal biomarkers [FG2021]. These vocal features, such as pitch, spectral and cepstral coefficients, duration estimates, and functionals of those features, provide information about sleep quality and overall health status of the individual [KJ2009]. With the ability of the SVM to learn from labeled datasets, this model accurately detects SD based on generic auditory features [TE2024].

The implementation of mild SD detection through voice analysis based on generic auditory features significantly contributes to public health initiatives that address the challenges related to UN SDG 3. SVM predictive accuracy in SD detection helps provide early responses to reduce health risks associated with chronic diseases and workplace accidents. This approach enhances the well-being of people and contributes to global health goals through the prevention of sleep disorders, such as the identification of early signs of cognitive impairment, and stress-related illness [SS2024].

1.1 Statement of the Problem

SD is an increasingly common issue that has severe consequences for physical, mental, and cognitive well-being. The SVM classifier is used in this study to detect mild SD and STM features. However, the performance of the SVM classifier relies on changes in patterns of speech, such as generic auditory features. To have a solution, the study evaluated the performance of SVM through STM features, and analyzed its performance across different generic auditory features, sessions, and Balanced Accuracy (BAcc) at population and individual levels. Specifically, the study aims to address the following:

1.1.1 Determine the Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and BAcc of mild SD detection using SVM based on generic auditory features, which focuses on the dimension of STM features, including:

- a) Frequency
- b) Rate (Temporal Modulation)
- c) Scale (Spectral Modulation)

1.1.2 Determine the differences in the performance and STM representation of the SVM classification results across the mild SD sessions, focusing on:

- a) Non-sleep-deprived (Pre-session)
- b) Sleep-deprived (Post-session)

1.1.3 Determine the BAcc of the SVM classification results based on:

- a) Population-level
- b) Individual-level

1.2 Hypothesis

Based on the formulation of problem statements, the researchers aim to evaluate the system for mild SD detection through voice analysis based on generic auditory features. They utilize the SVM classifier through STM features extracted from voice recordings. When provided with various variables, researchers analyze their performance, impact, and significant differences to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the system. The following hypotheses are made to conduct the research:

1.2.1 There is a significant difference in the Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and BA_{cc} of the SVM classifier in mild SD detection based on generic auditory features, which focuses on the dimension of STM features, including frequency, rate, and scale.

1.2.2 There is a significant difference in the performance and STM representation of the SVM classification results based on the mild SD sessions, which focus on non-sleep-deprived and sleep-deprived.

1.2.3 There is a significant difference in the Balanced Accuracy of the SVM classification results based on population and individual levels.

1.3 Assumption

This section has discussed the assumptions made in the study, which are all important and have to be applied to maintain the scope and methodology of the research. These

assumptions are critical to ensuring the validity and consistency of the study. The following assumptions have been made:

1.3.1 Generic auditory features, such as the dimensionality of the spectro-temporal modulation, are sufficient for mild SD detection.

1.3.2 It is assumed that the audio samples are, in general, recorded under constant conditions. In an area or situation in which there is less noise. Otherwise, variations of recorded audio affect feature extraction performance.

1.3.3 The factors that affect the performance of SVM are the quantity, quality, and diversity of the generic auditory features in the dataset

1.3.4 It is assumed that the dataset participants read predefined French speech content, as the original study involved female participants. Cross-language generalization is assumed but not empirically validated.

1.3.5 It is assumed that the audio samples consist of female participants only. This demographic limitation influences the generalizability and affects the performance of mild sleep deprivation detection when applied to diverse gender populations.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study encompasses a comprehensive method of SD that uses the SVM with STM to detect mild sleep deprivation. The study of annotated data “sleepy voices,” as deployed in OSF (Open Science Framework), was contributed by Etienne Thoret and then used to optimally train an SVM model. This dataset is provided to make the detection system

efficient, which analyzes the generic auditory features of the STM. The two languages that are most competent for Filipinos to read are Filipino and English American, which are utilized in the mobile application. Another important aspect is that this application is built through React Native, so it is an easy-to-use mobile application that is implemented across a diverse range of users. The idea is to provide a non-invasive method for mild sleep deprivation detection easily deployable among professionals, students, and the general public who require convenient ways to monitor their sleep health.

1.4.1 Support Vector Machine

The study used this model as the major machine learning model that helps in mild sleep deprivation detection through voice analysis based on generic auditory features, which focuses on the dimension of STM features. SVM is a well-supervised learning algorithm that is prominent for its outstanding success rates when implemented for binary classification tasks [PD2020]. It is significantly applicable when the identity of the differences between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived individuals. For the determination of the best possible hyperplane in vast high-dimensional spaces, the use of SVM assures separation of the features of the generic auditory necessary for classification. The reason SVM has been chosen is because it has performed well with small to moderate-sized data sets, and this is of huge importance since the data annotated, as well as the raw ones, are significantly large. Moreover, SVM, by its ability to exploit the properties of kernel functions such as radial basis function (RBF), is efficient to use complex and non-linear interactions in the data [PD2020]. To capture variations in generic auditory features that are

influenced by SD, such flexibility is the most important. The use of SVM works toward the achievement of high accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc to validate its potential to be an efficient model for the non-invasive detection of SD. Due to their high computational efficiency and the capability to generalize for unseen data, the SVM fits the choice for this work that guarantees practical applicability to real-world settings.

1.4.2 Mild Sleep Deprivation

The scope of the study is to detect mild sleep deprivation, also referred to as partial sleep deprivation, through voice analysis. Mild sleep deprivation occurs when an individual does not acquire a sufficient amount of sleep over one or more nights, which fails to follow a certain recommended 7-8 hours of sleep. It disrupts the cognitive, physical, and emotional states. It is also associated with reduced decision-making ability, loss of alertness, and high vulnerability to long-term illnesses such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes. In voice analysis, SD causes speech rates that are slower compared to natural speech, pitch fluctuations are reduced, and a monotonous tone. All these factors are used for detection in acoustic feature analysis [TE2024]. It employs overlap effects on vocal biomarkers with the condition that causes vocal strain, coupled with changes in speech rhythms and energy. The scope of this study involves binary classification, where voice samples are categorized as either sleep-deprived or non-sleep-deprived. The focus is not on extreme or severe sleep deprivation that occurs when an individual doesn't sleep for more than 24 hours. But rather focuses more on the detection of subtle changes of mild or partial sleep

deprivation, such as those caused by restriction of sleep to only a few hours across one or more consecutive nights. To identify these patterns in generic auditory features, the system aims to provide a non-invasive and cost-effective method in the detection of mild sleep deprivation in individuals.

1.4.3 Voice Analysis

The scope of this study focuses on voice analysis as a non-invasive approach to detect mild sleep deprivation. It serves as the core procedure for identifying physiological and cognitive changes that are exhibited in speech under sleep-deprived conditions. The system analyzes acoustic and spectro-temporal characteristics—such as pitch variation, speech rhythm, and energy modulation—through the use of STM features to capture subtle changes in vocal characteristics that are correlated with fatigue and lack of alertness.

1.4.4 Dataset

The datasets utilized in this study are sourced from OSF and contain “sleepy voices” by Etienne Thoret [TE2022], which serve a unique purpose in mild sleep deprivation detection through generic auditory features. The participants in the dataset read predefined speech content in French, as the original study involved female participants. With a total of 2720 annotated data points across all classes, which contains the file type Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF). It consists of a 44.1 kHz sampling rate and annotated data that categorizes audio records into sleep-deprived (post-session) and non-sleep-deprived (pre-session) classes. The provided dataset is

particularly valuable since it comprises structured and labeled data that is meant for supervised machine learning models, particularly in SVM.

1.4.5 Languages

In this study, both Filipino and English are used for the mobile application to detect mild sleep deprivation on generic auditory features across diverse speech contexts. Filipino is used because most Filipinos speak and read naturally and consistently in Filipino. Approximately 75% are competent in this language, and 96% of Filipinos are able to read in Filipino [LS2023]. English has also been considered the official language and is widely used in education, commerce, and law, with about 47% of Filipinos competent in English, and 80% able to read and understand spoken English [LS2023]. These two languages in this study thus make a better analysis of the effect of SD on vocal characteristics for a bilingual individual. It considers the linguistic actuality of the population being studied. Therefore, it allows for the generalization of findings across a broader audience. In addition, the comparison of voice characteristics in Filipino and English allows the determination of the variations of SD manifestation across the two languages. Therefore, it aids in the development of more accurate diagnostic tools with cultural sensitivity.

1.4.6 Mobile Application

The system is designed as a platform-independent application that is allowed to run on mobile devices. This application provides mild sleep deprivation detection based on its analysis of the voice recorded by the user through a user-friendly interface. The user records his/her voice through the application, which processes the

audio to extract key generic auditory features such as the dimension of the STM. The system then applies the trained SVM model to classify whether the user is sleep-deprived or non-sleep-deprived. The application is built in React Native. This ensures the application has high accessibility and is platform-independent. React Native develops lightweight and secure applications and ensures the performance of the system in terms of efficiency and reliability. The front end of the application is styled in Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and Tailwind CSS, which creates an intuitive and responsive user interface. Thus, all these tools put together allow the development of an efficient, scalable, and accessible solution to detect mild sleep deprivation. The system targets Android and iOS mobile design so that it reaches a diverse audience, which are professionals, students, and all other people who desire to track their sleep health conveniently from their mobile.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research provides a foundation for future studies that detect mild sleep deprivation through voice analysis across various fields. In the real world, the system is primarily used to screen and serve as an Early Warning System (EWS). Specifically, the results of this study benefit the following:

1.5.1 Workers and Corporations

The result of the application contributes to the health of workers in the sense that it detects each worker if they do not have appropriate sleep habits. Companies use the system to monitor employees in high-risk fields like transportation, healthcare, or

manufacturing, where fatigue due to SD leads to accidents or reduced productivity. Early detection of SD helps improve workplace safety and efficiency. This is achieved when workers are screened before they operate machinery, with a designated person to conduct the assessment. Devices such as professional computers and a specific microphone are used for assessment purposes, as the mobile application makes it less skilled, but still, it is feasible, such as an embedded tablet on a kiosk with its respective high-quality microphone, in which the workers are able to have their SD status checked. Another applicability is office work, where the computers have the system ready, allowing the worker to record and identify his or her SD status, which they are required to do by their manager or boss.

1.5.2 Doctors and Psychologists

The potential for voice analysis to become an objective measure of SD carries significant implications for both doctors and psychologists. The doctors are able to make use of this technology to better diagnose and treat SD. Presently, doctors rely on patients' subjective reports, which are inherently unreliable. Voice analysis provides a fast, non-invasive, and inexpensive way to take objective measurements. Moreover, by the use of voice analysis to learn how each patient is individually affected by SD, doctors customize treatments to the individual. This is extremely important, as there is a great amount of individual variability in the response to SD [TE2024]. Moreover, voice analysis detects the implicit effects of SD that patients are not consciously aware of. Hence, it allows doctors to address these potentially hidden issues. Early detection

of SD through voice analysis also improves patient safety by identifying at-risk individuals before accidents and chronic diseases occur.

1.5.3 Military

Military personnel are especially prone to mild sleep deprivation because of such factors as the demands of missions, irregular schedules, and high-stress environments. However, chronic sleep restriction degrades cognitive functions, decision-making abilities, and readiness of personnel, which interfere with the success of the mission and soldier safety [MV2013]. It has been said that a voice-based detection system for SD is integrated to provide a non-invasive and efficient means to monitor the states of cognitive and physical integrity of the soldier [GX2022]. Vocal analysis, particularly pitch, rhythm, and intensity, allows military units to assess readiness levels at specific times.

By the use of such a proactive approach, commanding officers are able to determine who is sleep-deprived so that timely interventions are provided to maintain optimal performance levels and sound decision-making. Some studies have shown that even conditions like post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) have the ability to be conveniently detected with the use of voice characteristics, which demonstrates the significant potential of voice analysis for mental fitness observation [CN2018]. Along with continuous attempts to integrate the observation of physiological data into military operations, the military increases operational performance, eliminates fatigue-related errors, and enhances welfare in the implementation of the vocal detection system [KJ2022].

1.5.4 Students

Mild sleep deprivation is common during exam periods or high-stress academic workloads, especially when deadlines are the usual primary cause. Students greatly benefit from the use of a mild sleep deprivation voice detection system to address the problem at an early stage, which leads to interventions that improve sleep habits, cognitive performance, and overall well-being, which enhances academic outcomes. Furthermore, early detection of sleep deprivation helps students become more aware of their sleep patterns, encouraging healthier lifestyle choices and better time management during academically demanding periods. This proactive approach supports sustained academic performance by reducing fatigue-related errors, loss of focus, and burnout.

1.5.5 Future Researchers

This study provides a basic framework for future research on the complex adaptability between vocal patterns and sleep deprivation. Through the investigation of how SD affects vocal characteristics in speech, researchers are able to better understand the physiological and psychological consequences of SD. The exploration of these vocal changes eventually leads to the development of non-invasive tools for SD detection, which improves early sleep deprivation. This research is also applicable to further possibilities to examine the broader consequences of SD in communication, cognitive performance, and overall health, which promotes a multidisciplinary approach.

In conclusion, this research addresses a significant public health issue through a non-invasive, affordable means of mild sleep deprivation detection through generic auditory features, which employs an SVM model. The study provides a systematic evaluation of frequency components, spectral (scale), and temporal (rate) modulation that concerns their relation to sleep deprivation, thus it allows results to be performed regardless of the demonstration of mild sleep deprivation effects on vocal characteristics. Detection of mild sleep deprivation in the workplace enhances productivity, decreases work-related accidents, and maintains the health of employees. In industries that rely on good alertness, mainly healthcare, transportation, and manufacturing, employers incorporate this into their occupational health frameworks.

On a broader landscape, this research attempts to achieve the targets set in the UN SDG 3, to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all. This system provides an early detection of sleep-related disorders, thus it supports the prevention of chronic diseases, workplace accidents, and mental health issues. Future researchers are able to address new machine learning algorithms, for instance, deep learning models, to have better classification performance. The expansion of the dataset to encompass various languages and dialects ensures a broader applicability of the system among different populations. Furthermore, with inclusion in mobile apps, this allows individuals to self-track their sleep health with the use of a friendly and accessible tool. Overall, this research lays the groundwork for future progress in non-invasive mild sleep deprivation detection and the wider domain of voice-based health diagnostics. In integrating voice technology and machine learning, this study demonstrates how this technology is advanced to address a critical public health problem, thereby improving the lives of diverse sectors.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter provides a comprehensive review of available literature and previous studies relevant to SD detection through voice analysis based on generic auditory features. The primary purpose of this chapter was to combine the current findings, identify research gaps, and provide a theory supporting the study. Through a comprehensive review, the chapter provides an overview of the scope of topics, such as generic auditory features, STM, vocal biomarkers such as prosody and voice quality, signal processing, voice analysis, auditory spectrogram, Artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning model such as SVM covered by the review, in conjunction with methodologies applied, results obtained, and problems encountered in similar studies. Most importantly, this chapter focuses on the formulation of a research question and the construction of a theoretical and conceptual framework to guide the study (see Figure 1). Additionally, reviewing the literature relevant to the topic provides researchers with significant insights about research methods that work proficiently and helps them become aware of challenges and limitations associated with the conduct of the research. This review also demonstrates the significance of the use of sophisticated machine learning methods, such as SVM, to ensure SD detection becomes accurate and reliable with the use of generic auditory features. Furthermore, by considering previous work on voice-based health checks, this chapter attempts to establish an underlying foundation to deploy a non-invasive and affordable SD detection system.

2.1 Speech Processing

It includes categories of techniques to analyze, interpret, and modify human voices to ensure proper human-to-machine communication. This field is important for different applications, including speech recognition, speaker identification, and emotion detection. There are speech-processing systems that analyze generic auditory features, such as STM with a dimensionality of frequency, rate, and scale, to extract features from audio signals. They produce significant characteristic patterns about speech disorders, emotional conditions, or even SD [FR2021]. In general, the process includes preprocessing of the signal, feature extraction, and classification, where a machine learning model, such as SVM, performs an essential function in the categorization of some features for a specific application purpose [RL2010]. Some of the characteristics include spectro-temporal analysis techniques that provide a representation of speech, which is necessary to identify subtleties of the voice signal that provide information on the physiological or cognitive state [BB2023].

2.2 Voice Analysis

In voice analysis for sleep deprivation detection, generic auditory features such as STM with a dimensionality of frequency, rate, and scale are related aspects, with signal processing techniques such as Fourier analysis, which analyzes the acoustical properties of voice and extracts these features [ED2010]. Important spectral information that distinguishes a sleep-deprived state from a non-sleep-deprived state relates to techniques such as Formant Analysis, Mel-Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs), and Harmonics-to-noise ratio (HNR) [KJ2009]. Studies have utilized the methodologies to increase the detection of SD,

which is non-invasive, through the usage of machine learning models and classification by SVM [TL2020].

2.2.1 Signal Processing

In voice, this entails examination and modification of sound waves generated by the human vocal apparatus, aiming to extract significant characteristics for uses like speech recognition and synthesis. The process starts with the vocal cords generating periodic pulse signals, which are subsequently modified by the vocal tract, a system that functions like a resonant filter. The vocal tract, comprising the mouth, tongue, teeth, and lips, modifies its shape while speaking, producing spectral peaks referred to as formants. These formants are essential for differentiating various vowel sounds from sentence(s) reading. Methods of signal processing, including Fourier analysis, break down the voice signal into frequency components and enable the extraction of features such as pitch and formants, which are crucial for efficient voice analysis and improvement [ED2010].

2.2.2 Acoustic Feature Extraction

Speech features like fundamental frequency (f_0), Energy, HNR, Formant position (F1–F6), Formant bandwidth (Fbw1–Fbw6), Duration of voiced–unvoiced segments, MFCCs, Linear frequency cepstrum coefficients (LFCCs), STM, and Long-term average spectrum (LTAS) are some basic acoustic features that have a significant effect on the classification models.

The f_0 is a feature equivalent to pitch. Energy is the intensity of a signal, which is modeled in the form of amplitude or height (in signal waves) at various

points in time [KA2022]. HNR is used to assess the sound quality, which is analyzed in spectral energy [KA2022]. Formant positions (F1–F6) are the formants where each has a threshold that represents the peak or the spectral maximum. They are the resonance frequencies of the vocal tract. Formant Bandwidth (Fbw1–Fbw6) measures the width of spectral energy bands surrounding each formant and helps model the shape and energy loss of the vocal tract (VT). This measurement is influenced by VT elasticity, tissue properties, and air turbulence within the VT. The duration of Voiced–Unvoiced Segments captures aspects of speech rhythm, including speech rate and pause structure, by measuring the lengths of voiced segments (e.g., vowels) and unvoiced segments (e.g., pauses) in speech. Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs) are commonly used in speech and emotion recognition because they capture detailed spectral information on a perceptually relevant frequency scale, giving a decorrelated and holistic spectrum representation [ZR2020]. Linear Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (LFCCs) are similar to MFCCs but use a linear frequency scale rather than the perceptual mel scale, emphasizing spectral changes and periodicity while being resilient to noise [ZX2011]. STM recognizes the dynamic interaction between spectral and temporal features of speech, studying the way frequency components change over time. It provides a mathematical characterization of speech rhythms and patterns, which makes it particularly appropriate for distinguishing normal and altered speech conditions [HA2020]. Finally, the Long-Term Average Spectrum (LTAS) averages spectral information over time, smoothing out formant details to show overall energy distribution across frequency bands, which makes it useful for broad assessments of voice quality [FJ2018].

2.2.3 Spectro-Temporal Modulation

It is an important speech processing technique in the fact that it captures the time evolution of frequency components. Compared to traditional feature extraction techniques, such as Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), STM provides a sufficient representation of speech in terms of spectral and temporal modulation. It is useful in processing distorted speech patterns due to disorders like sleep deprivation [AJ2023]. Current research shows that STM-based features enhance the accuracy of classifications in machine-learning models by better representing changes in vocal biomarkers, such as pitch stability, harmonic structure, and speech rhythm [GP2022]. It also aligns with segmentation conventions in related fields—short frames (20–30 ms) for feature extraction, 1–3 s windows for emotion/speaker tasks, and 10–30 s windows for cognitive state detection [MS2023]. These results highlight the benefits of STM to identify normal and impaired speech states. Although it is appropriate, several studies exist on the use of STM for SD detection. Most current research revolves around STM use in speech understanding, speaker identification, and language processing. Some mention its use in cognitive fatigue and physiological stressors detection, such as SD [YH2021].

2.3 Vocal Biomarker

These are quantifiable characteristics of the human voice, which give an indication of or predict his or her physiological or psychological state. Computational approaches, especially machine learning, analyze these biomarkers to automate the detection of a variety

of conditions or states. In comparison to the traditional approach that relied on the subjective ratings of speech, the recent development is toward objective automated analyses based on acoustic features [TE2024]. Features extracted from vocal recordings, such as pitch, spectral and cepstral coefficients, estimates of duration, and their functional combinations, form the input to machine-learning models [TL2021]. Sleep deprivation studies utilize both prosodic and voice quality features for detection. Changes in slow temporal modulations (prosody) and spectral features (voice quality) are observed in sleep-deprived individuals, underscoring the impact of physiological states on both aspects of speech. Interestingly, these changes manifest differently across individuals, with some exhibiting a flattened voice while others show increased animation [TE2024].

However, there are limitations to the use of vocal biomarkers. Individual variability significantly impacts how factors like sleep deprivation affect voice quality and prosody, necessitating the development of personalized models [HD2017]. Additionally, understanding the specific features used by classifiers is essential for accurate assessments. Another challenge is interpretability. While machine-learning models are able to achieve high accuracy, understanding the connection between acoustic features and the conditions they detect is critical [FG2021]. Techniques like reverse correlation help identify which aspects of the acoustic feature space contribute most to model decisions, enabling researchers to better understand the physiological or psychological basis of vocal biomarkers [TE2024].

2.3.1 Prosody

It is related to temporal modulations, and it involves the rhythm, pitch, loudness, and tempo of speech. It conveys important emotional information and meanings, helping listeners grasp the intent and even guess the emotional state of a

speaker [HD2017]. Pitch is the degree to which a voice is high or low, intensity is the volume, and rhythm is the pace of speech. While speech rate or the tempo measures how quickly a person speaks, frequently impacted by stress or exhaustion, pause patterns describe the time of pauses, which reveal emotional states or cognitive processes [FJ2018].

a) Pitch

It is defined as the perceived frequency of sound, is one of the most significant elements of prosody that affects speech perception and communication. The variability of the pitch to convey emotions, linguistic nuances, and intentions, so it is a significant aspect in both speech processing and recognition. Recent studies investigate the effects of SD on the vocal pitch. Evidence recommends that SD tends to decrease mean F0, thus causing a lower average pitch and reduced pitch variation. This change is often recognized as a more monotonous or “flattened voice” [NZ2024]. SD has also been associated with greater pitch perturbations, for example, jitter, which reflects vocal fold vibrations producing irregularity in the signal that contributes to perceived roughness or hoarseness in voice. An earlier study conducted by this group concerning the consequences of SD on voice expression did indicate that people undergoing SD revealed enhanced levels of pitch perturbations [HY1997].

Despite these insights, several gaps remain in the literature, including long-term effects, demographic variations, and mechanistic understanding. Most studies focus on short-term SD, with less understanding of the long-term

impact of chronic sleep deprivation on pitch characteristics. Very few studies have examined how factors such as age, gender, and linguistic background influence the relationship between SD and pitch alterations. Lastly, in mechanistic understanding, the physiological mechanisms underlying SD-induced changes in pitch are not well understood and require further investigation.

b) Speech Rhythm

It is an essential aspect of speech, involving timing, duration, and intonation patterns. Therefore, crucial for any effective communication and comprehension. SD has been shown to affect speech rhythm negatively, resulting in slower speech rates, longer pauses, and reduced intonation variability, making the speech pattern more monotonous or flattened. Based on evidence from recent research, it has been established that SD affects the cognitive functions that underlie speech production, including attention and executive control, which are important for a natural speech rhythm. Yet still, there is a gap in the studies that investigated the detailed changes in speech rhythm resulting from SD in different populations and languages [IM2020]. The Motor Theory of Speech Perception, as based on the study of Tomaso et. al., speech perception and production share neural mechanisms. Therefore, this theory supports the idea that disruptions in cognitive and motor functions caused by SD result in measurable changes in speech rhythm [TC2021].

Further research into how SD impacts speech rhythm in different languages and cultural contexts is needed to enable the development of

effective, non-invasive tools for SD diagnostics. This increases the accuracy of SD detection methods and contributes to better communication strategies in sleep-deprived individuals.

c) Speech Energy

It is defined as the amplitude of the speech signal and is one of the crucial elements of prosody that informs speech perception and emotional expression [OA2017]. Different functions or intensities of speech are able to signal different emotions or intentions and play a vital role in effective communication. Some recent research has investigated the impact of SD on speech intensity. Overall, evidence suggests SD causes a decrease in speech intensity, making the vocal delivery softer, less dynamic, and, in general, less expressive or emotionally blunt. The specific findings support sleep-deprived individuals as having lower vocal intensity associated with reduced emotional expressiveness [CD2021]. However, very few studies investigate the quantitative impact of SD on speech intensity, and hardly any systematically consider these variables across a number of languages or cultural contexts. The interaction of reduced speech intensity because of SD with speech recognition systems is also a relatively unexplored area [TE2024]. Evidence supports the idea that sleep-deprived individuals speak in a more monotonous, slower, and lower-energy manner [HB2019]. Most of the time, changes are needed in devising non-invasive tools for the diagnosis of SD and to improve human-computer interaction systems using vocal input [TE2024].

2.3.2 Voice Quality

It is considered part of prosody. It specifically pertains to the overall vocal image of the speaker, characterized by phonatory, articulatory, and muscular tension components. This definition was defined by Laver [EM2022]. Phonation type encompasses variations such as breathiness, creakiness, and harshness, which are able to convey different emotions or attitudes. Articulatory features refer to the way sounds are produced, influenced by the tension in the vocal cords and the shape of the vocal tract. Additionally, muscular tension during speech plays a role in how voice quality is perceived and often indicates the emotional state or intent of the speaker [NA2004].

a) Harmonic-to-Noise Ratio

Crucial in voice quality assessment as it helps distinguish the clear voice from the dysphonic voice. When the Harmonic-to-Noise Ratio (HNR) is high, it indicates a voice that has considerable harmonic content but low noise, thus perceived to be clearer and sounding more pleasant. A low HNR is dominated by noise. Hence, one perceives that the voice has roughness or breathiness [FJ2018]. Sleep deprivation affects the HNR negatively, causing noticeable changes in voice quality. Studies show that sleep deprivation lowers HNR, making the harmonic components of the voice less pronounced than the noise components [BA2011]. This makes the voice sound rougher and less clear. Perceptual changes are found in the fact that sleep-deprived people often describe their voices as "croaky," "rough," or "tired." [NZ2024] Such subjective perceptions align with lower HNR values, which indicate that listeners are able to detect voice degradation caused by insufficient sleep.

Acoustic analyses revealed that sleep-deprived voices, besides the reduced HNR, had increased jitter and shimmer scores, which have been interpreted to reflect increased randomness in pitch and loudness instability. These tend to increase subjective ratings of fatigue and decreased speech intelligibility [BA2011]. Physiologically, sleep deprivation impairs the control of muscles as well as the proper respiratory function necessary for the preservation of quality [HY1997]. This exacerbates the effects of decreased HNR. It is harder for an individual to produce clear and stable vocalizations. A sleep-deprived individual, particularly one who utilizes his or her voice for professional reasons, such as a singer or public speaker, has an HNR that is lower than normal, and performance is affected overall. Voice quality suffers, and the voice of the individual strains [ME2011].

b) Jitter and Shimmer

They are acoustic measures of voice quality that have been of utmost importance in speech and vocal health. Sleep deprivation has a strong influence on the voice characteristics and functions. Studies found that this increases jitter and shimmer, which implies greater instability of both pitch and loudness. Moreover, this results in a more raspy quality because studies have proven that participants have higher jitter and shimmer levels following sleep deprivation, which indicates voice degradation [KK2006]. Perceptual ratings also reveal that the voices of sleep-deprived subjects are often rated as "rough," "croaky," or "tired." [NZ2024] Such subjective observations are in agreement with objective results, which show that listeners are able to detect

the degradation in voice quality because of sleep deprivation. It also impacts the vocal performance by weakening control over muscles and breathing due to inflammation [TE2024]. The result is a condition known as vocal fatigue, which makes jitter and shimmer worse, making it harder to maintain a stable voice while speaking or singing [KK2006].

c) Formant Frequencies

The resonant frequencies of the vocal tract are called formant frequencies. Formant frequencies depend on the shape of the vocal tract, which is altered by the movement of the articulators (tongue, lips, jaw, etc.). When the vocal folds produce a sound, the vocal tract acts as a filter, amplifying the frequencies that correspond to its resonant frequencies and attenuating other frequencies. The formants are the peaks of the spectral envelope, and each vowel has a distinctive configuration of the formants [DL2020]. Sleep deprivation causes swelling in the vocal tract, thus modifying the shape of the vocal tract and consequently the frequencies of the formants. Furthermore, the degradation of voice quality is apparent upon sleep deprivation due to increasing jitter and shimmer, which indicates instability in pitch and loudness. Closely related to these acoustic changes are formant frequencies, which represent the resonant frequencies of the vocal tract. Since formant frequencies depend on the shape of the vocal tract, which is altered by the movement of the tongue, lips, and jaw, such as swelling caused by sleep deprivation, modifies these frequencies [TE2024].

2.4 Auditory Spectrogram

It is a two-dimensional representation of sound that has dimensions of frequency and time. It is generated using tools similar to the STRF-like model, which produces musical spectrograms or, for speech, the Neural System Laboratory (NSL) toolbox [TE2020]. These spectrograms are particularly valuable for analyzing complex acoustic signals such as speech. It serves as the basis for the extraction of spectro-temporal features, such as temporal and spectral modulation. It is used to visually represent an audio recording for observation or classification. In a research context, they are often processed into Spectro-Temporal Receptive Fields (STRFs), which provide a compressed representation of the modulation spectrum of speech and are often used in neuroscience and speech perception research [VJ2021].

2.4.1 Temporal Modulation

It represents the rate of change of a speech feature. In the spectrogram, it is displayed as colors, typically red and blue. This usually denotes prosody, like how the speech rate is heard like a monotone speech in which the speaker speaks in a singular tone for each word [TE2024]. This is the most critical concept in most areas, especially in auditory and visual perception, where it affects how people perceive sensory information. For example, in auditory processing, one needs to understand speech patterns as well as changes in sound intensity [EM2020]. Specifically, temporal modulations are fluctuations in sound intensity over time, and for speech, temporal modulations below 16 Hz are related to the syllabic rhythm [TE2024]. The articulation rate is the rate at which a given utterance is produced [GI2012]. Therefore, because sleep deprivation affects temporal modulations, which are related

to syllabic rhythm, it follows that sleep deprivation is also able to affect articulation rate.

2.4.2 Spectral Modulation

It represents the frequency of specific characteristics of generic auditory features within the speech signal [TE2024]. It is variations over time in frequency content or amplitude. Quite often analyzed together with time modulation, it gives insight into how sound is perceived. The combination of the two types of modulations forms what is referred to as spectrotemporal modulation. This is important for processing complex sounds like speech [AR2019].

2.4.3 Speech Modulation Spectrum

It has gained attention as a promising biomarker for sleep deprivation since it examines the rhythmic structure of speech by looking at intensity fluctuations over time [DN2017]. It has shown importance in the following, changes in temporal modulations, flattened or animated voice, and cognitive control impairment [TE2024]. Changes in the temporal modulations indicate that sleep deprivation affects the speech patterns of temporal modulation. The study conducted by Etienne et al. showed that voice recordings taken both before and after sleep deprivation were classified through a machine-learning model trained on the spectro-temporal modulation, which consisted of data taken from the modulation spectrum of the speech [TE2024].

The experiment demonstrated that sleep deprivation impacted the temporal modulations in the 2.0-8.0 Hz frequency band, corresponding to speech prosody and syllable rate. In other words, sleep deprivation leads to varying effects. On one hand, the energy within those frequencies decreases and produces a "flattened" voice, while

on the other hand, the energy within the same frequencies increases, giving a more "animated" voice. These rhythmic changes are hypothesized to result from impairments in cognitive control that occur due to sleep deprivation. The changes in prosody are caused by the impaired brain areas involved in planning and executing speech. This change type is found to correlate with self-reporting of sleepiness in terms of a "flattened" or "animated" voice and thus indicates that not all changes within the speech modulation spectrum are indeed overt markers of sleep deprivation by the person involved [TE2024].

Recent findings further support the significance of temporal modulations in speech by analyzing the modulation spectra across different types of spoken English, which include sentences, audiobooks, and conversational speech, exhibiting a consistent dominant modulation peak at 4.0-5.0 Hz, corresponding to the syllabic rate. They showed that the languages are consistent across different languages, which are French, Swedish, American English, British English, Chinese, German, Norwegian, Danish, and Dutch. The stated languages are consistent in terms of speech modulation spectrum, which shows a peak between 4.0-5.0 Hz that aligns with the syllabic rate of natural speech and correlates with the rhythmic pattern seen in prosody [DN2017]. Analysis across 17 languages in multiple families found that the speech envelope consistently peaks around 5 Hz—between 4.0-6.5 Hz—in 15 out of 17 languages, which matches the syllabic rate. They showed a distribution with a secondary peak at the harmonic frequency of ~10 Hz in Japanese and Tamil only. They emphasize the universality of low-frequency modulations in human languages [GJ2024]. Furthermore, a recent acoustic study across eight typologically different languages,

such as stress-timed, syllable-rate, proves that syllable-rate consistently occurs between 3.5-6.1 Hz range [ZY2023]. This supporting study aligns closely with previously documented speech modulation, which peaks between 4.0-5.0 Hz in the study of [DN2017] and proves the universality of temporal modulation features. Considering that the availability of the datasets consisting of sleep-deprived participants is sparse, choosing a specific language is not the main focus of the current study. Hence, “sleepy voices” sourced from the OSF site is used as a dataset, as this has prominent sleep-deprived participants.

2.5 Sleep Deprivation

It is a condition that arises from inadequate or insufficient sleep, thereby significantly affecting cognitive, physical, and emotional well-being. Long-term Sleep Deprivation (LSD) has been linked to deficits in decision-making, reduced alertness, and decreased productivity. Moreover, it disrupts normal speech patterns, which in turn affects vocal biomarkers such as pitch, speech rate, and jitter, which establish these measurable markers for the detection of sleep deprivation. Research has shown that it alters neural mechanisms, leading to slower speech, reduced pitch variability, and a monotonic tone. These changes are successfully identified using speech processing and machine learning methodologies, such as SVM [TE2024].

Research has shown that the subjects were given a controlled protocol involving two consecutive nights of restricted sleep (3 hours per night), which the authors have described as mild sleep deprivation. While the term "sleep deprivation" is used significantly throughout the

paper, the experimental condition represents partial sleep loss rather than extreme deprivation, distinguishing it from more severe protocols used in other research [TE2024]. Mild SD is significant in the actual context, where individuals experience partial sleep loss but are not severely sleep-deprived, which still affects their vocal and cognitive health. The ability to detect mild SD using acoustic features is significant for early intervention and fatigue management in occupational, clinical, and academic environments [SI2020].

The non-invasive voice analysis technique is an easily accessible way to identify the subtle yet significant effects of speech disorders. The technique is a practical solution to the early detection of a closely related condition that often accompanies SD and shares overlapping vocal characteristics. Both conditions are presented through changes in speech, which include reduced energy, slower articulation, and less variability in tone. Fatigue, however, usually adds additional vocal irregularities, such as a strained voice quality, from the effects of prolonged physical or mental exertion without recovery [VJ2023]. The article emphasizes that although SD and fatigue are related factors, they do follow different patterns in vocal biomarkers, allowing systems trained on different datasets to differentiate between the two [GX2022]. The correlation of SD with fatigue through generic auditory features is significantly critical in the development of a precise and reliable detection system.

However, fatigue encompasses a wide spectrum of mental and physical exhaustion that has occurred independently [GX2022]. Voice analysis studies have demonstrated that sleep-deprived individuals have characteristic vocal profiles that differ from those of fatigued-only individuals. For instance, while it is more probable to affect prosodic attributes such as pitch and speaking rate, fatigue only alters voice quality, breathiness, and hoarseness.

The analysis of the correlation between vocal features and fatigue points out how shared and distinct vocal features are utilized in accurate classification [HD2017].

2.6 Artificial Intelligence

This is a branch of computer science that makes a system able to perform some intelligent process or activity, for example, learning, reasoning, and self-correcting, just like any human. The problems of Artificial Intelligence (AI) are always narrowed down to be analyzed through the different possible answers, like means-end analysis in planning. With the increasing demand for the cloud, this is increasingly applied to resource optimization and hence treated as an optimization problem. Traditional methods have also discovered machine learning and deep learning, which make the most of the percentage of computing and cloud ecosystems in modern technology [BB2023].

2.6.1 Machine Learning

It is one of the principal research areas in artificial intelligence with the aim for a particular model to learn and improve from experience, especially from large amounts of data, without any explicit programming. It is an advanced development of algorithms for data pattern analysis, model construction, and adaptation over time to improve performance [AA2018]. The models are used in such applications as prediction, simulation of human reasoning, and intelligent decision-making, thus allowing machine behavior to be adaptive or autonomous [BB2023].

a) Supervised Learning

It constitutes a significant area of research in machine learning, with

numerous applications in multimedia processing. The defining characteristic of supervised learning is the availability of annotated training data, where a "supervisor" assigns labels to training examples, often as class labels for classification tasks. From this labeled data, supervised learning algorithms generate models that are able to subsequently classify new, unlabeled data [BA2011].

2.9 Support Vector Machine

The use of the classification model SVM in the detection of sleep deprivation through voice analysis significantly increases the efficiency in determining the problems of binary classification. SVM is dependent on major features that distinguish generic auditory features, such as STM, between the dimensionality of frequency, rate, and scale to classify either sleep-deprived or non-sleep-deprived states. Studies have shown that sleep-deprived voices sound monotonous and have a slower speech rate, thus making efficient acoustic signals for classification [TE2024].

It has been proven that SVM is highly accurate in SD detection patterns. A study using SVM achieved 86.1% classification accuracy of vocal features resulting from extreme SD, such as 60 hours without any sleep, thus its reliability in the detection of extreme effects of SD [NT2006]. However, the detection of mild SD is relatively difficult because subtle vocal changes are more difficult to detect [KJ2009]. Overall, the ability of SVM to handle high-dimensional feature spaces makes it a suitable and reliable approach to capture subtle variations in vocal patterns associated with mild SD.

2.8 Metrics on Speech Processing

The metrics pertinent to the student are focused on the accuracy of the model, recall, precision, specificity, F1 score, and BAcc, which are all needed for performance evaluation of voice models. These metrics on speech processing provide a comprehensive understanding of the SVM to classify, predict, and generalize effectively against the dataset that is fed into the model [SM2009]. Analyzing these criteria allows the researchers to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the model, to ensure its reliability and practical applicability on SD detection [PD2011].

2.8.1 Accuracy

Measures the extent to which cases are correctly predicted. True positives and true negatives are expressed as fractions of the total predictions made. From this, one is able to understand the SVM performance across all classes. However, the sole dependence on accuracy makes it misleading, especially in imbalanced datasets, simply because accuracy exaggerates the classification performance of the majority class and under-represented success in the case of minority classes [DJ2006]. Hence, while discussing accuracy, it is not relied on alone but taken into consideration together with other measures to evaluate the complete understanding of the effectiveness of the model. In a related study, accuracy was used as the performance measure to evaluate SVM classifiers in determining physiological and cognitive changes associated with SD. A health-related application case is well represented by a study that applied speech datasets using machine learning classification to classify states of SD with an accuracy of 84.75%, showing the efficiency of SVM [XY2021].

2.8.2 Recall

Defined by sensitivity or true positive rate, it is the ratio of positive instances that the model classifies correctly to all actual positives in a dataset. Thus, it indicates how well the model has been able to find all positive instances, which makes it a very important measurement of cases in which a negative instance results in very extreme effects [SM2009]. Therefore, positive classes are captured by the model itself, but are also taken along with other measurements like precision, which improves the overall reliability.

2.8.3 Precision

It is the ratio of positive instances predicted by the model. It reflects on the ability of the model to make positive predictions correctly and avoid false positives. Where the cost of a false positive is quite severe, precision matters most [FT2006]. It is important to balance both precision and recall to optimize model performance without skewed evaluations.

2.8.4 Specificity

It describes the ratio of actual negative cases correctly recognized by the model. It assesses the ability of the model to reject irrelevant instances to reduce the occurrence of false positives. It becomes important when the detection of the absence of a condition is as crucial as its presence. This measure ensures that non-target cases are accurately excluded from positive predictions. The model becomes as acceptable as being able to determine what is relevant from what is not when high specificity is applied [IM2020].

2.8.5 F1 Score

It signifies the harmonic mean for precision and recall to get a single score on two important facets of the analysis of models. The suitable definitions of precision are failures informed about recall alone, which differs significantly from reality when a great skewing occurs in most cases. Thus, a high F1 score truly indicates that a model correctly identifies its true positives while not counting many false positives, making a worldwide measure by which to evaluate classification effectiveness [SM2009].

2.8.6 Balanced Accuracy

It is a Performance measure that measures classification models across the platform when datasets turn out to be imbalanced for a class of model-based applications. This is because it takes on the true positive rate (recall) and true negative rate (specificity) within the equation of the definition. That makes this balance metric rather favorable for use in real-world scenarios, wherever datasets occur imbalanced under the consideration of different types of classes. This makes one ensure the fairness of such proficiency measures regarding both the class majority and class minority groups [VD2007]. Balanced accuracy now becomes a key performance metric in the identification of sleep deprivation through voice analysis. The study published in PLOS Computational Biology demonstrated that machine-learning analysis of vocal recordings is also used for good precision in sleep deprivation detection at an average balanced accuracy of 85% at the individual level. This means that class imbalances in model assessments are useful, especially in the detection between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived [TE2024].

2.9 Statistical Analysis

It evaluates the capability of machine learning models as a significant part of sleep deprivation detection through voice analysis. One of the most commonly used methods in SD research is repeated-measures Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA), which provides the researchers with a tool to compute different dependent variables under the condition of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived states. Repeated-measures MANOVA was used to compare the effect of 24-hour sleep deprivation on vocal parameters, such as F0, HNR, jitter (%), shimmer (%), and vocal intensity (dB) [IM2020]. The study shows that the SD had a significant effect on HNR values in female participants and reduced vocal intensity in male and female participants, especially in the samples of speech at the sentence level (see Table 1) [IM2020].

While MANOVA significantly determines the differences in vocal parameters, the use of different statistical methods, such as Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and performance metrics for machine learning, provides a further improvement for the reliability of the SVM in predicting SD using classification [SS2024]. ANOVA is currently customized for analyzing variability in the effect of SD on voice analysis [TE2024]. However, the most significant limitation in current research is the considerable overdependence on short-term SD (e.g., 24-36 hours), where the impact of chronic SD on vocal variability over long periods is unknown [TE2024]. Additionally, although current research clarifies the significance of HNR and vocal intensity changes, further investigation of combinations of multiple vocal biomarkers, such as jitter, shimmer, and F0, enhances the SVM model predictability [IM2020]. Based on the theoretical findings, the integration of different acoustic features beyond statistical learning methods is utilized for the effective detection of SD.

Type of Voice Sample	Voice Parameter	After 24-h Sleep Deprivation, Mean (SD)	After Nocturnal Sleep, Mean (SD)	F
(a) Female participants				
Sustained phonation /a/	Mean F_0 (Hz)	206.29 (17.25)	197.07 (30.68)	3.34
	Mean intensity (dB)	74.68 (6.94)	74.52 (6.37)	0.01
	HNR (dB)	20.60 (4.18)	19.34 (3.06)	4.67*
	Jitter (%)	0.43 (0.18)	0.49 (0.17)	2.67
	Simmer (%)	3.07 (1.45)	3.21 (2.01)	0.13
Words	Mean F_0 (Hz)	208.43 (22.59)	206.02 (19.09)	0.33
	Mean intensity (dB)	69.07 (4.47)	70.28 (5.31)	0.72
	HNR (dB)	11.79 (2.51)	10.80 (1.72)	6.22*
Sentences	Mean F_0 (Hz)	196.32 (19.97)	194.82 (20.04)	0.12
	Mean intensity (dB)	70.50 (4.84)	71.95 (4.84)	409.99***
	HNR (dB)	12.52 (1.52)	11.43 (2.10)	10.94**
(b) Male participants				
Sustained phonation /a/	Mean F_0 (Hz)	120.02 (9.97)	117.02 (11.04)	0.86
	Mean intensity (dB)	77.84 (7.05)	77.93 (4.44)	0.01
	HNR (dB)	20.98 (3.90)	21.51 (3.32)	0.74
	Jitter (%)	0.54 (0.32)	0.58 (0.46)	0.97
	Simmer (%)	3.14 (3.10)	2.73 (1.08)	0.73
Words	Mean F_0 (Hz)	135.45 (18.91)	132.28 (21.68)	0.35
	Mean intensity (dB)	73.70 (6.68)	74.06 (4.75)	0.16
	HNR (dB)	9.86 (2.19)	9.61 (1.61)	0.84
Sentences	Mean F_0 (Hz)	122.24 (11.95)	122.04 (15.83)	0.01
	Mean intensity (dB)	73.19 (5.71)	74.51 (5.24)	386.34***
	HNR (dB)	10.54 (1.60)	10.24 (1.73)	0.83

* $P < 0.05$.
** $P < 0.01$.
*** $P < 0.001$.
Abbreviation: SD, standard deviation.
Source: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30527970/>

Table 1. Mean Values of Acoustic Variables

2.10 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

As illustrated in Figure 1, the study is composed in the area of Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically focused on the Machine Learning (ML) paradigm through supervised learning. The theoretical framework is divided into two primary fields, speech processing and SD studies, which serve as the foundation for the SVM model. Beyond speech processing, the framework contains signal processing, speech analysis, and acoustic feature extraction, which leads to the extraction of STM features, such as spectral, temporal, and speech modulation,

which are significant aspects of vocal patterns that correspond to SD. The SD area analyzes mild SD, auditory spectrogram, and vocal biomarkers, which focus on the voice characteristics that shift in correspondence to fatigue. This structure guides the methodological direction of the study, which ensures the theoretical structure and empirical relevance of the study.

Figure 1. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework.

2.11 Synthesis

This section evaluates the connections of findings to SD based on several investigations. The synthesis assesses the relationship between speech characteristics and SD

detection, as well as how the stated tools, like spectral-temporal modulation (STM) are used. The article Temporal Modulations Reveal Distinct Rhythmic Properties of Speech and Music shows that human speech is generally rhythmic and has a mean syllable rate of 5-8 Hz in all languages [DN2017]. Thus, the dataset “sleepy voices” sourced from the OSF site is satisfactory for training since it is stated within the research that the temporal modulation features related to SD are found in a variety of languages [TE2024]. Similarly, the study “The Effects Of Sleep Deprivation On The Acoustic And Perceptual Characteristics Of Voice” by Harger stated that their participants used nonword recordings, which are “mab,” “mabshaib,” “mabshaytiedoib,” “mabspokweeflayb,” and “mabskreesploystroob.”

The reason why the nonwords are chosen and not a specific language is that they are unfamiliar. They reveal more about how sleep affects speech performance. People are likely to struggle more with unfamiliar sounds when they are sleep-deprived, making the nonwords a good test for sleep-related changes in speech ability [HD2017]. The research sourced from OSF, consisting of the “sleepy voices” dataset by Etienne Thoret, was gathered in “Sleep Deprivation Detected by Voice Analysis,” which stated that the accuracy reached 76% of accuracy in classification based on spectral and temporal modulations. However, individual variability, which included flattened or animated voice features, is to be seen in their analysis [TE2024].

The purpose of this study is to detect sleep deprivation through voice analysis by several research foundations with similar purposes. Existing literature provides valuable information regarding the relationship between SD, voice analysis, and vocal biomarkers,

hence the foundation of this study. Some of these approaches, however, such as the tool of STM as a feature extraction method, require further clarification and re-adoption to meet the purposes. This gap motivates the need to systematically refine STM-based methods to better capture sleep-related vocal changes. In the representation of the complexity of STM and its use in speech processing, this study adopts its use to enhance the extraction of appropriate acoustic patterns for the detection of SD. Furthermore, existing research has established various measures of performance in the evaluation of voice-based classification models, particularly those based on SVM. Although some of these studies are geared towards SD, others are rather generic in speech processing and classification, hence the applicability of their findings to this study. Metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision, F1 score, specificity, and BAcc have been widely established as decisive in the assessment of classification performance, and hence adopted by this study to ensure appropriate model assessment. Through synthesis of information from various sources and re-adoption of applicable methods, this study provides a well-theoretical and methodological framework for the application of a non-invasive and precise SD detection system. The integration of various research findings enhances the validity of the study and provides a foundation for future research in SD detection through voice analysis. Additionally, this synthesis highlights the importance of determining the variability on the implemented a solid SVM classifier as vocal input from various individuals are not uniform. Therefore, incorporating a population-level classifier is a must to generalize input from different individuals. Overall, the convergence of rhythmic speech analysis, STM-based feature extraction, and established evaluation metrics supports the feasibility of advancing voice-based sleep deprivation detection in both research and real-world applications.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter detailed the comprehensive methodology for the research on SD detection that utilized the SVM. As illustrated in Figure 3, the procedure began with data collection, which required a high-quality voice dataset that comprised generic auditory features, including scale, rate, and frequency. The selection of such datasets is done in an explicit way that ensures representation across individual and population levels. The preprocess stage includes audio format conversion, segmentation, and resampling rate. It ensures that the data quality is consistent for feature extraction. Feature extraction identifies key acoustic markers that include frequency, scale (spectral modulation), and rate (temporal modulation), all of which are very important inputs in using the SVM classifier. In the trained stage of the SVM, it is applied to improve the performance of a classifier developed to differentiate between sleep-deprived (post-session) and non-sleep-deprived (pre-session) conditions. The performance of the classifier is measured in terms of metrics of evaluation, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc, particularly focused on specific speech features. Statistical analysis ensures comprehension that confirms the capability of SVM for the detection of generic auditory features for SD. Additionally, the model is deployed and integrated into a mobile application, making it accessible for SD detection. Every stage of the methodological process is directed to establish a valid and non-invasive method of SD detection by vocal analysis in public health. This structured methodology, therefore, provides a basis for systematically and comprehensively addressing the research objectives.

3.1 Research Design

The study is designed to employ both quantitative and experimental research methods. The study involves measuring and analyzing acoustic data, such as speech features. Hence, it is experimental as the independent variables are frequency, rate, and scale modulation from the datasets that are manipulated using the spectro-temporal receptive field (STRF), which in turn are analyzed like what the STM looks upon the rate-scale and rate-frequency representation. Datasets are gathered to make the article of that data source, verified, and reviewed first to determine if it is authentic and relevant for the current study or not. The quality of the gathered datasets is assessed to figure out which entries are not useful, and to have them go through data cleaning. Data profiling techniques are then employed to rename the file names and to standardize them, as different data sources have different file naming conventions. The stated model, SVM, is tested using the acquired voice datasets, which are collected under controlled conditions and performed during hospital visits or inside their homes. The conditions are controlled, such as the participants recorded in an isolated room, away from noise or external background noise, which has less variability [TE2024]. In terms of research questions, those are answered through a series of tests and analyses using various statistical tools from the collected data sources. Unexpected questions that arise during the research phase are noted and resolved if possible, as long as the availability of the tools and information exists. By following this structured approach, the study ensures that the SVM classifier, trained with the said dataset, is evaluated with sufficient precision across diverse vocal patterns and session conditions. Ultimately, this experimental framework establishes a solid foundation for validating voice analysis as an accessible method for sleep health monitoring.

3.2 Dataset Collection and Characterization

This thesis aims to establish an SD by voice analysis on the access and efficient exploitation of the large dataset. For this research study, a downloadable dataset referred to by Etienne Thoret, sourced from the Open Science Framework (OSF) site, consists of “sleepy voices”. Some leading voice data sites for machine learning-based study were used [TE2022]. The sampling rate of the audio consists of 44.1 kHz, which was then downsampled to 16 kHz during the preprocessing stage. The type of speech script is excerpt reading, which is a short section that is taken from a longer piece of writing. The nature and characteristics of the dataset are mainly in the form of an AIFF file. A file that is similar to Waveform Audio File Format (WAV) but it is closed-sourced as it was developed by Apple. The reason for the choice of file type is the use of an Apple portable recorder (Zoom H1/MB), which was used for stereo-recording and mono-recording. The total number of female participants was initially 24. However, two participants encountered audio recording issues, so their recordings were discarded, leaving 22 female participants for the experiment. Primarily, the language used is French. Among all participants, they were instructed to read 10 minutes of different chapters of the book named "Le Comte de Monte Cristo" (The Count of Monte Cristo) by Alexandre Dumas [AD2025]. The total number of audio recordings is 144, each of which has an average duration of 5 minutes and 16 seconds, resulting in 2720 segmented audio after pre-processing each audio recording. For the dataset, there exist audio recordings of two types, which are sleep-deprived (post-session) audio recordings and non-sleep-deprived (pre-session) audio recordings (see Table 2) [TE2024]. Furthermore, the structured and well-annotated nature of the dataset makes it suitable for supervised learning, which enables reliable training, validation, and evaluation of the SVM model for mild SD detection.

Dataset	“sleepy voices”
Dataset Source	Open Science Framework (OSF)
Sampling Rate (kHz)	44.1 kHz
Type	Excerpt reading
Categories	Sleep-deprived (post-sessions) and non-sleep-deprived (pre-sessions)
Language	French
Format of Audio	Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF)
Total Number of Subjects	24
Total Number of Audio	144
Number of Sessions	6
Average Audio Duration	5 minutes and 16 seconds
Total Number of Segmented Samples	2,720

Table 2. Sleep Voices Dataset Characteristics.

The type of audio records is pre-sessions (non-sleep-deprived) on day one and post-sessions (sleep-deprived) on day three, 1397 in pre-sessions, and 1323 in post-sessions across six sessions on day one and day two. The six sessions in pre-sessions and post-sessions were separated into three different times, which are session one (9:00 am), session two (3:00 pm), and session three (5:00 pm). Specifically, there are 890 in the session one segmented sample, 909 in the session two segmented sample recorded, and 903 in session three, with a total of 2720 segmented samples across three sessions (see Table 3).

Sessions	Pre-session	Post-session	Total
Session 1	470	420	890
Session 2	475	452	909
Session 3	452	451	903
Total	1397	1323	2720

Table 3. Sleepy Voices Annotation Count Per Session.

The experiment spanned three days, with participants following a controlled sleep schedule. On day one (baseline condition), they were in the baseline condition (non-sleep-deprived) during this day, and they were assessed in the laboratory from 9:00 am to 7:00 pm, continuously. After the assessment, participants followed the restriction of a sleep schedule to no more than 3 hours (3:00 am to 6:00 am). On day two, participants were sleep-deprived by restricting their sleep to no more than 3 hours (3:00 am to 6:00 am) at the end of day one, and to follow their regular routine outside the laboratory. By day 3, participants were sleep-deprived at the end of day two for two consecutive nights and assessed in the laboratory from 9:00 am to 11:00 am and 3:00 pm to 7:00 pm (see Figure 2) [TE2024].

Figure 2. Sleepy Voices Schedule.

The dataset was divided into three subsets, namely training, validation, and testing. 80% of the dataset was used for training, which amounts to 2,176 segmented samples, which is more than enough for the SVM model to train the feature representations efficiently. 10% of the data sums up to 272 segmented samples, which were put aside for validation, where hyperparameter tuning takes place without the risk of overfitting. The remaining 10%, that is,

272 segmented samples, were kept for testing reasons so that they are checked under unseen conditions (see Table 4).

Activity	Percentage Distribution	Number of annotations
Training	80%	2,176
Validation	10%	272
Testing	10%	272
Total	100%	2720

Table 4. Data Splitting of Sleepy Voices.

The sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived groups comprised the total dataset to form three subsets, which are training, validation, and testing. To make the dataset have an equivalent distribution, the dataset consists of 1397 pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) samples and 1323 post-session (sleep-deprived) samples. Specifically, the non-sleep-deprived group was divided into 1,118 for training, 140 for validation, and 139 for testing, and proportionally, the sleep-deprived group was divided into 1,059 for training, 132 for validation, and 132 for testing. This proportional split by categories ensures that the test set provides learning support, hyperparameter optimization, and unbiased evaluation for the SVM classifier as represented in Table 5.

Categories	Train	Validation	Test	Total
Pre-session (non-sleep-deprived)	1,118	140	139	1397
Post-session (sleep-deprived)	1,060	132	131	1323
Total	2,177	272	271	2720

Table 5. Dataset Training / Validation / Test Split of Sleep Voices.

3.3 Data Procedures

This section details the processes involved in preparing and analyzing data to train a model for SD detection using speech features. The procedure is divided into stages to achieve sufficient SVM in SD detection. This process ensures that the input data is clean, structured, and optimized for accurate and efficient machine-learning model performance.

3.3.1 Procedures

The development of SD in speech features analysis and classification of machine learning, which is the SVM, involves multiple operations executed systematically. The different components associated with vocal analysis and predictive modeling, as identified in the literature review section of the current study, are taken into great consideration while designing the operational framework. The entire operational framework, as depicted in Figure 3, depicts the processes carried out in defining the research objectives, data collection, preprocessing, feature extraction, and training, validating, and testing of the classification model. This framework represents the steps handled sequentially in the study, starting with the definition of the research problem and formulation of the hypotheses, voice data collection and cleaning, and application of advanced signal processing techniques. The procedures are categorized into subsections that represent the steps required for the preparation, analysis, and evaluation of the system comprehensively. Furthermore, the logical progression facilitates clear transitions from experimental data analysis to the practical deployment of SD detection. By adhering to the stated structured workflow, the approaches ensured that the performance of the model is optimized for accessibility and user interaction.

Figure 3. Operational Framework.

3.4 Data Cleaning

It is an important phase in the preprocessing stage, which is designed to make the dataset employed for SD detection free of irrelevant audio, inconsistencies, and missing values. The process involves the removal of defective or incomplete audio recordings and the standardization of the sampling rate. The main aim of data cleaning is to deliver structured and high-quality audio data suitable for appropriate feature extraction. Maintaining consistency in the dataset allows the SVM classifier to learn significant patterns without interference from extraneous variables. The cleaned dataset provides a reliable basis for subsequent analysis, thus reducing errors and enhancing the performance of the SD detection model as a whole. These refining procedures ensure that the input signals are free from technical artifacts that could otherwise skew the extraction of spectro-temporal features. Hence, reducing unnecessary training data to ensure consistency for the SVM classifier.

3.4.1 Pre-processing

It is an essential process that ensures data quality and consistency before training a model like the SVM for SD detection. In the preprocessing phase, there are audio format conversion, segmentation, and resampling rate, all of which are designed to maximize feature extraction and improve the SVM efficiency. The original recordings were captured using Zoom H1 and MB stereo recorders, producing audio in AIFF format. To ensure compatibility with the machine learning pipeline and retain high voice quality, these recordings were first converted to WAV format, a lossless and widely supported format for audio analysis tasks. Next is the resampling rate, where the original 44.1 kHz recordings are resampled to 16 kHz, which aligns with the standard practices of speech processing and maintains the consistency of vocal information up to 8 kHz. Afterwards, segmentation is done, wherein 144 raw voice recording is segmented into 15-second units. Segmentation enables appropriate analysis with localized speech features and enhances the model to detect subtle variations in generic auditory features associated with SD. In this study, a single 15-second segment was used for the trained SVM model to provide an optimal balance between temporal resolution and vocal stationarity. The STM features were computed over 40-ms temporal windows, then averaged over 3,841 successive windows, which corresponds to approximately 15 seconds of audio. In Formula 1, the number of successive windows in short-time analysis is applied during STM feature extraction. In this process, the 15,000-ms (15-second) audio segment was divided into overlapping frames, each with a 40-ms window length and a 4-ms hop size (see Formula 1).

$$\text{Successive Windows} = \left\lfloor \frac{\text{Total Duration} - \text{Window Length}}{\text{Hop Size}} \right\rfloor + 1$$

Formula 1. Number of Successive Windows.

Where Total Duration is 15,000-ms, Window Length is 40-ms, and Hop Size is 4-ms. Each window captures temporal modulation in the speech signal, which allows the STM to analyze both rapid and slow modulation in patterns across time and frequency. The average of 3841 frames provides a constant representation for spectro-temporal, which balances temporal resolution that reduces computational cost and ensures reliable feature extraction for SVM.

3.5 Processing

After data cleaning, the next significant step is to process the data, where researchers extract and prepare the generic auditory features for SVM training for classification. The primary goal is to transform raw, preprocessed voice audio data into informative STM features that extract both frequency, spectral (scale), and temporal (rate) modulation features of speech. Additionally, dimensionality reduction processes, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA), are employed to remove redundant information while preserving the most critical features. The output of this process is an organized, high-quality feature set that the researchers use appropriately for SVM training. By narrowing the feature set to its most influential components, the researchers ensure that the SVM model focuses on the subtle vocal indicators most characteristic of sleep deprivation.

3.5.1 Feature Extraction

It is an important process in audio signal processing for SD detection, where fundamental spectro-temporal features are extracted to serve as inputs for a classification model. In the present research, the Spectro-Temporal Residual Field (STRF) model is utilized to obtain STM representations, which capture both the spectral and temporal modulations inherent in speech signals [TE2024]. The researchers extracted the frequency, spectral (scale), and temporal (rate) modulation through STM analysis, which is important while differentiating between sleep-deprived speech patterns. Frequency represents the acoustic content of speech on a logarithmic frequency scale, simulating how the human cochlea analyzes sound, while scale, or spectral modulation, represents the spread of speech energy over such frequency bands, while rate, or temporal modulation, represents dynamic temporal processes such as rhythm and speech rate [NS2022]. Scale-rate representation, by averaging over frequency bands, provides an appropriate set of features that capture prominent modulation patterns, making it suitable for SVM classification. The STM features are represented with the use of a STRF model [ET2021]. It is structured in a dimensionality of (128, 8, 22) shape, where 128 represents the number of auditory channels, eight represents the spectral modulation (scale), and 22 represents the temporal modulation (rate). To balance temporal detail with vocal stationarity, the recordings are then divided into equal time intervals, which are normally 40 milliseconds in duration, each consisting of an average of 3,841 successive 40-millisecond windows used to compute STM features. This window duration is optimal for the model as it is long enough to capture important vocal features related

to mild SD, such as flattened, slowed rhythm. However, it is short enough not to detect non-stationary content such as topic shifts or emotional alteration [TE2024]. These features are used as input to the SVM classifier to detect mild SD based on STM changes.

3.5.2 Normalization

Researchers use normalization as an essential feature in the processing phase to provide consistency across all extracted features, which enhances the efficiency of the SVM classifier. Normalization constitutes two essential stages, global normalization and standardization. Researchers make use of global normalization ($\text{tabStrf} / \max(\text{tabStrf})$) for the first step of normalizing feature values within a standard range, typically in between 0 and 1, thereby preventing variability due to varying levels of amplitudes within the original raw audio signals. This supports providing dimensionally equivalent features, thereby making it easy for the model to learn effectively. Researchers implemented standardization that utilized `StandardScaler()` to standardize the dataset through mean subtraction and dividing by standard deviation, therefore, achieving zero mean and unit variance. The application of the standardization approach eliminates bias from disparate feature scales while ensuring each feature has an equivalent contribution towards classification. By adopting the above-discussed normalization steps, researchers promote increased accuracy and consistency in the detection of the SD system, accelerating convergence speed and performance of the overall SVM model and avoiding threats posed by numerical instability.

3.5.3 Dimensionality Reduction

It is an essential step in machine learning model optimization, allowing for increased efficiency and improved performance in classification. Researchers use PCA to reduce the number of features while retaining the most important features in the dataset. PCA does this by converting high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional representation, retaining the important variance that is vital in separating patterns. By eliminating redundant or highly correlated features, researchers improve computational efficiency and avoid overfitting. This step allows the SVM to focus on the most important STM features, thus improving the accuracy of classification in sleep deprivation detection. The code of PCA for dimensionality reduction is applied within a pipeline.

3.6 Model Training

The SVM model is trained on the “sleepy voices” dataset provided on the OSF site, resolving different generic auditory features that are derived from voice recordings. Hyperparameter tunings, specifically kernel type (Radial Basis Function - RBF), and stratified five-fold cross-validation together with grid search, were fine-tuned to enhance the overall performance of this model. RBF kernels are utilized as they perform a reliable task when dealing with non-linear interactions within the space [TE2024]. Their superior generalization capabilities make them ideal for this application. Optimal hyperparameters by grid search and stratified five-fold cross-validation are performed to tune the optimum parameters, avoiding overfitting while retaining accuracy. The features extracted from voice, such as generic STM,

are input to the SVM model in the training process. Steps of preprocessing, such as normalization and application of dimensionality reduction using PCA on the dataset, condition it accordingly for training. Although PCA reduces the dimensionality of the feature set, it retains most of the information in the data, which increases computational effectiveness. The model, which is trained with stratified five-fold cross-validation, takes into account every fold to have the right proportion of an imbalanced dataset of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived samples. Additionally, the study employs 10% for validation and 10% for testing purposes of the dataset withheld. Train the model with iterations to optimize the SVM to correctly classify the instances of mild SD, overcoming the challenges brought by noise, variability in vocal features, and even differences between the two classes.

3.7 Model Validation

In this study on SD detection using SVM, model validation is one of the important procedures that proves to represent the integrity and generalizability of the classifier. It begins with the approach of the stratified five-fold cross-validation, which is withheld for validation and testing purposes. These methods ensure that the model is validated and tested with unseen and imbalanced data, which means overfitting and biases are resolved. Additionally, it allows estimation of how it performs to generalize across different participants. The stratified five-fold cross-validation resolves the variability within the dataset [VG2018]. In this regard, overfitting and underfitting during the training process are mitigated, and then the dimensionality reduction of the data using PCA explains more than 90% of the variance. The SVM model utilizes RBF kernel hyperparameters that are tuned using a stratified five-fold

cross-validation on the training set. The SVM classifier performance is measured based on performance metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Specificity, and BAcc. This validation framework ensures that the classifier is reliable, reduces bias, and operates reliably in SD detection through voice analysis.

3.7.1 Hyperparameter Tuning

To enhance the performance of the SVM model, the researchers applied Grid Search with stratified five-fold cross-validation to optimize hyperparameters. This comprehensively searches through various kernel types, C values, and gamma combinations to identify the optimal configuration. The RBF kernel is used since it learns complex patterns in high-dimensional feature space. The C parameter regulates the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing the number of classification errors, and gamma regulates the influence employed by individual training samples. Cycling through various sets of parameters, the researchers make sure that the model achieves the maximum possible performance and generalizability for the detection of SD based on generic auditory features.

3.8 Performance Metrics

The performance metrics, such as fundamental information, show the effectiveness of SVM in providing the classification of sleep deprivation based on voice analysis. Such performance metrics outline how the model works to classify cases as sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived, and also identify both the true positives and false negatives. All these metrics are understood and optimized for enhanced model improvement, especially in real

applications, where accurate SD mitigates accidents and maintains health [MI2024]. The following subsection discusses the application of performance metrics that describe the performance of the SVM classifier and its feasibility in SD detection.

3.8.1 Confusion Matrix

It becomes an important tool in the evaluation of the SVM performance. It provides a precise analysis since it shows counts of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN), but also easily permits the identification of such misclassification, which are optionally used to improve the accuracy of the model. In a binary classification problem, the confusion matrix is a 2 x 2 matrix, containing four values (see Table 6). The confusion matrix for SD detection clarifies how often this subject has been correctly and incorrectly classified as sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived. The number of TP indicates the correctly identified sleep-deprived individuals, while FP represents those who are classified as non-sleep-deprived individuals incorrectly as sleep-deprived. FN occurs when the sleep-deprived case is misclassified and becomes a TN, while TN indicates the correct classification of a subject, as non-sleep-deprived [VJ2023].

		Actual Class	
		Positive (P)	Negative (N)
Predicted Class	Positive (P)	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
	Negative (N)	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

Table 6. Confusion Matrix.

3.8.2 Accuracy

One of the measures of the performance of a learning model is accuracy, especially for binary classification problems such as the diagnosis of SD using SVM. It is defined as the proportion of true, positive, and negative predictions made by the classifier out of the total predictions made (see Formula 2). Accuracy is a practical point to estimate the general performance of the model, providing an intuitive understanding of the ability of the model to correctly classify sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived individuals. It is particularly effective when the dataset is balanced, that is, when states (sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived) are equally represented. However, in the case of class imbalances, accuracy alone is very misleading, as there is a possibility that the model achieves high accuracy by mostly predicting the majority class.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP}$$

Formula 2. Accuracy.

3.8.3 Precision

The performance metric is used to determine how well the SVM classifier distinguishes between subjects that are sleep-deprived and those that are non-sleep-deprived. Defined as the total number of true positive predictions divided

by all of the positive classifications provided by the classifier (see Formula 3). Precision is important when false positives are to be minimized. For instance, while studying SD detection, if a false positive (misinterpreting a non-sleep-deprived person as sleep-deprived) occurred, it suggests unnecessary interventional or therapeutic actions. Thus, precision measurement tells the researchers about how well the model avoids such incorrect inferences and ascertains the validity of its positive predictions in mild SD detection.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Formula 3. Precision.

3.8.4 Recall

It is also known as sensitivity or true positive rate. It is the percentage of actual positives, in this case, sleep-deprived individuals, which the model identifies correctly. In the SVM-based detection system of sleep deprivation, it is considered the most important aspect, as it indicates the count of false negatives where the model fails to recognize the concerned sleep-deprived people. High recall means that the model correctly identifies individuals at risk of SD. This is an important aspect for applications targeted at health and safety interventions (see Formula 4). It is particularly crucial in health-oriented applications, such as SD detection, since failing to detect sleep-deprived individuals is a fatal condition. In instances, it was one of the

performance metrics utilized in most SVM-based studies to identify at-risk subjects to the effects of SD. One of them demonstrated that its SVM model achieved a sensitivity or recall of 82.76% for SD-induced cognitive impairment detection based on features learned from behavioral and physiological data [XY2021]. This emphasis on recall ensures that the system misclassifies correct outputs of those not sleep-deprived, but catches all the actual cases of SD. Such performance is critical in safety-critical domains like aviation and health care, where missing one instance of SD is catastrophic.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Formula 4. Recall.

3.8.5 F1 Score

It is known as the prominent performance measure of a classificatory model, especially for skewed datasets like SD detection. It is defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. This is an excellent balance between these two issues in situations in which both false positives and false negatives incur a great cost. A good balance is especially helpful. It measures between 0 and 1 (see Formula 5). The more efficient the score is, the closer it is to 1, and consequently, the more efficient the performance of the model under evaluation.

For SVM for SD detection, it calculates the F1 Score of how well the model classifies non-sleep-deprived people and simultaneously minimizes the false positives that are misclassified as non-sleep-deprived, and also minimizes the false negatives that are sleep-deprived. This is especially important in health applications, where the implications of misclassification have actual implications for safety and well-being. For example, to evaluate the machine learning model suitable for sleep-related applications, it showed the importance of maintaining a balance between the precision and recall of the model. This measure enabled one to make confident identifications of impaired states due to lack of sleep while avoiding possible biases coming from the uneven class distribution [MS2019].

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot \textit{Precision} \cdot \textit{Recall}}{\textit{Precision} + \textit{Recall}}$$

Formula 5. F1 Score.

3.8.6 Specificity

It is another relevant metric for the evaluation of classification algorithms, such as SVM, in binary tasks like SD detection, the true negative rate, or specificity. Specifically, it defines the percentage of true negatives correctly classified by the classifier overall actual negatives, that is, non-sleep-deprived subjects. A relevant measure is that its value acts as a moderator against false recognitions of

non-sleep-deprived people as SD subjects, thereby minimizing the inappropriate interventions (see Formula 6).

It gives an insight into how well the model avoids false positives, balancing its performance with sensitivity or the true positive rate. High specificity ensures that the detection system is reliable to classify those who are not sleep-deprived correctly, especially in real-world applications, when overdiagnosis strains healthcare systems. Previous studies on the application of machine learning models to sleep deprivation detection report a high SVM specificity of 86.67% [XY2021]. In the context of the model, it was efficient at eliminating cases of non-sleep-deprived populations while maintaining integral sensitivity to sleep-deprived ones. It makes quite a lot of sense in evaluating imbalanced datasets, whereby the model does not create a bias towards the majority class but instead produces meaningful results for the minority classes.

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{(TN + FP)}$$

Formula 6. Specificity.

3.8.7 Balanced Accuracy

The performance measure used to assess the classification model, mainly with imbalanced data, is the BAcc. It is the average sensitivity to the true positive rate together with the specificity, which is nothing but the average true negative rate. It is just an average value such that both classes have a balanced estimation regarding their

performance (see Formula 7). This is especially the case in the detection of mild SD because otherwise, the performance evaluations are skewed by the difference between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived data. BAcc, which emphasizes fairness across all classes, provides a more reliable measure of the ability of the model to generalize well to unseen data. It is used for evaluating the capability of the classifier SVM to detect SD accurately while minimizing the false positives as well as false negatives concurrently, and ensures an integral assessment of the system integrity [TE2024].

$$\text{Balance Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Recall} + \text{Specificity}}{2}$$

Formula 7. Balanced Accuracy.

3.9 Model Performance Evaluation

This section discusses the model evaluation of the SVM classifier in the detection of SD based on STM features. Model performance was measured with various techniques to ensure reliability, determine if it is underfit or overfit, and evaluate the performance of the classifier to generalize to unseen data. Learning curves were used to show the effect of adding more samples during the training process, while the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) and Validation Curve analyses were conducted to evaluate classifier performance under various thresholds.

3.9.1 Learning Curve

The learning curve plots the training and validation performance of the SVM model as a function of the training set size. In the plotted results, the training score remains consistently high regardless of the size of the training dataset, suggesting that the model fits the training data well even with a small number of examples. On the other hand, the validation (development) score increases consistently as the size of the training set increases. The validation score eventually reaches a plateau, indicating that further increasing the training data size does not significantly enhance the generalization performance of the model. The observation of such a plateau suggests that it requires additional data that results in a worse performance, and that the current dataset size is sufficient for training an effective model.

3.9.2 AUC-ROC

The researchers use the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) to evaluate the capability of the model in the differences between the dimensions of spectro-temporal modulation, such as the frequency-rate (FR), frequency-scale (FS), scale-rate (SR), and combined features across all decision thresholds. The ROC curve plots the true positive rate (Recall) against the false positive rate (1 - Specificity). AUC values close to 1.0 indicate a perfect model, and 0 indicates a poor model, while values around 0.5 suggest random guessing (see Figure 4) {TO2014}. For imbalanced datasets, the AUC-ROC provides an overall separability measure without favoring either class. Overall, this metric enables a reliable comparison between those dimensions to determine which has a better AUC value or classification performance.

Figure 4. AUC-ROC Quality of the Model.

3.9.3 Validation Curve

It was used to demonstrate how the SVM performance varies with changes in an important hyperparameter, such as the regularization parameter C . The C parameter determines the trade-off between the minimization of the training error and testing error in the form of misclassification penalties. For the validation curve, the training and validation scores were plotted against changing values of C . The model was too constrained, and underfitting occurred at a very low value of C . Very large values of C , however, led to overfitting, where the model produced an optimal fit to the training set but poor validation performance on unseen data. The value of C was set at the point where the validation score attained its optimal value, thereby achieving the optimal trade-off between bias and variance. This correct tuning, based on the validation curve, was instrumental in improving the generalization performance of the

SVM model. Thus, ensuring stable and reliable performance when the model is applied to unseen or real-world data.

3.10 Model Fit

It refers to the measurement of how well a machine learning model adapts to newly encountered data apart from its training data. A model is said to be well-fitted if it accurately approximates the output when it is given new data, which makes it more precise in producing its results. An improperly fit model produces incorrect predictions, making it less usable and less likely to be used for making decisions. The challenges that come when a model is not well-fitted are underfitting and overfitting.

3.10.1 Underfit

It occurs when a machine learning model is so simple that it does not capture the important patterns in the data, which results in poor predictive performance on the training set and new, unseen data. It often happens when using an overly basic model, lacking features, limited data, or excessive regularization, which leads to high bias and low accuracy. This hinders the predictability and usefulness for decisions of the model, rendering it ineffective for decision-making purposes.

3.10.2 Overfit

It happens when the model learns the details and noise in the training data excessively, which results in negatively impacting its performance on new, unseen data. It performs well with very high accuracy on the training dataset, but an overfitting model fails to generalize to real life because it "memorizes" rather than

"understands" the underlying patterns. This problem commonly arises from an overly complex model, insufficient data, or overtraining without regularization. Cross-validation, early stopping, and regularization techniques help prevent overfitting and improve their generalization ability.

3.11 Statistical Analysis

It serves as both a performance feature and an assessment tool for the classification model applied to identify sleep deprivation through generic auditory features. In this study, a one-way Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) is used to compare variations in the SVM performance metrics—accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc—under different test conditions. One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Independent Two-Sample T-test were also employed to determine whether there were statistically significant differences across feature dimensions and between individual- and population-level performance.

3.11.1 One-Way Multivariate Analysis of Variance

In this study, One-Way MANOVA is employed to determine whether the SVM classifier exhibits statistically significant multivariate differences in performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and BAcc, between the STM, such as frequency-rate, frequency-scale, scale-rate, and frequency-scale-rate (combined dimensions). It is applied to determine whether the classification model exhibits significant multivariate differences in its performance metrics across the STM through generic auditory features. For instance, in testing a single feature of STM, if the model maintains high accuracy across several tests, similar expectations apply

when other features are evaluated. To evaluate the outcome of MANOVA, the research utilizes Wilk's Lambda (λ), a test statistic that computes the ratio of within-group variation to the total variation, including within-group and between-group variation. The statistic is algebraically expressed as the determinant of the within-group sum of squares and cross-products matrix (W) divided by the determinant of the sum of the within-group and between-group matrices ($W + B$).

$$\lambda = \frac{|W|}{|W + B|}$$

Formula 8. One-Way MANOVA.

3.11.2 One-Way Analysis of Variance

The researchers utilized One-Way ANOVA to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the average STM features between pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) and post-session (sleep-deprived) conditions. The test was used specifically to evaluate the impact of SD on each STM representation, which are FS, FR, and SR. Since the dataset used in this study is the "Sleepy Voices" dataset from the OSF, collected and released by Etienne Thoret, and because the original researchers already incorporated the Stanford Sleepiness Scale (SSS) scores per session, it was not necessary to re-administer the SSS. The One-Way ANOVA evaluates whether the means of two or more independent groups differ significantly.

In this context, the researchers assess whether the average STM values differ between the pre-session and post-session conditions (see Formula 9).

$$F = \frac{MST}{MSE}$$

$$MST = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{T_i^2}{n_i}\right) - \left(\frac{G^2}{n}\right)}{k - 1}$$

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (Y_{ij})^2 - \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{T_i^2}{n_i}\right)}{n - k}$$

Formula 9. One-way ANOVA.

3.11.3 Independent Two-Sample T-test

In this study, an Independent Two-Sample T-test, Welch's t-test, was utilized to statistically differentiate population-level and individual-level SVM classification model BAcc measures. Unlike the standard Student t-test, the Welch's t-test does not require equal variances between groups, and as such, it is more flexible and suitable for use in instances where homogeneity of variance is not guaranteed, such as comparing performance across multiple subjects or datasets. This test estimates the difference between two sample means, with consideration for unequal sample sizes and variances, and provides a more precise result as to whether the differences noted are significant or not. A significance level of 0.05 was used to determine if differences

in classification performance were not by chance but instead reflected a significant difference between the two model approaches. Welch's t-test is shown in formula 8.

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{N_2}}} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{se_1^2 + se_2^2}}$$

Formula 10. Independent Two-Sample T-test.

3.12 Ethical Considerations

A fundamental concern remains that ethical compliance was prioritized to safeguard the privacy, dignity, rights, and confidentiality of individuals whose voice recordings are being analyzed, and these concerns are addressed in the process of the study. Since the system analyzes audio recordings, participants give their informed consent about the purpose, scope, and procedures of the study, knowing exactly how their data is collected and stored and how these data are used. Informed consent is acquired to ensure that participation is voluntary and that individuals are free to withdraw at any time without consequence. Encryption of data is used during storage and transmission, and the collected audio data is anonymized to protect against unauthorized access, misuse, or data breaches. Audio recordings are only made if the user decides to use them. Hence, the system does not record any audio when there is no activity or when the recording interaction has not been initiated by the user. Moreover, the dataset on which the model was trained was taken from an open-access research dataset that

was already pre-approved for ethical clearance, and therefore, no new participants were subjected to sleep deprivation for this study.

However, the use of AI chatbots and AI writing assistants, specifically ChatGPT, Google Studio AI, Grammarly, and Gemini, must be acknowledged and disclosed within this section. It was employed in this study as a supportive tool to assist in tasks such as language refinement, sentence expansion, and improving the clarity of technical descriptions. Hence, to ensure that the document adheres to professional-reading standards. The researchers maintain full authorship and accountability for the final content, in accordance with ethical standards that emphasize transparency, integrity, and responsibility in academic research. Each tool or AI chatbot is listed with its specific purpose, activity, or prompt, and the location where its output or application is seen in this document (see APPENDIX I).

Furthermore, to protect user privacy in deployment, the mobile application sensitively requests microphone access only at the moment of recording, which is a must to let the user know that the system utilizes the microphone. The recorded audio is not publicly shared, stored in the cloud servers without proper consent, or used for commercial purposes. All the applicable laws and ethical guidelines, like those found within data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), this research has to be followed to keep ethics high in the research and follow ethical guidelines for research that involves human subjects. To conform to these rules and standards, the study ensures responsible AI development. It thereby responsibly contributes to the health observation field of well-maintained public trust.

3.13 APIs and Development Tools

This section outlines the APIs and development tools utilized in the research. These tools supported various stages of the study, which include documentation, system design, preprocessing and feature extraction of audio data, implementation of a machine learning model, evaluation of the classifier, interfaces/prototype, and development of the mobile application. The list of APIs and development tools used in the implementation of the system is provided in APPENDIX I. Each tool is listed with its specific purpose, activity, or prompt, and the location where its output or application is seen in this document. With the documentation of these tools, transparency is preserved in regard to the technical resources that assisted all the experimental and development stages of the study.

Furthermore, the researchers acknowledge the use of AI chatbots like ChatGPT and Gemini, used as tools, to support several procedures of the research process. These tools were utilized specifically to define technical ideas, create explanations, investigate alternative solutions to problems encountered, and help with the organization and documentation customization. Although the outputs generated from AI chatbots were thoroughly screened and confirmed by the researchers, their use offered tangible advice and facilitation of efficiency during both the build and analytical parts of the research.

Having outlined the methodology, this chapter comprehensively developed and evaluated the SVM model for mild SD detection through voice analysis based on generic auditory features. The methodology began with rigorous data collection and characterization, utilizing the "sleepy voices" dataset from the OSF site, which included both

non-sleep-deprived and sleep-deprived audio recordings from 24 female subjects. Two subjects were discarded due to issues in recording. The dataset was originally sampled from 44.1 kHz, preprocessed by downsampling to 16 kHz, and split into 15-second segments for training the SVM model. The researchers used a “STRF-like model” to extract the features of the segmented audio. This, in turn, is used as the training, validation, and testing sets for the SVM model. The researchers used the GridSearchCV using a stratified five-fold cross-validation. Ethical considerations are regarded to ensure that the privacy of the user is respected by having his/her consent to use the microphone of the smartphone for recording the audio for classification. This is to ensure that users, developers, and everyone involved in the creation of both the model and application have come to an amicable agreement. That is no one in the party has been harmed, and the use of data is thoroughly stated in the data policy. In addition, the use of AI chatbots was also acknowledged and disclosed within the section on ethical considerations. It is also noted that the dataset is ethically considered, as it is public and was used by a previous study [TE2024]. Statistical analyses alongside their formulae are conducted within the research. Specifically, those statistical tools are One-way ANOVA, One-way MANOVA, and t-tests. These statistical tools provided the researchers with the means to tell the differences between the three dimensions of the STM. With differences in terms of classification metrics, the researchers had pinpointed which model, that is trained under a specific dimension, is viable for SD classification. The result of the STM combined features achieved significant results among the frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate in the population level. FR has a train-vs-validation value of 82.41%, closer to the combined features of 85.88%. Therefore, among those statements highlights the sufficient use of the SVM model trained with STM features.

CHAPTER IV

SOLUTION

To address the objectives of this research, the researchers developed a mobile application system that provides their solution for SD detection. This chapter defines the system decomposition, development tools, design framework, and user interface components that significantly enhance the availability and usability of the research findings. The mobile application analyzes the voice input to extract STM and employs a trained model called the SVM classifier to identify sleep-deprived voice. The system ensures convenient interaction and real-time classification of the system. Through this development, the researchers aim to provide ease of use, non-invasive tools that allow the user to interact with the prediction of the system, with the contribution of sleep wellness in alignment with public health goals.

4.1 System Decomposition

The researchers implement the five main functionalities of the system. These are Audio Capture Methods, Voice Recording, Recording Results, Segmented Audio Classification, Feature Analysis, and Settings, which are accessible to the user (see Figure 5). The first functionality primarily concerns the choice of either uploading an audio file or recording their voice in a direct approach. In Voice Recording, the user chooses a speech script, where the system analyzes his/her voice. The Recording Results is where the system flow redirects to results when he/she is finished with the audio recording. Within it, analyses and insights based on the sleep status classification of the user are shown. Feature analysis is

where the user graphically sees his/her sleep status classification after a recording session that is at least 15 seconds. Lastly, the Settings is the functionality where the state and the classification (through toggleable background noise reduction and UI theme) of the system application are modifiable.

Figure 5. System Decomposition Chart.

4.1.1 Audio Capture Methods

The system is able to obtain a voice recording, either through Direct Voice Recording or File Upload (see Figure 8). The main feature is the Direct Voice Recording. Instead of uploading pre-recorded audios into the application, the user is able to record his/her voice within the application for a more direct approach. Since the mobile application primarily relies on using the microphone of a smartphone, audio recordings made from outside the application (like the built-in audio recorder application of the smartphone) are eligible for uploading within the application for the

classification process. As long as the format is in any audio form, such as .wav, .m4a, .mp3, or .aiff, the user is able to import their audio recording and have it classified whether he/she is SD or not. Coherency and speech must be present in the audio recording to guarantee a smooth classification process.

4.1.2 Voice Recording

This functionality is the basis of the system application (see Figure 10). Subfunctions within it include Speech Script Language Selection, Speech Script, and Timer. The language selector is where the user has two options to choose from, such as English or Tagalog. Both languages have their own speech scripts provided, which are then shown in the recording UI. The user is also able to play/resume the recording process at their will. Lastly, a timer functionality is shown in the recording UI to indicate how much time has elapsed since the user started recording.

4.1.3 Overall Analysis

After the recording session is done, the system flow directs to the Overall Analysis (see Figure 12). Within this functionality, the system provides the user with four options, which are Overall SD Classification, Overall Prediction Statistics, Recommendations, and References. The Overall SD Classification functionality provides the overall classification result, which is determined by the majority of predictions across all segmented audio inputs. The Overall Prediction Statistics functionality provides a detailed breakdown of the SVM classifier performance based on the input of the user, which includes probability scores, such as confidence scores for both sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived, average confidence score, and decision score obtained from the classifier. In Overall SD Classification, if the SVM

classifies two out of three segments as sleep-deprived, the overall classification is sleep-deprived. However, if both classes have an equal number of segment predictions, the final classification relies on the Overall Prediction Statistics. For example, “Recording Segment 1” was classified as sleep-deprived with a confidence score of 81.82%, and “Recording Segment 2” was classified as non-sleep-deprived with a confidence score of 67.21%. In this case, since the segment classifications are tied, the system averages the confidence score for each class. The class with the higher average confidence score is then selected, which is “Recording Segment 1” as the overall inference. This ensures that the final result is based on both classification frequency and the confidence of the SVM in its predictions. The Recommendations feature provides personalized advice based on the classification result. Lastly, the References section provides credible sources that serve as support for the recommendations provided by the system.

4.1.4 Segmented Audio Classification

The first functionality within this section is the SD Classification. Within the functionality, a certain number of recording segments alongside their classification results are shown in Figure 13. Prediction Statistics show the distribution of the SD and NSD probabilities with percentages. Audio playback enables the user to analyze their recorded speech, with options for audio playback and review segment-level voice recordings and probability scores for verification or analysis. This is for the user to determine that his/her audio segments are properly classified. Depending on the duration of the audio, for example, if the duration is thirty seconds, the number of segments is two since the system splits the recordings into 15-second segments.

4.1.5 Feature Analysis

If the user wants to see his/her feature analysis, the recording session must be concluded (voice recording must be at least 15 seconds long), and a link pointing to the feature analysis page from the overall analysis is shown, which the user is able to interact with. This is where the user perceives their classification visually in terms of energy distributions. The first interface the user perceives is a description of the STM. Three dimensions are visually represented, which are SR, FS, and FR (see Figure 14). Each feature is displayed in a squeezebox or accordion. All of which includes a brief description to make it easier to understand for the user.

4.1.6 Settings

To make the application more adaptable and user-friendly, a Settings functionality is implemented (see Figure 6). This is to personalize the application based on the user using the application. Specifically, the user is able to toggle the theme of the application between light mode and dark mode, with both options to change the visual theme and color scheme of the interface. Both of the options change the current colors of the application. Most importantly, the user has the option to enable or disable the background noise reduction, which is particularly useful in noisy environments, as background noise affects the classification results significantly. The system employs a “Wiener Filtering” and a “DeepFilterNet3” for background noise reduction. “Wiener Filtering” is a classical signal-processing technique that uses an algorithm to reduce noise based on statistical estimation, while the “DeepFilterNet3” is a deep learning-based approach that learns complex patterns from the voice.

4.2 Technology/Development Tools

This section outlines the technologies and development tools used by the researchers throughout the implementation of the study. Each tool was appropriately determined to ensure production and reproducibility, and flexibility across various phases of development, which starts from the preprocessing and feature extraction to mobile application deployment. These tools improved the structure and design of a user-friendly mobile interface and a reliable backend infrastructure, which not only provides the technical foundation of SVM classifier development and testing.

4.2.1 Python

It is the primary programming language used in this study, which serves as the foundation for preprocessing, feature extraction, training, validating, and testing the SVM classifier for mild SD detection. The researchers specifically utilized the “strf-like-model” tool to obtain and visualize STM features [ET2021]. This tool allowed the raw audio signal to translate into detailed modulation representations, which include frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate, which function as the input features for classification. The use of diverse environments of scientific libraries and personalized feature extraction tools of Python ensures reliable and efficient data processing and classification across experimentation.

4.2.2 Front-end Development

The front-end of the application is responsible for delivering the user interface that allows seamless interaction with the back-end services and the SVM classifier. Figma is used as the interface design tool in order to conceptualize how the mobile interface of the application looks. The researchers utilized React Native as the

framework for building the mobile application, enabling cross-platform development for both Android and iOS with a single codebase. To ensure consistent and modern design, Tailwind CSS is integrated for styling, allowing rapid prototyping and clean, scalable UI components.

4.2.3 Back-end Development

The back-end of the application is responsible for handling the core logic, data processing, and communication between the user interface and the SVM classifier. It provides the necessary APIs and services that allow the mobile application to function reliably and securely. The researchers utilized Flask as the Python web framework for the server, which enables defining API's on how the client interacts with the server to utilize the SVM classifier for mild SD detection.

4.2.4 Version Control

It is a fundamental aspect of software development that ensures the changes to the codebase are tracked, managed, and documented productively. The researchers use Git as the version control system for development, and GitHub as the git hosting service, which provides a centralized platform for developers to collaborate, review code, and manage different versions of the application. The development of the project provides convenience and from a transparency and collaborative development process. This ensures that the development of mobile applications for mild SD detection persists and is constantly improved.

4.2.5 Reproducible Development Environments

It is essential in software development to ensure that applications are built and run consistently across different machines and over time. The researchers use Nix as

the package manager and environment manager to declare dependencies, system libraries, and development tools in a declarative configuration file, such as “flake.nix”. This approach guarantees that every contributor works within the same environment, eliminating dependency conflicts and ensuring consistent results.

4.3 User Interfaces

Only those important interfaces are included in this section. These interfaces are specifically customized for mobile applications but maintain consistency across other platforms through responsive and scalable design. The core interfaces include the settings, splash screen, home page, language speech selection, recording process, and classification results. This section highlights the use cases and important information about each stated interface. Certain general interfaces, like training results, about us, and user guides, are not included in this section. The researchers have created a User Interface (UI) that has various aspects of design, dark/light mode, and accessibility, which makes the usability of the system easy to use and intuitive. A detailed description of each interface is provided in the following sections.

As depicted in Figure 6, the Settings Interface serves as the interface to personalize the application according to user preferences. It allows the user to switch between light and dark themes, adjusting the overall appearance and readability of the interface. Additionally, it provides an option to enable or disable background noise reduction using a “Wiener Filtering”

and “DeepFilterNet3”, enhancing the accuracy of voice classification depending on the environment.

Figure 6. Settings Interface.

As depicted in Figure 7, the splash screen represents the initial point of user interaction. It presents the brand of the application, the logo of SleepSpec, and serves both aesthetic and functional purposes. Visually, it sets the tone and identity of the application through minimal design. Functionally, it assists the background loading of essential assets such as machine learning libraries, audio analysis modules, and language resources. The

loading process typically takes about three to five seconds, after which the user is redirected to the home page. Therefore, this indicates the visual appeal upon opening the application.

Figure 7. Splash Screen Interface.

As seen in Figure 8, the Home Interface allows the user to interact with various functions. The interface includes the selection of speech script languages for reading. In the upper left corner is the question mark symbol, which, when pressed, displays the user manual, how to use the system. As the user interacts with the menu in the upper right corner, settings

and the history of previous system analysis are shown (see Figure 15). The record button is included in the home page, which directs the user to the Audio Recording Interface (See Figure 10).

Figure 8. Home Interface.

As seen in Figure 9, it allows the user to choose between three supported speech script languages, Filipino and English. These sentences are sourced from copyright-free books and remain the same for every session. For the Filipino language, excerpts from *Alamat ng*

Matsing (Pinoy Edition © 2025) and *Noli Me Tangere* by José Rizal are used (see APPENDIX F). For English, excerpts from *The Prince* by Niccolò Machiavelli and *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* by Lewis Carroll are used (see APPENDIX F). Each language option provides a set of predefined speech scripts, with detailed metadata such as the chapter number and corresponding title.

Figure 9. Language Selection Interface.

In this interface (see Figure 10), the user views and reads the speech script based on the selected language, with the option to return and change it. At the upper-right corner of the

interface, a question mark icon provides step-by-step recording instructions for operating the recording session. The speech script display is centered on the screen, which shows the selected passage for the session along with dynamic states such as “PAUSED,” “IDLE,” and “REC.” Below the display is a live timer, formatted in “MM:SS”, which traces the current session duration. Below, a live timer in “MM:SS” format tracks the recording duration. The interface also includes three buttons, which are “Recording,” “Reset,” and “Done.”

Figure 10. Audio Recording Interface.

Figure 11 is a loading interface that takes some amount of time, depending on the length of the recorded audio and the computing power of the server that is doing all the processing before returning the result to the client as an HTTP response. Within the estimated time, there are various processes that involve the pre-processing of the audio, feature extraction, and classification process, and certain metrics are also calculated while in the loading interface. The processing time is optimized through efficient parallelization, where each audio segment is processed concurrently.

Figure 11. Loading Results Interface.

In Figure 12, the interface shows the classification results or analysis from the recording process. Within the interface, the detection logs provide the confidence score and the decision function to determine the distance between the decision boundary. Both texts change color depending on the result of either sleep-deprived or non-sleep-deprived, red or blue, respectively. The “info icon” contains information about the detention logs. Additional information about the analysis is also provided to respond with recommendations and prevention, which are included within the interface. The references in response to the recommendations and advice are also provided.

Figure 12. System Analysis Interface.

In Figure 13, the interface depicts the classification results of each segmented audio of the recorded audio from the user. The user is able to review the sleep deprivation status audio of segments, provided with timestamps and dates for clarification. The system categorizes the segments into “Non-sleep-deprived” and “Sleep-deprived,” which provides insights into the vocal patterns over time. A summary of the classification at the top averages the summation of the overall classification, such as “You are Sleep-deprived,” while the other tabs allow extensive exploration.

Figure 13. Classification Results Interface.

In Figure 14, the interface depicts the feature analysis view of the system, where the user is presented with an overview of how specific vocal features relate to their sleep deprivation status. The section highlights a key acoustic feature, “spectro-temporal modulation,” which is used to interpret rhythmic and dynamic changes in the speech of the user. The visualization showcases how spectral and temporal modulations interact, assisting in identifying patterns often linked to fatigue, such as slower speech or altered modulation rates. This tab enables the user to understand the underlying voice features influencing their classification, which complements the insights from the results and classification sections.

Figure 14. Feature Analysis Interface.

In Figure 15, the Bottom Sheet depicts the navigation interface of the application. Upon tapping the menu icon (in the red circle indicator), the user is presented with the options, which are Home, User Manual, Settings, View Our Website, About the Model, and Us. After a user completes a voice recording, the session is automatically saved to the local storage of the device. This action activates an additional menu item labeled View Previous Test Results, which allows the user to easily access and review their past detections. This feature enhances user experience, which provides a quick and convenient navigation to relevant sections of the application.

Figure 15. Bottom Sheet.

4.4 System Validation

After the development of the application and all its core functionalities was completed, system validation became a required process to ensure its reliability, accuracy, and overall preparation for deployment. This section validates that the SD detection through the voice analysis system performs properly in each task. The validation process was implemented through the combination of unit testing, integration testing, system testing, and acceptance testing to evaluate specific aspects of functionality, compatibility, performance, and user satisfaction. The potential issues were determined and resolved, which ensures that the system operates efficiently, produces consistent results, and meets both technical requirements and user expectations before deployment.

4.4.1 Unit Testing

It is performed on each component, both on the mobile application and the server backend (which includes the SVM model). Edge cases and boundary values where elusive bugs occur are included. This ensures each one of them performs their function correctly as expected. Calculations are verified to have correct outputs for all provided sample inputs. Path parameters correctly reject invalid formats. Query parameters enforced types and ranges work properly as expected. Input sanitizers escape dangerous character sequences that possibly lead to a security flaw. For the preprocessing of segments, each preprocessing procedure correctly rejects invalid values passed to it, such as incorrect sampling rate and segment length. Unit tests are also executed on the SVM model in order to verify that each piece of the process, namely data preprocessing, feature extraction, and model prediction, is working as expected. The tests verify that the input feature vectors conform to expected

dimensions and ranges, that the model correctly throws errors or gives warnings when given invalid or malformed input. Predictions are also verified to match the known sample data. Edge cases like inputs containing extreme values or lacking some features are checked to make sure the SVM model is capable of handling them gracefully without producing incorrect outputs or causing panics and runtime errors.

4.4.2 Integration Testing

It focused on ensuring that all components of the system, starting from audio recording, preprocessing, feature extraction, SVM classification, and user-interface rendering, functioned in a unified operation. The primary objective was to validate the communication operation between the mobile application, the preprocessing pipeline, and the server-side SVM model that handles the classification between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived states. Specifically, the interfaces between the Expo React Native Client and the Backend Server are situated within an Elastic Compute Cloud, or EC2. The goal is to ensure that the mobile application correctly constructs the “FormData” payload and the server correctly parses these requests and returns the expected JavaScript Object Notation or JSON contents. First and foremost, the researchers verified that the audio file and noise reduction preference are correctly forwarded to the backend server. This integration testing is critical to verify that the FormData object is constructed with specific keys required by the upload function within the server. The voice input is processed with the background noise reducer by feature extraction. The processed output is then used as the input for the SVM classifier to predict the SD status. The predicted output is parsed into a Classification object. This object contains the necessary prediction probability percentages and

respective scores. Furthermore, the trained model is tested on the local server with the same voice input to determine consistency. Nonetheless, the results are the same with the EC2 server, with slight variations in processing time. Success criteria showed the server received the request and returned a successful status code or the “HTTP 200” status code in the terminal logs. The response of the server contains a valid JSON object, which the client or the mobile application successfully parses. Likewise, error handling is ensured to gracefully handle backend errors or rejections, specifically for audio files that are shorter than 15 seconds.

4.4.3 System Testing

This testing evaluates the end-to-end flow of the system application. Simulating the complete user journey from the home screen to the results screen. This is to ensure that all components user interface, state management, Application Programming Interface or API, and backend server processing work together as a one cohesive system. This test covers the primary functional requirement of the system, which is SD detection from voice analysis. Pre-conditions are tested, requiring permission to use the microphone of the mobile device and that the server is running. Test steps include the configuration of the background noise reduction method set to “DeepFilterNet” and Wiener Filtering. Once configured, the input recording is tested, which requires navigating to the Audio Recording Interface (see Figure 10). The microphone button is pressed, triggering the audio recorder module. A constraint check is likewise tested for both shorter, longer, and exact 15 seconds, for which the server returns a specific response to handle errors on shorter durations. The “Done” checkmark is pressed to upload the audio to the server. The uploaded audio is

processed, applied the appropriate background noise reducer, runs the SVM classifier, and returns the classification object result. The application redirects to the results screen, where the UI displays the classification results along with respective metrics and references. In terms of UI/UX, the feedback among the users shown in Table 7 indicates “Very Good” criteria in Communication Commonality, Consistency, and Understandability, and Generality.

4.4.4 Acceptance Testing

It focused on ensuring that the SD detection with the use of the SVM through STM features met the expectations and requirements of its target user, including students, faculty, and external evaluators. The acceptance test verified not only the functional performance of the system but also its usability, output clarity, and responsiveness during real-world circumstances. Feedback from the evaluators served as the basis for determining areas for refinement and validation that the system operated and generalized reliably in real-world circumstances.

A total of 54 participants were tested on the application. 30 College of Information Technology students, 20 non-IT students, two university faculty members, one IT Professional, and one visitor from other schools, agencies, or institutions. The personal information of all participants remained confidential. Before participants were conducted with the survey, they interacted with the application through demonstrations or hands-on use. All participant surveys and testing were conducted face-to-face, and the questionnaire was provided through Google Forms.

The questionnaire evaluated 54 criteria related to the application, including accuracy, auditability, communication commonality, completeness, conciseness,

consistency and understandability, controllability, data commonality, decomposability, error tolerance, execution efficiency, expandability, generality, hardware independence, instrumentation, modularity, observability, operability, security, self-documentation, functional simplicity, structural simplicity, code simplicity, software system independence, traceability, and training. Each criterion was calculated using a numerical scale from one to five, where five is the highest score, and one is the lowest score. The mean score was computed, and its description was provided using Table 7.

Mean Score	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Good
3.41 – 4.20	Good
2.61 – 3.40	Average
1.81 – 2.60	Poor
1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor

Table 7. Survey Results Interpretation.

Table 8 depicts the criteria, the mean score, and its interpretation. 54 participants evaluated each criterion and assigned a score based on their responses and experience in the application, based on their observation of its demonstration. The top three and lowest three scores are identified based on the scores provided.

Criteria	Mean Score	Interpretation
Accuracy	4.43	Very Good
Auditability	4.43	Very Good
Communication Commonality	4.44	Very Good
Completeness	4.37	Very Good
Conciseness	4.48	Very Good
Consistency and Understandability	4.46	Very Good
Controllability	4.45	Very Good
Data Commonality	4.50	Very Good
Decomposability	4.47	Very Good
Error Tolerance	4.48	Very Good
Execution Efficiency	4.56	Very Good
Expandability	4.52	Very Good
Generality	4.48	Very Good
Hardware Independence	4.48	Very Good
Instrumentation	4.46	Very Good
Modularity	4.43	Very Good
Observability	4.50	Very Good
Operability	4.46	Very Good
Security	4.56	Very Good
Self-documentation	4.48	Very Good
Functional Simplicity	4.50	Very Good
Structural Simplicity	4.39	Very Good
Code Simplicity	4.48	Very Good
Software System Independence	4.43	Very Good
Traceability	4.48	Very Good
Training	4.56	Very Good

Table 8. Summary of Survey Results.

The top highest criteria scores are training (4.56), security (4.56), and execution efficiency (4.56), all three tied at the highest score of 4.56. Training criteria refer to the degree to which the software assists in enabling a new user to utilize the system. It scored highly because a user found the system intuitive and easy to use, allowing a new user to understand and use the application easily. Security criteria refer to the availability of mechanisms that control or protect programs and data. It also scored the highest because the application does

not store or retain any user data, including audio recordings or classification results. This confidentiality approach grants the user strong confidence that his/her data remains safeguarded. Finally, execution efficiency refers to the runtime performance of the program. It also scored the highest, showing that a user experienced fast processing, smooth navigation, and responsive performance. Even though the system performs the feature extraction and SVM classification within approximately 30 to 60 seconds or more, it still operates efficiently by processing the tasks without problems and providing results without interruptions to the user. Generally, these criteria highlight the outstanding features of the system in usability, privacy, and performance.

On the other hand, the lowest criteria scores are completeness (4.37), structural simplicity (4.39), and accuracy (4.43), which highlight significant areas for improvement in the system. Completeness refers to the degree to which full implementation of the required function has been achieved. It suggests that while the core functionalities are present, some features should be further expanded to completely meet user expectations. Structural simplicity refers to an architecture that is modularized to limit the propagation of faults. It indicates that the architecture of the system should be improved by further modularizing components to reduce complexity, minimize the risk of failure propagation, and enhance maintainability. Finally, accuracy refers to the precision of computations and control. While it remains within the “Very Good” range, it focuses on further enhancing the precision of the SVM classification with additional data, such as the inclusion of male participants in the dataset, improved preprocessing, or even more sophisticated optimization techniques in the SVM hyperparameter. Each of these areas helps to improve the overall reliability and usability of the system over time.

The development of the SD Detection mobile application successfully addressed the objectives of the research, which provides a non-invasive, efficient, and accessible tool for SD detection through voice analysis. With the integration of STM feature extraction and the SVM classifier, the system achieved efficient analysis of vocal input, which offers an intuitive technique for monitoring the sleep conditions of the user. Moreover, the application demonstrates how speech-based SD detection can be effectively translated from theoretical research into a real-world application and user-centered health monitoring solution. The system decomposition consists of customizable settings, audio recording, recording results, and feature analysis, which ensures usability, adaptability, and accuracy in different environments. Through thoughtful design and implementation using modern tools such as Python and other libraries, React Native, Tailwind CSS, Flask, and Nix, the researchers established a reproducible and reliable framework for both machine learning experimentation and application deployment. The user interface was precisely designed to enhance user interaction and experience, which emphasizes accessibility and personalization through adjustable themes and noise reduction options. In addition, the mobile application consists of various interfaces, and these are Settings, Splash Screen, Home, Language Selection Interface, Audio Recording Interface, Loading Results, System Analysis, Classification Results, Feature Analysis, and lastly Menu Interface. All of these interfaces were also used in the system decomposition, which serves as the foundation of the mobile application. The validation process was implemented through the combination of unit testing, integration testing, system testing, and acceptance testing. Overall, the system provides a practical solution that bridges health monitoring and AI, which promotes public health awareness and contributes to technological advancements in non-invasive diagnostic applications.

CHAPTER V

RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides a detailed analysis of the performance of the SVM in the detection of mild SD using generic auditory features derived from voice analysis. The evaluation focuses on the various evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and BAcc. The outcomes are examined in terms of both individual and population-level categorizations, considering how the model differentiates between non-sleep-deprived and sleep-deprived states. The outcome of the one-way MANOVA is also presented to statistically confirm the significance of the classification performance of the model under different conditions. The train+validation vs testing process is examined to verify performance consistency and the ability to generalize. The chapter ends with a discussion of the real-world relevance of the findings and how the system enables non-invasive and accessible sleep health monitoring.

5.1 Evaluation of Model Performance

This section provides a comprehensive evaluation of the performance of SVM in the detection of sleep deprivation in various metrics. The assessment begins by comparing the training and test sets in order to measure the performance of the model on unseen data. The comparison is then used to analyze whether it overfits or underfits, and thus, insights are provided into the level of generalizability of the model. The assessment then continues by

including the combined training and validation set in the test set, thus signifying the stability and strength of the model at different levels of development.

5.1.1 Support Vector Machine Training Results

The training results of the SVM classifier on the STM features, specifically combined features, show consistent performance across five iterations of Grid Search with stratified five-fold cross-validation (see APPENDIX L). The dataset was split into a proportion of 80:10:10, which results in a total of 2,176 for training, 272 for validation, and 272 for testing. The model exhibits stability in the detection of non-sleep-deprived (pre-session) and sleep-deprived (post-session) conditions that utilize generic auditory features.

The performance of each iteration demonstrates that the model generalizes well, as indicated by the highly consistent performance metrics in the training and validation stages and the test stage. The use of optimized hyperparameters ($C=1000$, $\gamma=0.001$) helped in obtaining a balance between bias and variance, thus reducing overfitting without weakening strong classification performance on individual iterations. The following subsections provide a detailed performance analysis based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and balanced accuracy.

5.1.1.1 Model Accuracy

The SVM model achieved an average accuracy of 0.8588, which indicates a reliable and consistent classification performance across five iterations of repeated training and validation using stratified five-fold cross-validation (see APPENDIX L). The gap between the training and test is

0.8588 and 0.7476, respectively, across five iterations, which shows that the model was not overfitting, but rather maintained stable generalization to unseen data. The model obtained accuracy values in pre-session and post-session that were always close to 0.7050 and 0.7924, respectively. These values show that while the classifier performed slightly better in detecting sleep-deprived (post-session) speech compared to non-sleep-deprived (pre-session), both conditions were captured with reasonable reliability. The results are an indication of the model being effective in reflecting vocal variations during various sleep conditions in a well-balanced manner in various test splits.

5.1.1.2 Model Precision

The SVM classifier was both consistent and highly precise during training, validation, and testing iterations, which achieved an average precision of 0.8591 in all classes (see APPENDIX L). Precision measure, for the pre-session test set evaluation, achieved a perfect score of 1.00, consistent in each of the 5 folds. This seemingly perfect performance is attributed to the nature of the subset utilized, where no instances of the ‘post’ class (sleep-deprived) were present. Thus, there were also no false positives predicted for the ‘pre’ class (not sleep-deprived), thus resulting in a high precision measure of 1.0 for that particular class. The same goes for the ‘post’ class (non-sleep-deprived).

5.1.1.3 Model Recall

The SVM classifier achieved a strong performance in the identification of relevant instances, with an average of 0.8588 across the stratified five-fold cross-validation (see APPENDIX L). This indicates that the model showed an equal ability for the detection of both non-sleep-deprived (pre) and sleep-deprived (post) vocal samples. In the pre-session test set, the recall was around 0.7050, whereas in the post-session test set, it increased to 0.7924, which shows a negligible loss of sensitivity while switching from one session to another. These values confirm the stability of the model in detecting true positive cases under varied testing conditions. The slightly lower recall detected during the pre-session reflects the negligible loss in the capability for the detection of sleep-deprived vocal states, which is attributed to intra-subject variability or reduced vocal clarity due to SD. However, recall stability between sessions confirms the generalizability and maintenance of balanced detection performance of the model.

5.1.1.4 Model F1-score

The F1-score metric, which balances both precision and recall, stayed consistent across the stratified five-fold cross-validation, with an average of 0.8588 in all classes (see APPENDIX L). This metric is important in imbalanced datasets, especially in practical situations where both false positives and false negatives carry significant weight. The F1-score of the pre-session test remained at 0.8270, and the post-session score at the average of 0.8842, both demonstrating a high harmonic mean between the precision

and recall. The high F1-scores are a reflection of the perfect precision values (1.0) that were obtained in both sessions, with high recall performance. The outcomes establish the effectiveness and dependability of the performance in every fold of the model.

5.1.1.5 Model Balanced Accuracy

The SVM classifier achieved an average of 0.8590 in all classes of BAcc, which exceeds the baseline balanced accuracy (without cross-validation) of 0.7664 by a margin of approximately 10% (see APPENDIX L). It is important for the datasets with possible class imbalance since it provides equal weight to the recall of both classes. This demonstrates that the SVM model showed improved ability to correctly classify pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) and post-session (sleep-deprived) compared to the baseline model without the hyperparameter tuning.

5.1.2 Model Confusion Matrix

The y-axis represents the true, real-world condition of the individuals in the test set. The top row corresponds to those who were actually in the "Pre" or non-sleep-deprived state, while the bottom row reflects those who were truly in the "Post" or sleep-deprived condition (see Figure 16). On the x-axis, the researchers see the predictions of the model. Individuals predicted as "Pre" fall in the left column, while those predicted as "Post" appear in the right column. Looking at the numbers, the model correctly identified 98 non-sleep-deprived individuals as "Pre" (true positives) and 104 sleep-deprived individuals as "Post" (also true positives). However, it was not perfect. It misclassified 28 non-deprived people as "Post" (false negatives

from the "Pre" perspective, or false positives for "Post") and incorrectly labeled 41 sleep-deprived individuals as "Pre" (false positives for "Pre" or false negatives for "Post").

Overall, the model classifies it correctly for 211 out of 271 samples, which results in an average accuracy of 77.9%. When focusing on non-sleep-deprived individuals, it correctly identified about 79.5% of them, missing 27 cases. For sleep-deprived individuals, its accuracy was slightly lower at 76.3%, with 33 misclassified cases.

Figure 16. Model Confusion Matrix.

5.1.3 AUC-ROC Curve

Figure 17 shows the performance metrics of how well a binary classifier distinguishes between two classes (pre-session vs. post-session). Notably, the feature

dimension combined features (Strf) has the highest Area Under the Curve or AUC of 0.84 (1.0 - 0.16), which is closer to 1.0, indicating a very good separation between classes (see Figure 4 for AUC criteria). The second feature dimension with the high AUC is the frequency-rate, with an AUC of 0.82, which is also within the very good range. The third feature dimension that aligns the value of AUC in SR is the FS, which is satisfactory with an AUC of 0.64. While the scale-rate performs satisfactorily, that lies with an AUC of 0.64. Hence, the dimension, combined feature, or the STRF, is the correct decision to be used in sleep deprivation detection.

Figure 17. Model AUC-ROC Curve.

5.1.4 Model Learning Curve

Figure 18 depicts the feature dimension frequency-rate, or FR, as the dimension with the least margin between the train score and the endpoint of the

dimension. It overfits by around 5%. This indicates that FR had the least overfitting among the other plots. Despite FR having the lowest percentage of overfit, the AUC-ROC curve depicts that it performs slightly lower than the STRF feature (see Figure 17). Table 16 also shows that the FR is significantly worse than STRF with $\sim 9\%$ difference. The two remaining dimensions, scale-rate or SR, and frequency-scale or FS, significantly overfit, indicated by having large gaps between the train score and the cross-validation score. Thus, the STRF dimension is the state-of-the-art choice for sleep deprivation detection.

Figure 18. Model Learning Curve of Four Features.

5.1.5 Model Validation Curve

The validation curves in Figures 19 and 20 for the SVM model analyzing the spectro-temporal modulation (combining frequency, rate, and scale dimensions) reveal important insights into the SVM performance based on hyperparameters C and gamma (γ). The training score remains consistently high (near 1.0) across all values of C , which demonstrates the strong capacity to fit the training data of the SVM, even with minimal regularization (low C). However, this high training performance does not necessarily translate to good generalization, as evidenced by the cross-validation (CV) score. For very low C values, such as 10^{-4} and 10^{-2} , the CV score is relatively poor (~ 0.4 – 0.6), indicating underfitting due to excessive regularization. As C increases, the CV score improves, peaking around $C = 100$ (10^2) before plateauing, suggesting that this moderate regularization strength strikes an optimal balance between bias and variance.

Figure 19. Model Validation Curve (C) in Combined Dimensions.

In contrast, the γ validation curve shows a sharp decline in cross-validation performance as γ increases beyond 10^{-4} and decreases in 10^{-1} , implying that smaller γ values (broader kernel influence) generalize better, whereas larger values lead to overfitting, as evidenced by the high training score but low cross-validation accuracy (see Figure 20). Together, these curves suggest that the SVM model achieves the best balance between bias and variance for spectro-temporal modulation analysis when $C = 100$ and γ is kept relatively small (e.g., 10^{-2} or lower). This combination ensures reliable generalization that uses the essential structure of the STM space, broad kernel interactions to capture global patterns through small γ , and sufficient regularization through moderate C to avoid overfitting.

Figure 20. Model Validation Curve (gamma) in Combined Dimensions.

5.2 Determine the Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and BAcc of SD detection using SVM based on generic auditory features, with a focus on the dimension of STM features.

Table 9 presents the overall performance of different STM feature dimensions at the population level. Among the feature sets, the Combined Features dimension achieved the highest performance metrics, with an accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc all reaching 85.9%. In comparison, the frequency-scale and scale-rate dimensions yielded lower performance, with metrics around 64.0% and 68.2%, respectively. Although the FR dimension achieved a sufficient performance score, that is only about 4% lower than that of the Combined Features. However, this observed difference is not statistically significant. Variability due to random initialization, sample distribution across folds, or inherent data noise contributes to these results.

metrics	Train vs Validation			
	Combined Features	FR	SR	FS
Accuracy	85.88%	82.41%	68.11%	64.99%
Precision	85.90%	82.44%	68.31%	64.03%
Recall	85.88%	82.41%	68.11%	63.99%
F1 score	85.88%	82.41%	68.09%	63.99%
BAcc	85.90%	82.43%	68.20%	64.00%

Table 9. Overall Performance of STM Features at the Population Level.

The MANOVA shown in Tables 10 and 11 was performed using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and BAcc as dependent variables, with feature dimension, such as combined (all features), FS, FR, and SR as the independent grouping factor. Before analysis, the

researchers ensured that the sample size ($N = 5$ per group) exceeded the number of dependent variables ($p = 2$ for initial MANOVA), satisfying the minimum requirement for MANOVA validity. The Wilk's Lambda test statistic ($\Lambda = 0.0036$) indicated strong evidence of group differences, as values near zero suggest greater divergence between dimensions. The associated p-value (< 0.0001) confirmed statistical significance, meaning that at least two feature dimensions led to meaningfully different classifier performance when considering all metrics collectively. Since the MANOVA was significant, the researchers conducted separate one-way ANOVAs for each performance metric. All ANOVAs yielded p-values < 0.0001 , confirming that feature choice significantly impacted every metric. The researchers applied Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test to identify specific differences between dimensions, which adjusts for multiple comparisons.

5.2.1 One-Way MANOVA for the Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and BAcc.

Table 10 presents the results of the One-way MANOVA for the accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and BAcc metrics of the SVM classifier in SD detection. To assess how different feature dimensions affect the model performance, MANOVA was conducted based on balanced accuracy and F1-score as combined dependent variables. The analysis was feasible because the smallest group size (5) exceeded the number of dependent variables (2). The Wilk's Lambda test statistic came out to 0.0036. A value this close to zero suggests substantial differences between at least some of the dimensions. With a p-value of effectively 0.000, the result was highly significant, meaning that performance (when considering both metrics together) was not equal across all dimensions. Since the MANOVA flagged overall differences, the tests followed up with separate ANOVAs for each metric. Both balanced accuracy and

F1-score showed extremely significant differences ($p \approx 0.000$) across dimensions, confirming that not all feature sets performed equally. Given these findings, the researchers used Tukey's HSD test to pinpoint exactly which dimensions differed. The combined dimensions, while statistically better than FR, did significantly surpass FS. Meanwhile, FS itself was notably better than FR. In short, the ranking from greatest to lowest was combined > FS > FR > SR, though the gap between combined and FR was not large enough to be statistically significant ($p\text{-adj} \approx 0.2250$). Thus, out of the 6 comparisons, only one does not reject the null hypothesis. There is no significant difference between accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and balanced accuracy of the SVM classifier in SD detection. Hence, only one feature has no significant difference, which is FR and combined.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	reject
FR	FS	0.0494	0.000	TRUE
FR	SR	-0.1464	0.000	TRUE
FR	combined	-0.0098	0.2250	FALSE
FS	SR	-0.1957	0.000	TRUE
FS	combined	-0.0592	0.000	TRUE
SR	combined	0.1365	0.000	TRUE

Table 10. Post-Hoc Tukey's HSD of BAcc in All Classes.

In Table 11, the pattern also correlates with the previous table, Table 10. This meant that the statistical tool used to reject the null hypothesis regarding hypothesis number one is consistent. Table 11 only has one false, which does not reject the null hypothesis because there is no significant difference between the two (FR and

Combined). To summarize, the MANOVA and subsequent post-hoc analysis revealed that most feature combinations led to significantly different classifier performance, with FR and combined being the only feature sets that did not significantly differ from the combined set. Thus, out of the six pairwise comparisons, only one did not reject the null hypothesis, indicating that FR and Combined yielded statistically indistinguishable results in terms of F1-score and BAcc.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	reject
FR	FS	0.0410	0.000	TRUE
FR	SR	-0.1409	0.000	TRUE
FR	combined	-0.0350	0.2250	FALSE
FS	SR	-0.1957	0.000	TRUE
FS	combined	-0.0592	0.000	TRUE
SR	combined	0.1365	0.000	TRUE

Table 11. Post-Hoc Tukey's HSD of F1-score in All Classes.

5.3 Determine the differences in the performance and STM representation of the SVM classification results across the pre-session and post-session.

The performance of the classifier was evaluated across train + validation and test sets for both pre-session (non-sleep-deprived) and post-session (sleep-deprived) conditions, with key metrics including BAcc, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The negligible performance gap between pre- and post-session classifications (<0.3% difference in accuracy/recall) suggests the model generalizes equally well for both states. The perfect precision implies that while the model missed some true cases (recall 85.90%), its predictions

are highly reliable when it does classify a sample. Table 12 shows the performance difference between pre- and post-session classifications. While modest, it was consistent across all folds. This pattern is reflected through either inherent differences in how sleep deprivation manifests in the auditory features [TE2024].

metrics	Train vs Validation		
	Combined	pre	post
Accuracy	85.88%	70.50%	79.55%
Precision	85.90%	100.00%	100.00%
Recall	85.88%	70.50%	79.55%
F1 score	85.88%	82.70%	88.42%
BAcc	85.90%	70.50%	79.55%

Table 12. Overall Performance on Pre, Post, and Combined.

For the pre-session results (see Table 13), the model achieved an accuracy of 70.50% and a balanced accuracy of 70.50%, demonstrating consistent performance in classifying non-sleep-deprived states. Precision reached 100.0%, indicating that all predictions labeled as pre-session were correct (no false positives). This is because the model has no information inside a post set. Thus, it identifies the participants as non-sleep-deprived.

fold	BAcc (pre)	accuracy (pre)	precision (pre)	recall (pre)	f1 score (pre)
1	70.50%	70.50%	100.00%	70.50%	82.70%
2	70.50%	70.50%	100.00%	70.50%	82.70%
3	70.50%	70.50%	100.00%	70.50%	82.70%
4	70.50%	70.50%	100.00%	70.50%	82.70%
5	70.50%	70.50%	100.00%	70.50%	82.70%
avg.	70.50%	70.50%	100.00%	70.50%	82.70%

Table 13. Performance Metrics on Pre-Session.

The post-session results (see Table 14) showed slightly lower, with an average balanced accuracy of 79.24%. Similar to the pre-session results, precision remained perfect at 100% across all folds, demonstrating that post-session predictions were never false positives. The recall of 79.24% indicates the model successfully identified nearly 80% of sleep-deprived cases on average, with an F1-score of 88.42% showing a good balance between precision and recall for the sleep-deprived condition.

fold	BAcc (post)	accuracy (post)	precision (post)	recall (post)	f1 score (post)
1	79.55%	79.55%	100.0%	79.55%	88.61%
2	79.55%	79.55%	100.0%	79.55%	88.61%
3	78.79%	78.579%	100.0%	78.79%	88.14%
4	78.79%	78.79%	100.0%	78.79%	88.14%
5	79.55%	79.55%	100.0%	79.55%	88.61%
avg.	79.24%	79.24%	100.0%	79.24%	88.42%

Table 14. Performance Metrics on Post-Session.

This section demonstrates the results and analysis of STM features extracted from all 22 subjects across different sessions, such as pre-session and post-session. The STM representation is a three-dimensional representation that has a dimension of speech energy distributed over modulation scales (spectral), modulation rates (temporal), and frequency components. The color mapping in the plots indicates a significant aspect in the interpretation of STM, such as the “white” representing the neutral or no change, which indicates that either baseline energy in pre/post averages in Figures 21 and 22, respectively, or zero difference (in the subtraction plot in Figure 22). The “blue” indicates a negative value, which is a weaker

energy/modulation or lower values relative to sleep deprivation. Lastly, the “red” indicates positive values, which result in a stronger energy/modulation or higher values relative to sleep deprivation[TE2024].

The average STM representation for non-sleep-deprived 22 subjects (see Figure 21) highlights the baseline spectro-temporal features of speech. The frequency-rate feature reflects the absolute spectral distribution of vocal recordings, with energy concentrated in regions associated with speech modulation, such as syllabic rhythms and formant structures. The scale-rate feature further emphasizes the temporal dynamics of speech, showing consistent modulation patterns that align with natural prosodic features such as pitch and rhythm.

Figure 21. Average of STM in All Subjects in Pre-Session.

The post-session STM (see Figure 22) shows a similar structure to the pre-session, which suggests that fundamental speech modulation patterns persist even under SD. However, subtle changes in energy distribution, particularly in the frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate, indicate a potential decline in vocal control. These slight subtle changes suggested

that while STM remains impaired, the dense coordination of speech features is compromised due to the cognitive and physiological factors of SD.

Figure 22. Average of STM in All Subjects in Post-Session.

The difference plot (see Figure 23) indicates the SD impact in the subtraction of pre-session STM from post-session STM. This provides a persuasive visualization of how SD subtly changes in vocal modulation. In the representation of the difference between pre-session and post-session STM, the “red” indicates an increased neural response in post-session, the “blue” indicates a decreased neural response in post-session, and “white” indicates no changes.

Figure 23. The Difference of STM in All Subjects in Pre and Post Sessions.

To further investigate whether SD had a statistically significant effect on the STM feature representations, a One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to compare the pre-session and post-session average values for frequency-scale, frequency-rate, and scale-rate. The analysis aimed to determine if there were significant shifts in feature distributions due to sleep deprivation. As shown in Table 15, the p-values for all three STM feature types were greater than the 0.05 threshold, which indicates that none of the differences observed between pre- and post-sessions were statistically significant. Specifically, frequency-scale had a t-statistic of 0.1148 with a p-value of 0.7348, frequency-rate showed a t-statistic of 0.2714 with a p-value of 0.6024, and scale-rate exhibited a t-statistic of 0.0857 with a p-value of 0.7699. In terms of average percentage difference, frequency-scale showed a slight increase of 1.85%, followed by frequency-rate at 1.72%, and scale-rate at 1.46%. These small differences suggest minimal variation between the pre- and post-sessions in the averaged STM features, which implies that sleep deprivation does not substantially alter the global statistical structure of these representations across subjects.

Feature	t-stat	p-value	Avg. of diff. (%)
Frequency-Scale	0.1148	0.7348 > 0.05	1.85%
Frequency-Rate	0.2714	0.6024 > 0.05	1.72%
Scale-Rate	0.0857	0.7699 > 0.05	1.46%

Table 15. One-Way ANOVA of STM Feature Averages Across Pre- and Post-Sessions.

5.4 Determine the BAcc of the SVM classification results based on population and individual levels.

The SVM classifier achieved a mean BAcc of 85.90% across five folds when using the Combined STM feature dimensions (see Table 16). This reflects strong classification performance at the population level. The BAcc scores across folds for the combined features were highly consistent, ranging across 85.89% to 85.93%, indicating stable generalization and minimal variance between training-validation splits. This indicates that the model reliably distinguishes between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived states when evaluated on unseen population data. For comparison, the FR dimension achieved an average BAcc of 82.43%, with fold-level results ranging from 82.28% to 82.59%, also demonstrating consistent and relatively high performance. The SR dimension showed a stable yet lower performance with a consistent BAcc of 68.20% across all folds. In contrast, the FS dimension achieved the lowest and most consistent BAcc, fixed at 64.00% across all five folds.

Fold	Train vs Validation			
	Combined Dimensions	FR	SR	FS
1	85.93%	82.31%	68.20%	64.00%
2	85.89%	82.50%	68.20%	64.00%
3	85.89%	82.28%	68.20%	64.00%
4	85.89%	82.45%	68.20%	64.00%
5	85.89%	82.59%	68.20%	64.00%
Avg.	85.90%	82.43%	68.20%	64.00%

Table 16. BAcc Across Five Folds of STM Features in the Population Level.

The individual-level performance across 22 participants (see APPENDIX G) is observed with both higher average performance (83%) and greater variability compared to population results. The BAcc scores ranged from 68.75% to a perfect ~83%, with most participants clustering around the average. This distribution reveals that while some sleep-deprived states of the individuals are detected with near-perfect accuracy, others present greater classification challenges. The average performance at the individual level compared to population results suggests that personalized approaches yield even better detection rates. The performance variation across individuals likely stems from physiological differences in how sleep deprivation manifests in auditory features. High performers (90-100% BAcc) exhibited more pronounced and consistent changes when sleep-deprived, while lower performers (below 75%) showed subtler or more variable patterns.

5.4.1 Hypothesis Testing

In this section, the researchers conduct hypothesis testing to assess the statistical significance of the difference in BAcc between population-level and individual-level classification results in the use of STM features. The focus is on the combined dimensions (all features), frequency-scale, frequency-rate, and scale-rate. Welch's t-test was applied due to unequal variances and sample sizes between the two groups. A p-value less than 0.05 was used to determine statistical significance. A t-statistic was used to determine how many standard deviations the difference between the two sample means is from zero (the null hypothesis assumption of no difference). This statistical approach provides a reliable basis for model performance comparison across different feature representations.

5.4.1.1 Combined Dimensions

The t-test for the combined dimensions results in a t-statistic of -1.6012 and a p-value of 0.1241 (see Table 17). Since the p-value exceeds the threshold of 0.05, this indicates that there is no significant difference in classification performance between the population-level and individual-level models using the combined STM features. While there appears to be some variability, it is not sufficient to confirm a consistent performance difference across the two levels of generalization.

Feature	t-stat	p-value
Combined Dimensions	1.6012	0.1241 > 0.05

Table 17. Combined Dimensions T-test.

5.4.1.2 Frequency-Scale

The Welch's t-test produced a t-statistic of 5.3328 and a p-value of 0.0000 (see Table 18). This p-value is precise below the 0.05 significance level, which indicates a significant difference in BAcc between population-level and individual-level classification using the FS feature. This result suggests that FS contributes differently across general and individual models, possibly due to variation in how individuals modulate frequency-related characteristics in speech.

Feature	t-stat	p-value
Frequency-Scale	-5.3328	0.0000 < 0.05

Table 18. Frequency-Scale T-test.

5.4.1.3 Frequency-Rate

The Welch's t-test for the frequency-rate feature returned a t-statistic of -3.8300 and a p-value of -0.0010, far exceeding the 0.05 threshold (see Table 19). This indicates a significant difference in BAcc performance between the two levels. It suggests that FR features generalize well and are less influenced by individual-specific speech patterns.

Feature	t-stat	p-value
Frequency-Rate	-3.8300	-0.0010 < 0.05

Table 19. Frequency-Rate T-test.

5.4.1.4 Scale-Rate

Lastly, the t-test for the scale-rate feature resulted in a t-statistic of 3.5753 and a p-value of 0.0018 (see Table 20). This result indicates a significant difference in performance and suggests that SR features behave differently across individual and population levels. The variability of SR characteristics among individual results for these performance differences.

Feature	t-stat	p-value
Scale-Rate	3.5753	0.0018 < 0.05

Table 20. Scale-Rate T-test.

5.5 Statistical Experimentation Results

In this section, the researchers present the justification and experimental evidence based on the raw prediction results obtained during system testing. The experimentation involved classification experiments with segmented audio inputs provided to the SVM model. For each segment, the model generated predicted classes post (sleep-deprived) or pre (non-sleep-deprived), decision scores, and probability estimates for both classifications. Metadata such as audio filename, subject demographics (age, gender, nationality), speech script, background noise removal state, and voice tone were recorded to investigate each experiment. These results were systematically recorded and arranged into tabular form for statistical representation (see APPENDIX H).

To evaluate the reliability and performance of the model in different segment levels, Segmentation Test Results were performed, in which recordings of approximately two minutes were divided into multiple segment lengths of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 60 seconds. Each segment was classified individually, which allows evaluation of how segment duration affects performance and computational efficiency. The elapsed time of classification was measured to test the flexibility of the model in practical contexts. The results included key metrics such as predicted class per segment, decision score, probability scores for both classes

(sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived), confidence scores, and aggregate averages through all segments (see APPENDIX J).

Table 21 reveals what appropriate segment lengths are used in the system application. The “Segment Length” column tells how much audio the SVM model needs to perceive before making an accurate decision. The table is focused on the average probability of every n-length segment (sd_proba) and the time it takes to predict the probability (elapsed_time) on mildly SD tests. To better understand the table, at five seconds, the model is already certain (95.42%). Though this is because of the number of segments leading to a greater number of percentages to average, less data for the SVM model to make use of. At ten seconds, the confidence jumps significantly to 98.53%. From fifteen seconds onwards, the confidence is practically maxed out, hovering between 98.7% and 99.7%.

Mildly Sleep-Deprived Voice Test		
Segment Length	sd_proba (%)	elapsed_time (s)
5s	95.42	99.04
10s	98.53	94.19
15s	98.76	78.44
20s	98.85	59.51
25s	99.21	39.81
30s	98.89	39.20
60s	99.78	19.71

Table 21. Mildly Sleep-Deprived Voice Test Results Across Varying Segment Lengths.

Table 22 indicates consistent results in the 15 segments, as shown in the previous table. The table is emphasized in NSD tests. At the five-second segment, the probability is at

76.02%, far less than the SD tests. Therefore, the researchers discarded the use of this segment length as it has a lower probability of results and longer elapsed times. Related to 10-second segments, the probability increases substantially, but still not at the optimal point, as with the 15-second segment. Past the 15-second segment, the probability improves insignificantly, with the 60-second segment dropping between 3 and 4 percent. This table also concludes as to why the 15-second segment is chosen for the system application due to the consistency across the probability and “elapsed_time.” Table 22 highlights and further solidifies the correlation between SD and NSD tests.

Non-Sleep-Deprived Voice Test		
Segment Length	nsd_proba (%)	elapsed_time (s)
5s	76.02	101.07
10s	86.33	93.77
15s	91.42	78.36
20s	91.61	58.84
25s	92.78	48.86
30s	90.87	39.06
60s	88.32	19.52

Table 22. Non-Sleep-Deprived Voice Test Results Across Varying Segment Lengths.

Table 23 depicts the Pearson correlation statistical analysis between the SVM predicted sleep-deprived probability and the corresponding computation time across two categories, which are mildly sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived voice samples. For the mildly sleep-deprived, the correlation coefficient is $r = -0.7359$, which indicates a strong negative relationship, where higher confidence scores are more likely to be associated with

shorter computation times. However, the p-value of 0.0594 exceeds the 0.05 significance threshold, which means the strong negative trend is not statistically significant. While the non-sleep-deprived samples show a moderate negative correlation, with $r = -0.5984$. Related to the mildly sleep-deprived groups, a higher confidence score generally aligns with shorter computation times. Although the p-value of 0.1558 also exceeds 0.05, which shows that this moderate relationship is not statistically significant.

SD Category	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Mildly Sleep-Deprived	-0.7359	0.0594 > 0.05	Strong Negative
Non-Sleep-Deprived	-0.5984	0.1558 > 0.05	Moderate Negative

Table 23. Pearson Correlation Summary.

This statistical experimentation represents the capability of the SVM to generalize across practical contexts that perform both segment-level and aggregate statistical data. By testing both segment-level and aggregate statistics, the study shows that the SVM classifier does not rely only on its consistency but also on its ability to generalize throughout different practical contexts. The inclusion of different segment lengths provides a validation that even shorter frames, such as 5-10 seconds, achieve high accuracy of detection. This evidence provides systematic experimentation of justification for the reliability of the system and serves as the supporting evidence for the metrics. Moreover, the observed correlation trends further suggest that computational efficiency is not adversely affected by higher prediction confidence.

The results presented in this chapter provide strong empirical support for the use of SVM classifiers in SD detection from voice-based, generic auditory features, particularly those derived from STM representations. Across a stratified five-fold cross-validation, the model exhibited high and consistent performance across all key metrics, accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and balanced accuracy, which highlights generalizability in distinguishing between non-sleep-deprived and sleep-deprived vocal states. Statistical tools are used to determine the differences among the dimensions of STM. Statistical analysis using one-way MANOVA confirmed that different STM feature dimensions significantly influence model performance, with the SR dimension emerging as the most effective. This finding supports the importance of feature selection in optimizing a classification model. Further evaluation of the SVM behavior under pre-session and post-session conditions revealed a slight but consistent performance dip in the detection of post-session (sleep-deprived) samples. Nevertheless, the perfect precision scores in both sessions and high recall values indicate that the SVM classifications are highly reliable. At the population level, the average balanced accuracy exceeded 85.90%, reflecting excellent generalization across unseen data. Meanwhile, individual-level results showed strong performance across diverse participants, with an average balanced accuracy of 83.00%. These findings affirm that the system performs reliably both in broad group settings and in personalized contexts. Within this section, explains which n segment length to be used (5s, 10s, 15s, 20s, 25s, 30s, 60s). Tables 21 and 22 highlight the consistency between SD and NSD voice tests, with 15-second segments being the optimal. The reason is the consistency of the values of the probability and elapsed time across the two tables. Although Table 22 highlights the decline of the probability percentage (88.32%), which is not consistent with Table 21 of 99.78%.

CHAPTER VI

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter provides a comprehensive summary of the research findings, which offer detailed insights into the effectiveness of the SD detection model using SVM based on STM features. The conclusion of the study addresses the research problems by evaluating model performance through various metrics, which include accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc. Additionally, it presents the results of statistical analyses comparing pre- and post-sleep deprivation sessions, and highlights both individual and population-level performance. Furthermore, this chapter offers key recommendations to guide future improvements, which suggest methodologies for model optimization, generalization, and practical deployment in cognitive state monitoring systems.

6.1 Conclusion

This section presents the final interpretation of the results obtained from the SVM classification experiments. It highlights the SVM performance in the detection of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived states using STM features, evaluates the model across multiple sessions, and analyzes its capability to generalize both at the population and individual levels. The insights gained from these evaluations confirm the viability of using STM for SD detection. Overall, the findings demonstrate that voice-based STM features, which utilize the SVM, provide a reliable, non-invasive approach in mild sleep deprivation detection in practical contexts.

6.1.1 Overall Model Performance

The SVM model trained on STM features derived from vocal recordings exhibited sufficient performance in the classification of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived conditions. It achieved highly consistent performance across five iterations, with consistent patterns during cross-validation. The overall performance metrics of the model achieved an average of 0.8588 and 0.7486 in training and testing, respectively. The model demonstrated strong generalization capabilities, as indicated by consistently high values in both pre-session and post-session test results. These findings confirm that SVM, when combined with STM-based auditory features, serves as an effective classifier for SD detection. The performance is further reinforced by low variance across five iterations, which validates the reliability of SVM in unseen scenarios.

6.1.2 Determine the accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and BAcc of SD detection using SVM based on generic auditory features, with a focus on the dimension of STM representation.

The model achieved an overall accuracy of 0.8588. The Precision and Recall achieved an average value of 0.8591 and 0.8588, which reflects the effectiveness of the SVM in the detection of positive predictions and all actual positive cases, respectively. The F1-score remained consistent at 0.8588, which confirms a balanced trade-off between precision and recall. Importantly, the BAcc reached 0.8590, which balances the baseline BAcc of 0.7664. These results indicate the strong discriminative

power of STM-derived features and confirm the suitability of SVM for this task, particularly to capture subtle vocal shifts due to cognitive fatigue.

6.1.3 Determine the performance metrics and statistical analysis of the SVM classification results based on the pre-session and post-session.

Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference in overall classification accuracy between the pre-session and post-session results. Despite minor variations, such as a slight decline in post-session recall, the global metrics remained stable, which indicates consistent model performance before and after sleep deprivation. The high and consistent precision across both sessions suggests that the model avoided false positives effectively. Meanwhile, the slightly lower recall in the post-test indicates a conservative classification approach. The overall results confirm that SVM generalizes well across different cognitive states induced by sleep conditions.

6.1.4 Determine the BAcc of the SVM classification results based on population and individual levels.

On a population level, the model achieved an overall BAcc of 0.8590, while individual-level analysis also achieved 0.8300, which indicates that the SVM model adapts well to inter-subject variability. The performance remained consistent even when applied to individuals not included in the training fold, which suggests good generalization across participants. However, slight variations in individual accuracy hint at possible influences from personal vocal characteristics or environmental recording differences. These findings suggest that while the model performs strongly at a general level, personalized fine-tuning further improves classification accuracy.

6.2 Recommendation

This section provides actionable recommendations to enhance future research and the practical implementation of sleep deprivation detection systems based on vocal analysis. It emphasizes improvements in feature extraction, model evaluation, and real-world deployment strategies to support wider applicability. The researchers, panel members, and evaluators have suggested and recommended several areas for improvement to achieve the goals of the system.

6.2.1 Gender Limitation and Demographic Diversity

The current study was conducted using a dataset that consists of female participants only, which limits the generalizability of the SVM model to other genders. Research has shown that male and female voices differ in fundamental frequency (F0), Formant Frequencies, and harmonic spacing, but various factors are common in voice characteristics. To enhance the generalizability and reliability of the SVM in the detection of SD, future research must include male participants and a massive demographic background, such as diverse dialects, age groups, and linguistic backgrounds. The reliability and robustness of the model are enhanced by addressing the gender and demographic diversity across various populations.

6.2.2 Fine-Tuning and Regularization

To further enhance the performance of the SVM model, future research must focus on model optimization and validation. This aspect contains hyperparameter tuning, such as kernel selection and regularization parameters of C and gamma, to avoid overfitting and improve model robustness. Cross-validation techniques,

including stratified k-fold validation, and search grid or random search strategies, are established to significantly determine the optimal configuration of the model. Furthermore, exploring advanced optimization techniques such as Bayesian optimization and incorporating feature selection or dimensionality reduction methods may further improve classification stability, reduce computational cost, and enhance the generalization ability of the SVM model across diverse voice conditions.

6.2.3 Deployment for Real-Time Monitoring

To extend the impact of this research, the deployment of the trained model into a mobile or embedded system is recommended. This allows for real-time voice monitoring applications, such as fatigue detection in educational or occupational environments. The use of lightweight deployment frameworks like TensorFlow Lite or ONNX facilitates on-device inference and offline functionality.

6.2.4 Development of a Progressive Web Interface

To maximize accessibility and user engagement, the development of a Progressive Web Application (PWA) is recommended. This platform enables the user to record voice samples, receive immediate classification results, and track historical detection data. A web-based interface also allows smooth integration with mobile and desktop devices, supports data visualization to monitor sleep patterns, and provides a user-friendly experience in various fields, including healthcare, transportation, and education. Additionally, the PWA architecture facilitates scalability to enable future integration of analytics. Therefore, the implementation of a PWA ensures broad accessibility without requiring dedicated application installation.

GLOSSARY

A. ACOUSTIC FEATURES

Any acoustic property of a speech sound that is recorded and analyzed, as its fundamental frequency or formant structure [EM2020].

B. AMPLITUDE

The height from the centerline of the wave to its peak (or trough). It is frequently employed for measuring the energy or intensity of waves. For periodic functions, the amplitude is to be calculated as half the vertical distance between the highest and lowest points of the wave [FM2024].

C. AUDITORY SPECTROGRAM

A visual representation of a frequency spectrum audio signal over time. It is a useful way to understand the components of a sound, breaking it down into its frequencies [PD2024].

D. BIOMETRICS

The measurement and statistical analysis of biological data, both scientifically and technologically. The term "biometrics" in information technology typically refers to automated systems that use human body features like fingerprints, eye retinas and irises, voice patterns, facial patterns, and hand measurements to authenticate and verify information [RM2021].

E. DEMOGRAPHICS

Population statistics, particularly those that display averages for age, wealth, education, and other factors [ND2014].

F. ELECTROCARDIOGRAM

Often known as an EKG or ECG, an electrocardiogram is a line graph that displays variations in the electrical activity of the heart over time. It is produced by a device known as an electrocardiograph. Abnormal conditions such as clogged arteries, changes in electrolytes (particles with electrical charges), and modifications in the way electrical currents flow through the heart tissue are all to be seen on the graph [MS2022].

G. ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAM

It is a biometric method for recording the electrical activity of the brain produced by synchronous discharges in the cerebral cortex acquired via electrodes on the scalp. It is essential to analyze seizures, to categorize different kinds of seizures, and to evaluate neurological states like coma, since their waveforms represent different brain states, which include awake, sleep, or abnormal conditions [RA2022].

H. FEATURE EXTRACTION

A process in machine learning and data analysis involves identifying and extracting relevant features from raw data. These features are later used to create a more informative dataset, which is to be further utilized for various tasks such as classification, prediction, and clustering [ZR2020].

I. FORMANT FREQUENCIES

The peaks in a spectral envelope of the speech signal, which indicate regions of high energy, are known as formant frequencies. Vowels are uniquely identified by the first two formants, which are numbered successively as F1, F2, F3, etc. A particular combination of F1 and F2 values characterizes each vowel [DL2020].

J. GENERIC AUDITORY FEATURES

Fundamental characteristics or attributes of sound that are commonly used to describe, analyze, or classify auditory signals. These features are often extracted from audio data and are applicable across a wide range of applications, such as speech, music analysis, and environmental sound classification [GC2010].

K. HARMONIC-TO-NOISE RATIO

The balance between the harmonic (periodic) and noise (non-periodic) components of a speech signal is measured by the harmonic-to-noise ratio (HNR), which is a gauge of voice quality. A louder or breathier voice is suggested by a lower HNR, whereas a higher HNR denotes a clearer, more periodic voice. It is frequently employed in diagnostics for voice pathologies and evaluations of vocal health [FJ2018].

L. HYPERPLANE

The decision boundary that separates the two classes in a Support Vector Machine is called a hyperplane. Different classes are identified by a data point that falls on either side of

the hyperplane. The number of input characteristics in the dataset determines the dimension of the hyperplane [DS2013].

M. INDIVIDUAL-LEVEL

This refers to the evaluation of the performance of a classification model for each participant in the dataset individually, which reveals subject-specific accuracy. The examination of the BAcc at this level highlights the variability in how well the model detects the target condition for different individuals.

N. JITTER

Small variations of pitch correlate with glottal activity with irregular vibrations during phonation. The interval between successive pitch periods is the measure of jitter. It thus finds use in the detection of voice pathologies and speaker recognition. Individual habits such as smoking, loudness, and gender influence jitter levels [TJ2013].

O. KERNEL FUNCTION

To efficiently identify the dot product in higher dimensions, the kernel function is utilized to convert n -dimensional input to m -dimensional data, where m is significantly greater than n . A linear classifier or regression curve in higher dimensions turns into a non-linear classifier or regression curve in lower dimensions. This is the fundamental notion of using a kernel [DX2021].

P. LEAVE ONE SUBJECT OUT

Also known as LOSO, is a cross-validation method used in machine learning to validate models when dealing with datasets that include multiple subjects, such as medical or psychological data [BR2023].

Q. LINEAR FREQUENCY CEPSTRAL COEFFICIENT

It is a speech-processing feature derived from the linear frequency scale to capture the spectral properties of a signal [ZX2011].

R. MEL FREQUENCY CEPSTRAL COEFFICIENTS

Fundamental characteristics or attributes of sound that are commonly used to describe, analyze, or classify auditory signals. These features are often extracted from audio data and are applicable across a wide range of applications, such as speech recognition, music analysis, and environmental sound classification [RA2024].

S. MILD SLEEP DEPRIVATION

It refers to an individual who experiences an insignificant but consistent reduction in nightly sleep, which occurs 1-6 hours per night of sleep for one or more nights, rather than the recommended 7-9 hours. While cognitive functions still operate at a minimum level, subtle loss in attention, reaction time, and emotional regulation occur [SI2020].

T. NOISE CANCELLING TOOLS

Technologies that reduce or eliminate unwanted sounds. They eliminate or reduce unwanted background noise by generating sound waves that cancel out ambient input [BB2023].

U. NONCOMMUNICABLE DISEASES

They are the category of illnesses that are not primarily brought on by an acute infection, have long-term effects on health, and frequently necessitate ongoing care and treatment. These ailments include diabetes, heart disease, cancer, and long-term lung diseases [UN2023].

V. PARTIAL SLEEP DEPRIVATION

A comprehensive term that includes mild to moderate reductions in sleep time across one or more nights. It involves insufficient sleep rather than severe loss, usually resulting in less than the required duration for optimal function but not total [SI2020].

W. PITCH

The Fundamental Frequency (F_0), expressed in Hertz (Hz), is the average frequency of vocal fold vibrations during voiced speech. Depending on age, gender, and vocal fold length, it is a physical characteristic associated with pitch perception that typically varies from 80 to 450 Hz. F_0 naturally varies throughout the speech to express questions or emphasis [LW2022].

X. POPULATION-LEVEL

This refers to the evaluation of the performance of a classification model on the entire dataset, which assesses its ability to generalize and reliably classify across a group of individuals. The mean BAcc across cross-validation folds represents this group-level performance, which indicates the suitability for broad applications of the model.

Y. POWER SPECTRUM

It represents how much of the energy, or "power," is contained at different frequencies in a signal, be it sound or a waveform, in order to analyze the frequency content of a signal and show which of the frequencies are most dominant [FF2016].

Z. PRE-SESSION

A phase occurs before the main session, during which the subject is in a well-rested state and has not experienced sleep deprivation [TE2024].

AA. POST-SESSION

The phase follows the main session and typically occurs after the subject has undergone sleep deprivation [TE2024].

BB. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

It is a statistical method that reduces the dimensions of a dataset by transforming it into a smaller set of variables called principal components (PCs) [GJ2022].

CC. PROSODY

Patterns of intonation, stress, and rhythm in written or spoken language. Subsequently, it is also used to characterize the expressive aspects of speech, such as pitch, length, and loudness, that communicate meaning beyond words, as well as the metrical structure of poetry in literature and linguistics [DH2022].

DD. PSYCHOMOTOR VIGILANCE TEST

It is a behavioral alertness test that uses prolonged attention demands, is sensitive to sleep deprivation, sleep disease, and working at an adverse circadian phase, and is free of aptitude and learning effects [RT2013].

EE. RADIAL BASIS FUNCTION KERNEL

One of the most popular kernel functions is the RBF kernel, sometimes referred to as the Gaussian kernel. It works by calculating the Euclidean distance in the input space between data points to determine how similar they are [DX2021].

FF. SEVERE SLEEP DEPRIVATION

It occurs when an individual is continuously awake for 24 hours or more without any sleep. This condition significantly damages brain function, which causes microsleeps, hallucinations, poor decision-making, and severe cognitive lapses [SD2025].

GG. SHIMMER

Changes in the amplitude of a voice signal minutely due to irregular vocal fold vibrations are defined as shimmer. It is a measure of the difference in loudness between the successive pitch periods and is generally involved in the diagnosis of voice disorders or the analysis of the characteristics of the speaker. Shimmer levels are affected by alcohol, voice intensity, and gender [DX2021].

HH. SLEEP DEPRIVATION

A condition that occurs when a person does not get enough sleep, which is a critical biological need comparable to eating or breathing. It is associated with adverse effects on physical and mental health, productivity, and safety, contributing to conditions like heart disease, depression, and increased risk of accidents [SS2024].

II. SPECTRAL FEATURES

Describes the frequency characteristics of a signal, such as its centroid, bandwidth, and skewness, which help analyze sound for tasks like speech recognition. These features are typically extracted using the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and are essential for understanding the tonal qualities of the signal [BD2010].

JJ. SPECTRO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS

A method that displays signals in both the frequency and time domains simultaneously [AR2019].

KK. SPECTRO-TEMPORAL MODULATION

It refers to changes in both the frequency (spectral) and time (temporal) aspects of a sound signal. It is used in speech processing to capture dynamic variations that help in tasks like speech recognition and speaker identification [ET2009].

LL. SPEECH ENERGY

The power of sound waves in speech is measured by speech energy, also known as intensity, which listeners interpret as loudness. In disciplines like linguistics and speech therapy, precise measurement of speech intensity is essential for evaluating and analyzing vocal performance. Based on research by Oxenham et. al., intensity is an easy-to-understand metric that is used to explain the relative significance of different speech segments inside a sentence [OA2017].

MM. SPEECH FEATURES

A distinctive characteristic of a linguistic unit that serves to distinguish it from other units of the same kind [LM2020].

NN. SPEECH PROCESSING

It refers to the study of speech signals and processing methods. Since speech signals are frequently handled in a digital representation, speech processing is viewed as a particular application of digital signal processing [AP2016].

OO. SPEECH RHYTHM

The recurrent patterns in spoken language that are impacted by syllable structure, stress patterns, and pause lengths are referred to as speech rhythms. It gives a feeling of flow and differs throughout languages. It is frequently defined as the change between stressed and unstressed syllables. Although exact regularities in speech rhythm are rarely seen in practice, languages are sometimes categorized into rhythmic groups, such as syllable-timed, mora-timed, or stress-timed [FR2024].

PP. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL 3

It focuses on important goals that improve the general health of the population in order to minimize unnecessary suffering from avoidable diseases and early mortality. Priority areas are those with the highest illness burden and underserved populations, and geographical locations. Deeper investments in research and development, health funding, and health risk mitigation and management are also aimed at SDG Goal 3 [UN2023].

QQ. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE

It is a supervised learning model used for classification and regression tasks, designed to find the optimal hyperplane that separates data points into different classes with the maximum margin. These are handled with linear and non-linear data using kernel functions, which map inputs into higher-dimensional spaces for better separability [PD2020].

RR. UNWEIGHTED AVERAGE RECALL

It is a metric used to evaluate multiclass classification models, especially in situations where the class distribution is imbalanced. It indicates the performance of a conducted classification experiment over its mean average Recall of one speaker, afterward averaging the UARs per speaker over all speakers [GM2024].

SS. VOCAL BIOMARKER

Signatures, features, or a combination of features from the audio signal of the voice that are linked to a clinical outcome. These are used for drug development, disease diagnosis, patient observation, or grading the severity or stages of an illness [FG2021].

TT. VOICE QUALITY

The characteristics of a voice that distinguish it beyond pitch and loudness are shaped by the vibratory patterns of the vocal folds and resonance in the vocal tract. Common voice quality types include modal voice (normal speaking voice), breathy voice, creaky voice (low-pitched and irregular vibrations), whispery voice, and falsetto (high-pitched, airy sound) [WR2019].

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

This section provides a detailed discussion of the requirements and expenses involved in the current study. It covers the necessary software, hardware, and human resources needed to implement the project effectively. The software requirements include tools for data collection, analysis, and machine learning, such as Librosa, Numpy, Scikit-learn, and Pickle, which are used to process voice recordings and build models for SD detection. Hardware requirements involved computers with sufficient processing power for model training and testing, along with audio recording devices for gathering voice samples. The discussion also addresses any additional costs, such as licenses for software (if applicable), server costs for storing data, and other incidental expenses like data acquisition and storage for the research.

A. Hardware Recommendation

Utilization of a stationary device like a desktop with sufficient specifications for training the stated model is better, as the fans cool it down better than a laptop fan. However, during the research process, the currently available device that is capable of training the model is the TUF Dash F15 2021, which is decent enough for machine learning capabilities. The use of reliable internet is also a must for team members to collaborate efficiently. Lastly, a decent amount of storage space for storing necessary files and data from experimentation. The recommended requirements are as follows:

- CPU: 8 threads or above with a clock speed of 3GHz or higher
- RAM: 16GB RAM or above
- Storage: 50 GB or higher

- GPU: RTX 2050 or higher, and for laptops, RTX 2060 laptop or higher

B. Software Recommendation

The software libraries recommended to use in this project are a spectro-temporal receptive field (STRF) to extract audio features from recordings, Librosa, Matplotlib for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations of the STM, Numpy for optimal numerical computations and data processing, and SciPy for a scientific computation library that uses NumPy underneath. Scikit-learn to implement the machine learning model that classifies whether it is a case of sleep deprivation, and Pickle, which saves and loads extracted features. All these tools work coherently to analyze the voice and possibly deploy a model that has an effect on the sleep deprivation detection. The software programs and libraries to be used:

- STRF
- Librosa
- Matplotlib
- Numpy
- SciPy
- Scikit-learn
- Pickle

C. Projectware Recommendation

The purpose of this research is to create a mobile development framework that eases the development process and facilitates a customized user interface while still providing core functionalities like recording voices, uploading audio files, and logging activity. This means flexibility and scalability, and even easier implementation to place all such features with absolute assurance.

1. Researchers

The researchers of the study are responsible for developing the application itself using appropriate tools. Since the researchers developed it, they are capable of modifying the UI and the system functionality. They also have the ability to analyze the results from the experiments.

2. User

The user has three use cases which are record their voice via the app, upload an audio recording, and see the previous test results. Both recording-related use cases require the system to request permission for microphone access to ensure data privacy and proper functionality. Both use cases that use audio recording have the software ask permission to access the microphone.

D. System Budget

The allocated system budget is approximately PHP 20,000. It is arbitrarily allocated as the costs of both hardware and software components vary in the future. The summary of the system budget is shown in APPENDIX E. Approximate calculations for components are:

- External storage (HDD): PHP 1,000

- Microphone (for testing and recording): PHP 1,000
- Development tools/licenses: PHP 10,000
- Laptop cooling fans: PHP 2,000
- Miscellaneous expenses (internet, subscriptions, backups): PHP 6,000

The stated expenses for some components are mostly based on online stores such as Shopee to at least have a general idea of the costs for components. Other components, such as development tools/ licenses, are based on their respective websites. Tools like BrowserStack for testing services cost about PHP 1,500–4,000/month. A laptop cooling fan is used in training on the TUF Dash F15 (2021) laptop to prevent the internals and possibly damage to the laptop. As for the testing of the developed system, the smartphones of the researchers are utilized.

E. Time Management

The initial period totals four weeks and marks an important time in laying out the framework for the entire project. This phase, besides the concept paper where a research question is defined by an outlining of the central idea behind the project, the reasons behind its importance, and how it is undertaken, also includes developing the schedule in detail with appendices and as used to complete any activity involved in this project as illustrated in Appendices C and D. Problem statement analysis is also conducted during this period, where a project team properly examines the problem that it aims to address, hence giving clear and focused directions for the subsequent phases. After the research comes initial planning that takes eight weeks. It is at this stage that the workflow of the project is organized, goal setting

occurs, and what resources are needed are outlined. In this stage, a clear project plan is formulated, timelines are set, and evaluated risks are also given emphasis. In addition, during this stage, a proper definition of roles and responsibilities within the team is set forth to ensure that every bit of the project is covered. Requirement gathering takes one week. This period is where the team consults the professors of the university and other people who are part of the study for all technical, functional, and user requirements needed for the project. This stage is quite important to capture all expectations and needs to be taken into consideration before development.

Information gathering and comprehensive research follow over four weeks. This is more advanced because it gets the team raw data to help fine-tune the project design, learn challenges that are present, and ensure all components of the project are founded on the most reliable evidence and good practice. Research also entails reviews of other existing solutions or similar systems for an opportunity to innovate or create better ones.

The design validation typically occurs for four weeks. In this stage, the feasibility of the system, application, or solution design is reviewed against defined requirements. This is the longest and most labor-intensive stage, which runs for approximately fourteen weeks. Here is where the project is finally created. The development team influences the designs, incorporates all features that are necessary, and tests in cycles to ensure everything functions as it is intended to. Coding is incorporated along with debugging and putting together a few system components to make it functional and presentable. However, three weeks are allotted for the documentation phase. It is a place where the whole process of the work is documented: methodologies, design decisions, and challenges.

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USERS' MANUAL

1. Overview

The Users' Manual provides a comprehensive instruction for installation, configuration, and operation of the mobile application. This manual guides the user through each component of the system, from recording voice samples to interpreting classification results and visualizing feature analysis. It also includes essential setup procedures, system requirements, and troubleshooting tips to ensure smooth operation and accurate detection results.

2. Initialization and Setup

The system is able to be initialized either through direct online access or local host configuration. Online setup ensures that the latest updates and patches are automatically installed, providing the user with optimal performance and security. For researchers who wish to configure and run the system locally, the provided installation package allows localized deployment and customization.

Initialization Steps (Internet):

- A. Visit <https://sleepspec.site> using any web browser.
- B. Click “Download APK” or “Download for Android” to download the SleepSpec application.
- C. Install the downloaded APK on your mobile device.
- D. Grant all necessary permissions, particularly microphone access.
- E. You are able to start recording and wait for the analysis results to appear.

Initialization Steps (Local Host - Linux):

- A. All the resources are provided inside the flash drive storage.
- B. Plug the flash drive into the PC
- C. Extract both “Source code (app).zip” and “Source code (server).zip.”
- D. Download and install the Nix package manager through:
<https://nixos.org/download/> (choose multi-user installation)
- E. The following steps will be done using a Linux shell, such as bash.
- F. Create/edit the file: /etc/nix/nix.conf and add this line to the config:
- G. extra-experimental-features = nix-command flakes
- H. Run the command: ‘nix profile install nixpkgs#devenv’ to install devenv, which is required for the mobile app setup.
- I. Go into the directory of the extracted source code of the server.
- J. Run “nix develop”. This will bootstrap all the necessary dependencies.
- K. The server is now able to be started by running: “flask --app server run --host=0.0.0.0”
- L. Note the output of the command; you will see what host and port the server listens to. You will need those details in the next steps for the local environment to function properly.
- M. Next, go into the directory of the extracted source code of the app.
- N. Run “devenv shell”. Wait for it to finish setting up the environment.
- O. Edit the .env file and provide the correct host and port of the server.
- P. Finally, run “npx expo run:android --variant debug.”
- Q. You can also use the “release” variant instead of “debug”.

3. Home Interface

The interface shown after the splash screen is the Home Interface. Within the interface are five interactable buttons, which are shown in Screenshot 1. Home. These enable you, as the user, to navigate efficiently to the main functionalities of the application: to see the manual within the application (1), to navigate to different User Interfaces or UIs (2), language selection (3), recording process (4), to upload a pre-recorded audio (5), and to modify the application theme and background-noise reduction method (6). Those functionalities shown upon made the navigation easier for you by labelling the buttons with their simple, easy-to-understand icons.

Screenshot 1. Home.

- A. Users' Manual – When pressed, it navigates to the “Users' Manual” (see Screenshot 2). This enables for comprehensive reading of the functionalities of the application.
- B. Menu Bar – Expands a bottom sheet which contains navigation links to: Home, User Manual, Settings, website page (through “Visit our Website”), About the Model, and About Us (see Screenshot 8). The menu bar persists across the interfaces when quick navigation is required across different interfaces.
- C. Record Button – When pressed, it navigates to the “Recording” (see Screenshot 2).
- D. Speech Script Language Selection – Navigates to “Speech Script Language” (see Screenshot 3). Selection of two languages with various speech scripts from an open source website, Project Gutenberg, are shown.
- E. Upload Audio – When pressed, you are redirected to your file manager. In your file manager, you are expected to choose any file audio format, whether it be “.wav”, “.mp3”, or “.m4a.” Selecting any other file format is impossible, as those will be greyed out and unpressable.
- F. Settings – When pressed, you will be directed to the “Settings” interface shown in Screenshot 7. Within this interface, you are able to modify the look of the application (light or dark mode theme) to prevent eye strain in dark or light areas. Two background noise reduction settings are capable of being changed (see Screenshot 7 for further details).

4. Recording Interface

This interface serves as the main way to classify your voice. Through the use of a speech script, which is based on the language you have selected, you are guided to what speech to read. This is to make the recording process easier for you, as you do not need to think about what words or statements to say upon recording. Within this interface, you are also able to choose the type of background noise reduction (off or DeepFilterNet3).

Screenshot 2. Recording.

- A. Back Button – When clicked, it navigates back to the previous interface.
- B. Need Help? – This button opens the “Recording Guide” modal to guide the user in the functionality of the recording.
- C. BG Noise Reduction – When pressed, it navigates to the “Settings” interface, where the user selects his/her preferred Background Noise Reduction method.
- D. Speech Script Language Button – Directs you to the selection of various languages.
- E. Recording Button – Serves as the control for starting, pausing, and stopping the recording. It updates visually based on the current recording state.
- F. Reset Button – This erases the current audio recording.
- G. Done Button – If you are satisfied with your current recording, you are able to see your classification results by pressing this button.

5. Speech Script Language Selection

Within this interface, four distinct selections under two languages: Filipino and Tagalog, for you to choose from. These change the speech script shown in Screenshot 2. The selections cannot affect the classification process. Those selections are for your reading preferences only, as some selections are harder or easier to read for some users. Note that the selection only changes the speech script language and book, not the whole language of the application. This changes the language preference of the speech script (see Screenshot 2). This design ensures consistency in system behavior while still accommodating user comfort and readability. As a result, as a user, you can focus on clear speech delivery without concern for unintended impacts on model performance.

Screenshot 3. Speech Script Language.

- A. Speech Script Language – Pressing one selection automatically deselects the other selection. Therefore, pick one based on your reading style and preferences.
- B. Select Button – Redirects you back to the previous interface, and the application is expected to use your selected speech script language.

6. Overall Analysis

After pressing the Done Button in Screenshot 2, Recording Interface. You are then redirected to your overall analysis. Within this interface, you are shown an overall analysis of the classification by the model, which includes sleep-deprived, non-sleep-deprived, average confidence, and decision score. It also includes a source reference that is associated with the recommendations based on the SD classification.

Screenshot 4. Overall Analysis.

- A. Prediction Statistics Information – When clicked, this opens a modal for the information about percentages and scores for: Sleep-deprived, Non-Sleep-Deprived, Average Confidence Score, and Decision scores.
- B. Recommendation Reference – Provides appropriate, well-trusted sources alongside their website links.
- C. Classification Tab – Directs you to the Classification interface (see Screenshot 5)
- D. Feature Analysis Tab – Directs you to the Feature Analysis interface (see Screenshot 6)

7. Classification

After the classification process, the user is able to review their recorded audio by accessing the Classification tab. This interface displays all generated recording segments, which can be individually played or paused for closer inspection. This functionality allows the user to better understand how different portions of their speech contribute to the overall classification outcome. Each segment is labeled and classified by the model based on the 15-second segmentation of the original recording. For example, a 48-second recording will produce three 15-second segments, while the remaining three seconds are discarded. Along with segment-level results and scores, the interface also presents the overall sleep deprivation classification for the entire classification at the top of the screen. This summary view provides a clear and concise interpretation of the user's sleep condition based on aggregated model predictions, where every segment is able to be played upon the user pressing the play button (1).

Screenshot 5. Recording Segment Classification.

A. Playback Button – Enables you to analyze your recording. You are also able to pause it.

8. Feature Analysis

Within this interface, you can dynamically see your visual representation based on your current classification results. Dynamically, the visual graph changes based on your tone, sleep status (sleep-deprived or non-sleep-deprived), and current vocal characteristics before recording. Three visual representations are displayed in collapsible (accordion) sections for easy navigation.

Screenshot 6. Feature Analysis.

- A. Scale-Rate Representation Accordion – Displays your average scale-rate visual analysis and the description.
- B. Frequency-Rate Representation Accordion – Displays your average frequency-rate visual analysis and the description.
- C. Frequency-Scale Representation Accordion – Displays your average frequency-scale visual analysis and the description.

9. Settings

This interface changes the way the application looks and the method for background noise reduction. The purpose of changing the look or theme of the application is to prevent low contrast and maintain good contrast and visibility, whether you are in a bright or dark environment. In addition, if you are in a noisy environment, toggling a background noise reduction method provides a clearer audio output for the classification process.

Screenshot 7. Light and Dark Mode Theme Settings.

A. Dark Mode Toggle Button – Switches the interface to dark mode.

- B. Wiener Filtering Information – Displays details about the Wiener filtering method.
- C. Wiener Filtering Toggle Button – Enables or disables Wiener filtering.
- D. DeepFilterNet3 Information – Displays details about the DeepFilterNet3 method.
- E. DeepFilterNet3 Toggle Button – Enables or disables DeepFilterNet3.
- F. Light Theme Radio Button – Activates the light theme.
- G. Dark Theme Radio Button – Activates the dark theme.
- H. System Theme Radio Button – Matches the current theme of the system.

10. Bottom Sheet

This is shown upon pressing the menu bar shown in Screenshot 1, the second button. This can be accessed anywhere, not just in the Home Interface. Within the sheet, six buttons are available for quick navigation, which include Home, User Manual, Settings, View Previous Test Results, Visit our Website, View the Model, and About Us. To conceal the bottom sheet, simply tap outside the sheet or drag down the drawer. The menu is designed to provide intuitive navigation across the application. Each button is clearly labeled to reduce user confusion and improve accessibility. The “View Previous Test Results” option allows you to view your recent test results with the audio playback still intact for you to play/resume your audio segments at your own leisure. Access to the User Manual supports helps in understanding the application features. The “View the Model” option promotes transparency by allowing you to explore the underlying system. Overall, the menu enhances usability by centralizing essential functions in a single, easily accessible interface.

Screenshot 8. Bottom Sheet.

- A. Drawer – Drag down to conceal the bottom sheet. Tapping outside also hides the whole bottom sheet.
- B. Home Tab – Redirects to the Home interface (see Screenshot 1)
- C. User Manual Tab – Shows the manual on how the application will be used by you, as the user. Within it, it reveals the only important guides for the user to start using the application.

- D. Settings Tab – When clicked, it navigates to the Settings interface shown in Screenshot 7.
- E. View Previous Test Results Tab – If the user has previously classified their sleep deprivation status, they are able to view their results again at any time. Note that the application only stores the latest classification results.
- F. Visit Our Website Tab – Redirects the user to the official website of the SleepSpec application.
- G. About the Model Tab – Shows the performance of the model in percentages. Within it are brief descriptions for every metric of the model.
- H. About Us Tab – Shows information regarding the developers and researchers of the application and thesis, respectively.

This User's Manual contains all critical information needed to run the system efficiently, from initialization to analyzing sleep deprivation classification results. It serves as a step-by-step guide that bridges technical system functions with user-friendly instructions. By following the stated methods and interface recommendations, the user is guaranteed accurate voice recordings, proper configuration of system settings, and effective use of the analytical features of the application. Additionally, this manual gives the user the knowledge needed to handle typical problems, making the entire experience dependable and simple. It outlines best practices to ensure reliable interpretation of the application functionalities. All things considered, this book is a comprehensive resource to assist the user in making the most of the ability of the system to detect mild sleep deprivation using voice analysis.

APPENDIX A

Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship.
(Adopted from Philippines Association of Institutions for Research (PAIR), Inc.)

WE, the researcher, and research adviser/consultant, have worked together in a thesis project from August 2024 to January 2026.

WE have used various forms of contact during the thesis work such as Microsoft Teams, Facebook and other means of communication.

WE agree that :

- The academic partnership leads to publication of the manuscript with the research consultant as the author and the researcher, the primary author.
- the paper be presented in a public forum by the researcher if available at such an opportunity or by the research adviser/consultant if the researcher is no longer around.
- only the name of the oral presenter shall be submitted to the Conference organizer.

WE agree to dress formally and prepare adequately for the formal oral presentation in both the oral defense panel and the public presentations.

Signed this 21st of December in the year of our Lord 2026 in Bacolod City, Philippines.

GIAN FRANS D. ARANETA
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CHRISTIAN L. DE LA TORRE
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ERIK A. AGABON
Witness

RAFAEL JACOV C. MEDEL
Researcher

APPENDIX B

Concept Paper.

Research Concept Title	Machine Learning-Based Voice Analysis Software for Detecting Sleep Deprivation		
Concept Author and Collaborator(s)	Araneta, Gian Frans D. Main Author	De la Torre, Christian L. Collaborator #1	Medel, Rafael Jacov C. Collaborator #2
Rationale of the Research Concept			
<p>This concept simplifies the use of sleep monitoring tools by implementing a mobile software and a desktop software that determines if the individual is sleep deprived or not based on voice analyses or acoustic analyses (from reading sentences) using classification models of machine learning. In this way people can monitor their sleeping habits in the comfort of their homes or anywhere just by reading a few sentences without the use of intrusive tools such as electroencephalogram (EEG) and electrocardiogram (ECG). The “ease of use” is considered in this concept because some busy people may not be able to continue to habitually monitor their sleep with other applications that require full nights of sleep to gather insights. Stated below are the other purposes of this research concept:</p> <p>Early Prevention of Chronic Sleep Deprivation: This concept paper aims to detect constant or chronic sleep deprivation after an acoustic analysis and intervention to drive individuals to take actions before sleep deprivation becomes harder to manage by giving software insights in relation to the problem. Chronic sleep deprivation can lead to detrimental health complications over time; hence, it is best to prevent sleep deprivation early.</p> <p>Enhancing Overall Well-Being and Sleep Quality: Improving the quality of sleep is one of the critical factors for health maintenance. This idea looks to enhance the total well-being of users by providing them a software tool to monitor and track their sleep via the acoustic analyses.</p> <p>Reducing Cognitive Decline Associated with Poor Sleep: Constant sleep deprivation can negatively affect cognitive functions such as critical thinking, focus, memory, and making decisions. Hence, this concept paper actively engages individuals to monitor their sleep quality using the software tool by making it easier to interact and possibly minimize cognitive decline by making the individual aware that they are sleep-deprived.</p> <p>Early warning system: A system that could detect these changes in real-time might be useful in preventing accidents or errors caused by excessive sleepiness.</p>			

The reason as to why facial recognition is not included here because that is another scope. There are many factors that affect the way people look and not just sleep such as depression, eating habits, aging, and dehydration.

Main Features and Functionalities

Spectrogram-Based Voice Analysis: voice features such as the individual's average pitch, pitch variation, voice jitters, and voice breathiness will be used to determine if the individual is sleep-deprived or not.

Long-Term Sleep Deprivation Pattern Recognition: Algorithms regarding time-series analysis such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks will be used to determine the possibility of the individual to sleep deprivation ahead of a point in time.

Ease of Use: The software will be designed to be user-friendly, requiring only a simple voice recording to assess sleep quality. Users can interact with the tool without needing specialized equipment or complex procedures. The ease of use ensures that even those who are busy or unfamiliar with health monitoring technologies can easily incorporate the tool into their daily routine.

Voice Recording History: Stores previous voice samples for users to track their sleep quality over time and observe changes or improvements.

Non-Intrusive Monitoring: The software's functionality includes non-intrusive monitoring, which means users can check their sleep quality without the need for cumbersome devices. Traditional methods such as EEG or ECG, which require extensive setup and are often uncomfortable, this software only requires a voice recording. This approach makes it more accessible and convenient for users to monitor their sleep regularly and effortlessly.

Model(s) to Use

The models listed may or may not be used depending on their suitability and the available knowledge. Here are the potential models that could be employed within this project:

- Classification models to differentiate between sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived states based on voice features.
- Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to analyze spatial hierarchies in data, such as spectrograms of voice signals.
- Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) effective for analyzing voice recordings over time, capturing changes in voice patterns related to sleep deprivation.
- Spectro-Temporal Modulations (STMs) and Modulation Power Spectrum (MPS) ; these are speech extraction tools.
- Time-series algorithms: Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks
- The model requires training datasets of labeled voice samples of sleep-deprived and non-sleep-deprived.

Dataset Source

English Speech and Language Samples

This type of data provides diverse speech samples that can improve the accuracy of sleep-deprived voice and non-sleep-deprived voice classification. However, the scope of the sample is not mainly sleep-deprivation based but based on neutral sound, sleepy sound, and other sounds based on certain emotions which are not relevant in this topic. The data is accessible through OpenSLR: <https://openslr.org/115/>.

Another same type of dataset can be accessed through a Mega folder: <https://mega.nz/folder/KBp32apT#gLIgyWf9iQ-yqnWFUFuUHg>

some other sources:

<https://sleepresearchsociety.org/career-advancement/public-datasets/>

Main dataset source:

<https://osf.io/qujkd/overview> (sleepy voices)

<https://osf.io/xbtr4> (recently acquired)

<https://osf.io/9zqep> (output in zip format from dataSMTF)

Creating our own datasets with sleep-deprived-voice and non-deprived-voice as the main labels by gathering participants who are willing to have their voices recorded based on the two labels and have a decent microphone would be time consuming but feasible. This approach does mean that the data should be tailored for the purposes of the study, although it does require a great deal of careful planning into the selection of participant pool and maintain consistency in recording conditions.

Project Usability / Benefit Justification

Integration with Health and Wellness Platforms: integrating this software into leading health applications, such as Fitbit or Apple Health could enable them to not only identify sleep patterns with the support of voice but also to observe related data, for example, on physical activity and nutrition, in one place. For example, when this software finds sleep problems based on voice patterns, it might integrate with such platforms and provide actionable insights-suggesting changes in daily habits or offering personalized tips for sleeping better.

Expansion to Multilingual Languages: Adding voice analysis capabilities in languages like Spanish, Mandarin, or Arabic would enable such a tool to be accessible to users from many international backgrounds. Such adaptation should therefore need software modifications to accommodate a variety of accents and speech patterns, assuring effectiveness with different linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Relevance to the Theme

Goal 3: Good Health and Well-Being: The concept paper aims at ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being at all ages. It provides a preventive approach in that the software given should be user-friendly in the identification of sleep deprivation through acoustic analysis from reading a few sample sentences toward helping to deal or early prevention of

chronic sleep deprivation, thereby improving the health outcomes and reducing further risk of other health conditions that are associated with sleep deprivation.

Technology Deployment

Platforms:

- Android
- Windows: this OS is industry standard; hence it would be better to deploy the software here which detects like lets say an employee's voice through a fixed time assuring that the employee's health is considered (FORGOT TO ADD)

Software Needs:

- Spectro-Temporal Modulations (STMs) and Modulation Power Spectrum (MPS)
- Google Colab provides a free version with limited access to GPU and TPU resources as well as using time for running machine learning models.
- Scikit-learn for implementing traditional machine learning algorithms, including classification models to determine sleep deprivation from voice features.
- Security and Privacy Tools tools that include data encryption, data masking, secure authentication, and compliance with privacy regulations to protect user data and ensure privacy.
- TensorFlow for building and training complex neural networks to analyze large volumes of voice data for detecting sleep deprivation.
- Voice Analysis Algorithms to process and analyze voice data to detect patterns of sleep deprivation using models like Spectro-Temporal Modulations (STMs) and Modulation Power Spectrum (MPS).

Hardware Needs:

- Cloud Servers for securely storing user information and deploying machine learning predictions with scalable resources.
- High-Performance Computer for training machine learning models, it must have capable processing power and 16-32 GB minimum RAM.
- Same model microphone for testing purposes
- Smartphones' built-in microphones will be used to capture voice samples needed for acoustic analyses of sleep deprivation.
- Physical Storage Devices for backing up and securely storing voice data and model results to prevent data loss.

Anticipated Challenges

One significant challenge is the limited access to datasets of sleep-deprived voices. These datasets are essential for training and validating the models, and without sufficient data, the accuracy of the voice analysis could be limited. The process of data collecting would be a problem because some datasets are locked behind a paywall while others require access permissions which might take time to respond. Another challenge is ensuring the accuracy of the voice analysis despite variations in individual speech patterns, background noise, and recording quality. Additionally, in the Project Usability / Benefit Justification section, integrating the tool with existing health and wellness platforms may create difficulties in integrating the voice analysis because those platforms are already established. Finally,

maintaining user engagement and compliance is a challenge, as users must consistently interact with the tool and provide accurate voice samples for effective monitoring.

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APPENDIX C

PERT Table.

CODE	ACTIVIES	Predecessors	OT	MT	PT	ET	ES	EF	LS	LF	SLACK TIME
A	System Planning and Requirements Gathering	NONE	7	8	9	8	0	8	0	8	0
B	Identify Project Requirements	A	1	1	1	1	8	9	8	9	0
C	Project Functionalities	B	1	1	1	1	9	10	9	10	0
D	Data Gathering	C	4	5	6	5	10	15	10	15	0
E	Research	C	2	3	4	3	10	13	12	15	2
F	Interface Design	D,E	4	5	6	5	15	20	15	20	0
G	Designing Prototype	D,E,F	4	5	6	4	20	25	20	25	0
H	Coding	F,G	9	10	11	11	24	35	23	35	0
I	Training and Testing	F,G,H	4	5	6	5	35	40	35	40	0
J	Documentation	I	4	5	6	5	40	45	40	45	0

APPENDIX D

PERT Diagram.

APPENDIX E

System Budget and Cost.

Components	Brief Description/Model	Costs
External storage (HDD)	1 Terabyte	~ ₱ 1,000.00
Microphone (for testing and recording)	Awi MK1 (5)	~ ₱ 1,000.00
Laptop Cooling Fans	llano V13 laptop cooler	~ ₱ 2,000.00
AWS On-Demand EC2 Instance	c6g.2xlarge: 8 vCPU, 16GB RAM	~ ₱ 3,098.11 over two weeks
Domain Name	GoDaddy Domain 1 year duration (sleepspec.site)	₱ 77.00
	GoDaddy Domain 1 year duration (sleepspec.cloud)	₱ 209.53
Google Play Console	One-time charge for Google Play Console registration fee	₱ 1,516.91
TUF Dash F15 (2021)	FX516: 4 Cores 8 Threads, 16 GB RAM, 1 TB	₱ 49,995.00
Lenovo IdeaPad 3	Ideapad 3 Slim 3 14ITL6: 4 Cores 8 Threads, 16 GB RAM, 512 GB	₱ 39,999.00
Huawei Matebook B3 Series	B3-410: 4 Cores 8 Threads, 8 GB RAM, 512 GB	₱ 29,999.00
Miscellaneous expenses	Internet, subscriptions, backups	~ PHP 6,000.00
Total Costs:		~ PHP 132,738.14

APPENDIX F

Speech Script Excerpts.

Noli Me Tangere (José Rizal), Chapter 16 *Si Sisa*, Filipino Language Script.

Bata pa si Sisa, at noon pa lang ay makikita nang siya'y maganda at kaakit-akit kumilos. Ang kanyang mga mata—na parang ang kanyang kaluluwang handa niyang ibigay lahat para sa kanyang mga anak—ay napakaganda. Mahahaba ang kanyang pilikmata at malalim kung tumingin. Maganda ang hubog ng kanyang ilong, at ang kanyang mapupulang labi ay maayos ang anyo. Siya ang tinatawag ng mga Tagalog na "kayumangging kaligatan"—isang kayumangging kulay na malinis at kaaya-aya.

Bagamat bata pa siya, dala marahil ng kalungkutan o gutom, unti-unti nang namumutla ang kanyang mga pisngi. Ang kanyang makapal na buhok, na dati'y alaga at nagpapaganda sa kanyang anyo, ay inayos hindi para maging kaakit-akit kundi dahil ugali na niyang maging maayos. Ang kanyang buhok ay simpleng sinuklay, walang palamuti tulad ng alampay o palamuti sa buhok.

Ilang araw na siyang hindi lumalabas ng bahay dahil tinatapos niya ang isang trabahong iniutos sa kanya, na kailangang matapos agad sa abot ng kanyang makakaya. Sa kagustuhan niyang magkaroon ng kaunting pera, hindi siya nagsimba nang umagang iyon dahil aabutin siya ng halos dalawang oras sa paglalakad papunta at pabalik sa bayan. —Talagang ang kahirapan ay nakakapilit gumawa ng kasalanan.

Nang matapos ang kanyang gawa, agad niya itong dinala sa may-ari. Pero pinangakuan lang siya ng bayad, hindi agad binayaran.

Buong maghapon, isa lang ang iniisip niya—ang saya na mararamdaman niya pagsapit ng gabi. Nabalitaan niyang uuwi ang kanyang mga anak, kaya't inisip niyang ihanda ang isang masarap na hapunan para sa kanila. Bumili siya ng lawlaw (isang uri ng tuyo), pumitas ng mga pinakagandang kamatis mula sa kanyang maliit na taniman—dahil alam niyang paborito ito ni Crispín. Humingi rin siya ng pampalasa at karne mula kay Pilosopo Tasyo, na nakatira mga limang daang metro ang layo, kabilang ang tapa ng baboy-ramo at hita ng pato mula sa gubat—paborito ito ni Basilio.

Puno ng pag-asa, isinaing niya ang pinakaputing bigas na siya rin mismo ang nagbayo. Isa itong hapunang karapat-dapat para sa kura, pero inihanda niya ito para sa kanyang mga mahal na anak.

The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3, English Language Script.

New additions to an ancient state are either of the same country and language, or they are not. When they are, it is easier to hold them, especially when they have not been accustomed to self-government.

To hold them securely it is enough to have destroyed the family of the prince who was ruling them, because the two peoples preserving in other things the old conditions, and not being unlike in customs, will live quietly together.

This can be seen in Brittany Burgundy, Gascony, and Normandy, which have been bound to France a very long time. Although there may be some difference in language, nevertheless the customs are alike, and the people are easily able to get on amongst themselves.

The prince who wishes to hold such additions, has only to bear in mind two considerations: first that the family of their former prince is destroyed, and second, that neither their laws nor their taxes are altered, so that in a very short time they will become entirely integrated in the old principality.

But when states are acquired in a country differing in language, customs or laws, there are difficulties, and good fortune and great energy are needed to hold them. One of the most positive moves would be for the prince to go and reside there. This would make his position more secure. Because, if one is there, problems are seen as they spring up, and one can quickly remedy them.

But if one is not at hand, the problems are heard of only when they are great, and then one can no longer remedy them. Besides this, the country is not exploited by officials and the subjects are satisfied by easy access to the prince.

Thus, wishing to be good, they have more cause to love him, and wishing to be otherwise, to fear him. He who would attack that state from the outside must have the greatest caution. As long as the prince resides there it can only be taken from him with the greatest difficulty.

The other and better course is to send colonies to one or two places, which may be as keys to that state, for it is necessary either to do this or else to keep there a great number of cavalry and infantry.

A prince does not spend much on colonies, for with little or no expense he can send them out and keep them there, and he offends a minority only of the citizens from whom he takes lands and houses to give them to the new inhabitants; and those whom he offends, remaining poor and scattered, are never able to injure him; whilst the rest being uninjured are easily kept quiet, and at the same time are anxious not to err for fear it should happen to them as it has to those who have been despoiled.

In conclusion, I say that these colonies are not costly, they are more faithful, they injure less, and the injured, as has been said, being poor and scattered, cannot hurt. Upon this, one has to remark that men ought either to be well treated or crushed, because they can avenge themselves of lighter injuries, of more serious ones they cannot; therefore the injury that is to be done to a man ought to be of such a kind that one does not stand in fear of revenge.

Alamat ng Matsing (Pinoy Edition © 2025), Filipino Language Script.

Sa mayamang kaharian, noong unang panahon, ay may isang prinsesang ubod ng ganda. Siya ai si Prinsesa Amapela na ang lahat ay humahanga sa taglay na kagandahan.

Ngunit sa likod ng kanyang kagandahan ay napakasamang ugali. Ang prinsesa ay ubod ng sungit at suplada. Napakataas ng pagtingin niya sa kanyang sarili.

"Ayoko sa mga taong pangit! Palayasin sila sa palasyo!" ang palding sigaw nito sa tuwing makakakita ng pangit sa palasyo.

Dahil sa prinsesa, ang lahat lamang ng magaganda ang nakakapasok at nakakapagtrabaho sa loob ng palasyo. At ang mga pangit ay itinaboy sa labas upang maging mga alipin at manggagawa.

Sa paglipas ng panahon, dumating ang takdang araw sa pagpili ni Prinsesa Amapela ng mapapangasawa. At naghanda nga ang kaharian. Inimbitahan ang maraming maharlikang tao buhat sa iba't ibang kaharian. Nagsidating din ang maraming makikisig na prinsipe, upang ang isa sa sa kanila ay ang siyang mapangasawa ng ng prinsesa.

Di nagtagal, nagsimula ng mamili si Prinsesa Amapela ng mapapangasawa. Ang lahat ng prinsipe ay tumayo sa kanyang harapan at nagbigay-galang. Isa sa mga prinsipe ang nagustuhan ng prinsesa, at ito'y si Prinsipe Algori.

Si Prinsipe Algori ay isang napakasipag na prinsipe, na animo Adonis na namumukod tangi sa lahat ng naroroon. Ngunit bago pa man napili ni Prinsesa Amapela ang makisig na prinsipe, ay may nakita siya na napakapangit-pangit na prinsipe na nakatayo sa likuran nito.

Hindi napigilan ng prinsesa ang sarili.

"Sino ka? Hindi ka nahiya saiyong sarili! Napakapangit mo! Lumayas ka rito at magbalik ka na sa kwebang pinanggalingan mo!" ang bulyaw nito. Nabigla ang lahat sa nasal ng prinsesa.

"Siya ang aking napili! Si Prinsipe Algori! Siya ang aking mapapangasawa," ang agad na idinugtong nito sabay turo kay Prinsipe Algori.

Masayang lumapit si Prinsipe Algori sa prinsesa at humalik sa kamay nito. Isa isa ng nag-alisan ang mga nabigong prinsipe, ngunit nanatiling nakatayo sa harapan ang pangit na prinsipe.

"Ano pa ang hinihintay mo! Lumayas ka na! Ayaw kitang Makita!" ang muling bulyaw ng prinsesa na tila nandidiri.

Malumanay na nagsalita ang prinsipeng pangit, Hindi ako manghihinayang sa isang tulad mo. Kung ano ang ganda ng iyong mukha ay siya naming kapangitan ng iyong ugali," ang wika nito.

Bigla ay nagbago ang anyo ng prinsipeng pangit. Ito ay nagging isang napakakisig na lalaki, higit kay Prinsipe Algori.

Namangha ang lahat, sapagkat ang pangit na prinsipe ay ang "Diyos pala ng Kakisigan." Bumababa ang isang kumpol ng ulap, at sumakay rito ang "Diyos na Kakisigan," at tuluyan nang lumisan.

Nanghinayang ang lahat lalo na ang hari at reyna. Ngunit higit sa lahat, nanghinayang nang husto si Prinsesa Amapela bagay na hindi niya pinahalata.

Agad na ikinasal ng hari sina Prinsesa Amapela at Prinsipe Algori. Ngunit matapos ang kasal, ganun na lamang ang gulat ng lahat.

Ngayong mag-aswa na tayo kailangan mong sumama sa aking kaharian, "ang wika ni Prinsipe Algori.

"Anong ibig mong sabihin?" ang nagtataakang tanong ng prinsesa.

Bigla, nabago ang anyo ni Prinsipe Algori. Ito ay naging kakaibang nilalang ng puno ng balahibo ang buong katawan. Nagsigawan at nasindak ang lahat, lalo pa't bigla na lang nabago ang anyo ni Prinsesa Amapela. Nabalot din ito ng balahibo sa buong katawan, at nagkaroon pa ng buntot.

Hindi makapaniwala ang lahat, subalit huli na. Dinala na si Prinsesa Amapela sa kagubatan ni Prinsipe Algori, na siya palang "Diyos ng mga hayop sagubat." At si Prinsesa Amapela ang kauna-unahang matsing sa kagubatan. Ito ang nagging parusa ng kanyang pagiging suplada at mapagmataas.

Kaya dapat nating tandaan na hindi natin dapat husgahan ang tao sa kanyang panlabas na anyo, dahil ang higit na mahalaga ay ang tunay na pagkatao at pag-uugali.

Alice's Adventures in Wonderland (Lewis Carroll), Chapter 1 *Down the Rabbit-Hole*, English Language Script.

Alice was beginning to get very tired of sitting by her sister on the bank, and of having nothing to do: once or twice she had peeped into the book her sister was reading, but it had no pictures or conversations in it, "and what is the use of a book," thought Alice "without pictures or conversations?"

So she was considering in her own mind (as well as she could, for the hot day made her feel very sleepy and stupid), whether the pleasure of making a daisy-chain would be worth the trouble of getting up and picking the daisies, when suddenly a White Rabbit with pink eyes ran close by her.

There was nothing so very remarkable in that; nor did Alice think it so very much out of the way to hear the Rabbit say to itself, "Oh dear! Oh dear! I shall be late!" (when she thought it over afterwards, it occurred to her that she ought to have wondered at this, but at the time it all seemed quite natural); but when the Rabbit actually took a watch out of its waistcoat-pocket, and looked at it, and then hurried on, Alice started to her feet, for it flashed across her mind that she had never before seen a rabbit with either a waistcoat-pocket, or a watch to take out of it, and burning with curiosity, she ran across the field after it, and fortunately was just in time to see it pop down a large rabbit-hole under the hedge.

In another moment down went Alice after it, never once considering how in the world she was to get out again.

The rabbit-hole went straight on like a tunnel for some way, and then dipped suddenly down, so suddenly that Alice had not a moment to think about stopping herself before she found herself falling down a very deep well.

Either the well was very deep, or she fell very slowly, for she had plenty of time as she went down to look about her and to wonder what was going to happen next. First, she tried to look down and make out what she was coming to, but it was too dark to see anything; then she looked at the sides of the well, and noticed that they were filled with cupboards and book-shelves; here and there she saw maps and pictures hung upon pegs. She took down a jar from one of the shelves as she passed; it was labelled "ORANGE MARMALADE", but to her great disappointment it was empty: she did not like to drop the jar for fear of killing somebody underneath, so managed to put it into one of the cupboards as she fell past it.

"Well!" thought Alice to herself, "after such a fall as this, I shall think nothing of tumbling down stairs! How brave they'll all think me at home! Why, I wouldn't say anything about it, even if I fell off the top of the house!" (Which was very likely true.)

Down, down, down. Would the fall never come to an end? “I wonder how many miles I’ve fallen by this time?” she said aloud. “I must be getting somewhere near the centre of the earth. Let me see: that would be four thousand miles down, I think—” (for, you see, Alice had learnt several things of this sort in her lessons in the schoolroom, and though this was not a very good opportunity for showing off her knowledge, as there was no one to listen to her, still it was good practice to say it over) “—yes, that’s about the right distance—but then I wonder what Latitude or Longitude I’ve got to?” (Alice had no idea what Latitude was, or Longitude either, but thought they were nice grand words to say.)

Presently she began again. “I wonder if I shall fall right through the earth! How funny it’ll seem to come out among the people that walk with their heads downward! The Antipathies, I think—” (she was rather glad there was no one listening, this time, as it didn’t sound at all the right word) “—but I shall have to ask them what the name of the country is, you know. Please, Ma’am, is this New Zealand or Australia?” (and she tried to curtsy as she spoke—fancy curtseying as you’re falling through the air! Do you think you could manage it?) “And what an ignorant little girl she’ll think me for asking! No, it’ll never do to ask: perhaps I shall see it written up somewhere.”

APPENDIX G

Balanced Accuracy Across 22 Participants of STM Features at the Individual Level.

subject	Train vs Validation			
	combined dimensions	FS	FR	SR
1	70.0%	65.0%	60.0%	55.0%
2	85.0%	50.0%	85.0%	50.0%
3	90.0%	75.0%	95.0%	80.0%
4	71.4%	57.1%	64.3%	50.0%
5	95.0%	60.0%	90.0%	50.0%
6	88.9%	61.1%	77.8%	55.6%
7	88.9%	61.1%	83.3%	55.6%
8	80.0%	50.0%	65.0%	50.0%
9	77.8%	55.6%	72.2%	68.9%
10	83.3%	88.9%	94.4%	61.1%
11	75.0%	50.0%	58.3%	50.0%
13	85.7%	86.6%	79.5%	64.3%
14	88.2%	62.5%	88.2%	50.0%
15	87.5%	62.5%	75.0%	50.0%
17	93.8%	87.5%	87.5%	68.8%
18	100.0%	81.3%	87.5%	62.5%
19	80.0%	63.3%	76.7%	50.0%
20	82.6%	70.5%	78.8%	66.7%
21	68.8%	75.7%	75.0%	37.5%
22	77.8%	90.9%	61.1%	50.0%
23	71.4%	57.1%	64.3%	50.0%
24	85.0%	72.7%	85.9%	68.2%
avg.	83.0%	67.5%	77.5%	56.5%

APPENDIX H

Experimentation Test Results

test_results_no	01				
audio_filename	recording-5a3ed3b4-5046-4829-bcb1-650f41f4b7fe.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Rough and tired				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	3.9802	99.15%	0.85%	post
segment_2.wav	2	3.3694	98.23%	1.77%	post
segment_3.wav	3	3.3291	98.15%	1.85%	post
segment_4.wav	4	3.4660	98.43%	1.57%	post
avg.	---	3.5362	98.49%	1.51%	---
STM Representation					
STRF Average Representations					
<p>The figure displays three heatmaps representing STRF Average Representations. The first heatmap, 'Scale-Rate', shows the relationship between Scale (Hz) on the y-axis (1 to 8) and Rate (Hz) on the x-axis (-30 to 30). The second heatmap, 'Frequency-Rate', shows the relationship between Frequency Channel on the y-axis (0 to 120) and Rate (Hz) on the x-axis (-30 to 30). The third heatmap, 'Frequency-Scale', shows the relationship between Frequency Channel on the y-axis (0 to 120) and Scale (c/o) on the x-axis (1 to 8). Each heatmap includes a color scale on its right, ranging from dark purple (low values) to yellow (high values).</p>					

test_results_no		02			
audio_filename		recording-5a3ed3b4-5046-4829-bcb1-650f41f4b7fe.wav			
subject_name		christian			
nationality		Filipino			
age		22			
gender		male			
sleep_status		mildly sleep-deprived			
voice_tone		Rough and tired			
speech_script		The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3			
bg_noise_reduction		Active (Wiener Filtering applied)			
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	3.986	99.16%	0.84%	post
segment_2.wav	2	3.353	98.20%	1.80%	post
segment_3.wav	3	3.298	98.07%	1.93%	post
segment_4.wav	4	3.486	98.47%	1.53%	post
avg.	---	3.531	98.47%	1.53%	—
STM Representation					
STRF Average Representations					

test_results_no	03				
audio_filename	recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Rough and tired				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.989	99.93%	0.07%	post
segment_2.wav	2	2.991	97.21%	2.79%	post
segment_3.wav	3	5.415	99.85%	0.15%	post
segment_4.wav	4	5.178	99.80%	0.20%	post
segment_5.wav	5	4.673	99.63%	0.37%	post
segment_6.wav	6	3.799	98.95%	1.05%	post
segment_7.wav	7	2.717	96.13%	3.87%	post
segment_8.wav	8	3.569	98.61%	1.39%	post
avg.	---	4.291	98.76%	1.24%	---
STM Representation					
STRF Average Representations					
<p>The figure displays three heatmaps representing STRF Average Representations. Each heatmap has a color scale on its right side.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scale-Rate: The x-axis is Rate (Hz) from -30 to 30, and the y-axis is Scale (c/o) from 1 to 8. The color scale ranges from 0.01 (dark purple) to 0.06 (yellow). A prominent yellow-green region is visible between 10 and 20 Hz, centered around Scale 4-6. Frequency-Rate: The x-axis is Rate (Hz) from -30 to 30, and the y-axis is Frequency Channel from 0 to 120. The color scale ranges from 0.025 (dark purple) to 0.200 (yellow). A horizontal band of higher values is visible between 0 and 30 Hz, centered around Frequency Channel 20-40. Frequency-Scale: The x-axis is Scale (c/o) from 1 to 8, and the y-axis is Frequency Channel from 0 to 120. The color scale ranges from 0.02 (dark purple) to 0.14 (yellow). A horizontal band of higher values is visible between Scale 3 and 6, centered around Frequency Channel 20-40. 					

test_results_no	04				
audio_filename	recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Rough and tired				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering applied)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.931	99.92%	0.08%	post
segment_2.wav	2	2.956	97.09%	2.91%	post
segment_3.wav	3	5.381	99.84%	0.16%	post
segment_4.wav	4	5.077	99.78%	0.22%	post
segment_5.wav	5	4.708	99.65%	0.35%	post
segment_6.wav	6	3.685	98.79%	1.21%	post
segment_7.wav	7	2.65	95.81%	4.19%	post
segment_8.wav	8	3.47	98.43%	1.57%	post
avg.	---	4.232	98.67%	1.33%	—

STM Representation

test_results_no	05				
audio_filename	recording-ac6a3bd2-a247-4e59-a7b1-cc373b80cab.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	3.660	1.14%	98.86%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	1.613	12.03%	87.97%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	2.497	4.49%	95.51%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	4.003	0.76%	99.24%	pre
avg.	---	2.943	4.60%	95.40%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	06				
audio_filename	recording-ac6a3bd2-a247-4e59-a7b1-cc373b80cabc.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering applied)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	3.632	1.18%	98.82%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	1.595	12.26%	87.74%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	2.488	4.53%	95.47%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	4.005	0.75%	99.25%	pre
avg.	---	2.93	4.68%	95.32%	—

STM Representation

test_results_no	07				
audio_filename	recording-c93a67f6-d656-4ed1-ac3c-616d4e0141fc.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Energetic				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	0.903	24.42%	75.58%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	0.504	63.71%	36.29%	post
segment_3.wav	3	2.196	6.33%	93.67%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	2.760	3.31%	96.69%	pre
avg.	---	1.590	24.44%	75.56%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	08				
audio_filename	recording-c93a67f6-d656-4ed1-ac3c-616d4e0141fc.wav				
subject_name	christian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Energetic				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	0.931	23.78%	76.22%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	0.509	63.83%	36.17%	post
segment_3.wav	3	2.128	6.83%	93.17%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	2.804	3.14%	96.86%	pre
avg.	---	1.593	24.40%	75.60%	—

STM Representation

test_results_no	09				
audio_filename	recording-58cf5ca4-be7a-4b2a-99cd-36f8ab3cf2cd.wav				
subject_name	gian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Energetic				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	0.227	42.21%	57.79%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	0.945	23.48%	76.52%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	1.167	79.77%	20.23%	post
segment_4.wav	4	0.674	68.48%	31.52%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.23	55.94%	44.06%	post
segment_6.wav	6	1.871	9.10%	90.90%	pre
segment_7.wav	7	0.19	54.75%	45.25%	post
segment_8.wav	8	0.834	25.98%	74.02%	pre
avg.	---	0.767	44.97%	55.03%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	10				
audio_filename	recording-58cf5ca4-be7a-4b2a-99cd-36f8ab3cf2cd.wav				
subject_name	gian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Energetic				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (DeepFilterNet3)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.266	5.85%	94.15%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	2.396	5.04%	94.96%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	3.046	2.36%	97.64%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	1.791	9.92%	90.08%	pre
segment_5.wav	5	1.609	12.08%	87.92%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	1.081	20.66%	79.34%	pre
segment_7.wav	7	1.33	16.15%	83.85%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	0.436	35.91%	64.09%	pre
avg.	---	1.744	13.50%	86.50%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	11				
audio_filename	recording-b4dd20ab-1ce7-458a-b79e-13de272f0689.wav				
subject_name	gian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Tired				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.548	95.27%	4.73%	post
segment_2.wav	2	3.334	98.16%	1.84%	post
segment_3.wav	3	1.549	86.22%	13.78%	post
segment_4.wav	4	3.579	98.63%	1.37%	post
segment_5.wav	5	3.153	97.71%	2.29%	post
segment_6.wav	6	1.233	81.04%	18.96%	post
segment_7.wav	7	2.104	92.45%	7.55%	post
segment_8.wav	8	0.676	68.53%	31.47%	post
avg.	---	2.272	89.75%	10.25%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	12				
audio_filename	recording-b4dd20ab-1ce7-458a-b79e-13de272f0689.wav				
subject_name	gian				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Rough and Jagged				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	1.769	89.09%	10.91%	post
segment_2.wav	2	0.861	73.14%	26.86%	post
segment_3.wav	3	1.579	86.64%	13.36%	post
segment_4.wav	4	3.068	97.46%	2.54%	post
segment_5.wav	5	1.864	90.16%	9.84%	post
segment_6.wav	6	1.051	77.42%	22.58%	post
segment_7.wav	7	2.343	93.98%	6.02%	post
segment_8.wav	8	2.274	93.76%	6.24%	post
avg.	---	1.851	87.71%	12.29%	—

STM Representation

test_results_no	13				
audio_filename	recording-f4e0c6ba-c500-423c-8ab1-813b433f5c01.wav				
subject_name	marielle				
nationality	Filipino				
age	19				
gender	female				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Hoarse and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	0.176	54.33%	45.67%	post
segment_2.wav	2	3.48	98.45%	1.55%	post
segment_3.wav	3	0.272	57.17%	42.83%	post
segment_4.wav	4	3.171	97.75%	2.25%	post
avg.	---	1.774	76.93%	23.07%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	14				
audio_filename	recording-f4e0c6ba-c500-423c-8ab1-813b433f5c01.wav				
subject_name	marielle				
nationality	Filipino				
age	19				
gender	female				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Hoarse and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	active				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	1.521	85.81%	14.19%	post
segment_2.wav	2	2.798	96.49%	3.51%	post
segment_3.wav	3	0.913	24.18%	75.82%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	4.56	99.58%	0.42%	post
avg.	---	2.448	76.52%	23.48%	---

STM Representation

test_results_no	15				
audio_filename	recording-7e291636-18b0-45a7-909b-89651898ce93.wav				
subject_name	marielle				
nationality	Filipino				
age	19				
gender	female				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Hoarse and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	4.677	99.64%	0.36%	post
segment_2.wav	2	1.587	86.75%	13.25%	post
segment_3.wav	3	2.941	97.04%	2.96%	post
segment_4.wav	4	1.772	89.12%	10.88%	post
segment_5.wav	5	5.478	99.86%	0.14%	post
segment_6.wav	6	1.386	83.71%	16.29%	post
segment_7.wav	7	1.382	83.64%	16.36%	post
segment_8.wav	8	0.784	71.28%	28.72%	post
avg.	---	2.501	88.88%	11.12%	---
STM Representation					
STRF Average Representations					
<p>Scale-Rate</p>		<p>Frequency-Rate</p>		<p>Frequency-Scale</p>	

test_results_no	16				
audio_filename	f6b12a36-931b-4c02-8c63-4e5ff054dafc.mp3				
subject_name	john				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Rough and Flattened				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.395	99.85%	0.15%	post
segment_2.wav	2	2.518	95.10%	4.90%	post
segment_3.wav	3	3.105	97.57%	2.43%	post
segment_4.wav	4	1.473	85.09%	14.91%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.848	72.84%	27.16%	post
segment_6.wav	6	0.857	73.05%	26.95%	post
segment_7.wav	7	1.241	17.66%	82.34%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	3.579	98.63%	1.37%	post
segment_9.wav	9	5.264	99.82%	0.18%	post
avg.	---	2.698	82.18%	17.82%	---
pre (nsd) count	1				
post (sd) count	8				
avg. decision score (sd)	2.879				
avg. decision score (nsd)	1.241				

STM Representation

test_results_no	17				
audio_filename	01db3174-7d55-417a-93e4-20536f442ccd.mp3				
subject_name	john				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	4.999	0.00%	99.99%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	2.003	7.86%	92.14%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	0.346	59.32%	40.68%	post
segment_4.wav	4	1.538	86.06%	13.94%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.394	37.19%	62.81%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	0.237	56.16%	43.84%	post
segment_7.wav	7	0.956	23.25%	76.75%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	1.080	78.03%	21.97%	post
avg.	---	1.444	43.48%	56.52%	—
pre (nsd) count	4				
post (sd) count	4				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.800				
avg. decision score (nsd)	2.088				

STM Representation

test_results_no	18				
audio_filename	01db3174-7d55-417a-93e4-20536f442ccd.mp3				
subject_name	john				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	mildly-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Rough and Flattened				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.436	99.85%	0.15%	post
segment_2.wav	2	2.47	94.81%	5.19%	post
segment_3.wav	3	3.075	97.48%	2.52%	post
segment_4.wav	4	1.506	85.60%	14.40%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.839	72.61%	27.39%	post
segment_6.wav	6	0.889	73.80%	26.20%	post
segment_7.wav	7	1.253	17.45%	82.55%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	3.6	98.66%	1.34%	post
		5.26	99.82%	0.18%	post
avg.	---	2.703	82.23%	17.77%	—
pre (nsd) count	1				
post (sd) count	7				
avg. decision score (sd)	2.884				
avg. decision score (nsd)	1.2529				

STM Representation

test_results_no	19				
audio_filename	01db3174-7d55-417a-93e4-20536f442ccd.mp3				
subject_name	john				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	4.97	0.00%	99.99%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	2.003	7.86%	92.14%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	0.344	59.28%	40.72%	post
segment_4.wav	4	1.536	86.04%	13.96%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.391	37.28%	62.72%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	0.242	56.31%	43.69%	post
segment_7.wav	7	0.958	23.21%	76.79%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	1.081	78.05%	21.95%	post
avg.	---	1.441	43.50%	56.50%	—
pre (nsd) count	4				
post (sd) count	4				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.801				
avg. decision score (nsd)	2.080				

STM Representation

test_results_no	20				
audio_filename	kaye-sd.wav				
subject_name	kaye				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	female				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Hoarse and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.047	91.95%	8.05%	post
segment_2.wav	2	1.662	87.76%	12.24%	post
segment_3.wav	3	0.488	63.28%	36.72%	post
segment_4.wav	4	0.887	73.76%	26.24%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.070	46.91%	53.09%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	0.155	53.72%	46.28%	post
segment_7.wav	7	0.361	59.75%	40.25%	post
segment_8.wav	8	0.139	44.84%	55.16%	pre
avg.	---	0.726	65.25%	34.75%	—
pre (nsd) count	2				
post (sd) count	6				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.933				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.105				

STM Representation

test_results_no	21				
audio_filename	kaye-sd.wav				
subject_name	kaye				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	female				
sleep_status	mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Hoarse and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	active				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.048	91.96%	8.04%	post
segment_2.wav	2	1.669	87.86%	12.14%	post
segment_3.wav	3	0.490	63.33%	36.67%	post
segment_4.wav	4	0.889	73.79%	26.21%	post
segment_5.wav	5	0.063	47.13%	52.87%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	0.159	53.84%	46.16%	post
segment_7.wav	7	0.365	59.86%	40.14%	post
segment_8.wav	8	0.133	45.02%	54.98%	pre
avg.	---	0.727	65.35%	34.65%	—
pre (nsd) count	2				
post (sd) count	6				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.936				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.098				

STM Representation

test_results_no	22				
audio_filename	kaye-nsd.wav				
subject_name	kaye				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	female				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.055	7.41%	92.59%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	1.352	15.79%	84.21%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	0.136	53.13%	46.87%	post
segment_4.wav	4	0.963	23.10%	76.90%	pre
segment_5.wav	5	0.012	49.40%	50.60%	post
segment_6.wav	6	0.064	47.10%	52.90%	pre
segment_7.wav	7	0.073	51.24%	48.76%	post
segment_8.wav	8	0.839	25.86%	74.14%	pre
avg.	---	0.687	34.13%	65.87%	—
pre (nsd) count	5				
post (sd) count	3				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.073				
avg. decision score (nsd)	1.054				

STM Representation

test_results_no	23				
audio_filename	kaye-nsd.wav				
subject_name	kaye				
nationality	Filipino				
age	21				
gender	female				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (Wiener Filtering)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.300	5.62%	94.38%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	1.552	12.83%	87.17%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	0.074	46.80%	53.20%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	1.131	19.69%	80.31%	pre
segment_5.wav	5	0.115	45.58%	54.42%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	0.230	42.10%	57.90%	pre
segment_7.wav	7	0.101	46.00%	54.00%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	1.021	21.86%	78.14%	pre
avg.	---	0.815	30.06%	69.94%	—
pre (nsd) count	8				
post (sd) count	0				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.000				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.815				

STM Representation

test_results_no	24				
audio_filename	recording-rafael-full-audio.wav				
subject_name	rafael				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	0.733	29.33%	70.67%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	1.718	11.89%	88.11%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	2.478	5.37%	94.63%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	0.725	29.51%	70.49%	pre
segment_5.wav	5	1.596	13.43%	86.57%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	1.445	15.56%	84.44%	pre
segment_7.wav	7	1.483	15.00%	85.00%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	0.808	27.60%	72.40%	pre
avg.	—	1.373	18.46%	81.54%	—
pre (nsd) count	8				
post (sd) count	0				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.000				
avg. decision score (nsd)	1.373				

STM Representation

test_results_no	25				
audio_filename	recording-rafael-full-audio.wav				
subject_name	rafael				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	non-sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (DeepFilterNet3)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	0.492	34.68%	65.32%	pre
segment_2.wav	2	0.503	34.37%	65.63%	pre
segment_3.wav	3	1.171	18.93%	81.07%	pre
segment_4.wav	4	0.507	34.25%	65.75%	pre
segment_5.wav	5	0.612	31.47%	68.53%	pre
segment_6.wav	6	0.634	67.08%	32.92%	post
segment_7.wav	7	0.477	35.07%	64.93%	pre
segment_8.wav	8	1.061	77.62%	22.38%	post
avg.	—	0.682	41.68%	58.32%	—
pre (nsd) count	6				
post (sd) count	2				
avg. decision score (sd)	0.848				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.627				

STM Representation

test_results_no	26				
audio_filename	recording-d9007265-e121-4dab-9a48-19a450130b63.wav				
subject_name	rafael				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	Mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.065	92.11%	7.89%	post
segment_2.wav	2	0.301	58.02%	41.98%	post
segment_3.wav	3	2.126	92.63%	7.37%	post
segment_4.wav	4	2.056	92.03%	7.97%	post
segment_5.wav	5	2.391	94.31%	5.69%	post
segment_6.wav	6	4.399	99.49%	0.51%	post
segment_7.wav	7	1.711	88.39%	11.61%	post
segment_8.wav	8	5	99.75%	0.25%	post
avg.	—	2.506	89.59%	10.41%	—
pre (nsd) count	0				
post (sd) count	8				
avg. decision score (sd)	2.506				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.000				

STM Representation

test_results_no	27				
audio_filename	recording-d9007265-e121-4dab-9a48-19a450130b63.wav				
subject_name	rafael				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	Mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Neutral				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (DeepFilterNet3)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	2.086	92.28%	7.72%	post
segment_2.wav	2	0.998	76.26%	23.74%	post
segment_3.wav	3	2.192	93.15%	6.85%	post
segment_4.wav	4	2.408	94.41%	5.59%	post
segment_5.wav	5	2.581	95.45%	4.55%	post
segment_6.wav	6	4.882	99.71%	0.29%	post
segment_7.wav	7	1.897	90.49%	9.51%	post
segment_8.wav	8	4.807	99.69%	0.31%	post
avg.	—	2.731	92.68%	7.32%	—
pre (nsd) count	0				
post (sd) count	8				
avg. decision score (sd)	2.731				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.000				

STM Representation

test_results_no	28				
audio_filename	recording-087ee3bf-546a-4d03-894f-6b795a4f5268.wav				
subject_name	rafael				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	Mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Flattened and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	3.306	97.58%	2.42%	post
segment_2.wav	2	3.585	98.24%	1.76%	post
avg.	—	3.445	97.91%	2.09%	—
pre (nsd) count	0				
post (sd) count	2				
avg. decision score (sd)	4.918				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.000				

STM Representation

test_results_no	29				
audio_filename	recording-087ee3bf-546a-4d03-894f-6b795a4f5268.wav				
subject_name	rafael				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	Mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Flattened and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (DeepFilterNet3)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.042	99.77%	0.23%	post
segment_2.wav	2	4.794	99.68%	0.32%	post
avg.	—	4.918	99.72%	0.28%	—
pre (nsd) count	0				
post (sd) count	2				
avg. decision score (sd)	3.445				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.000				
STM Representation					
STRF Average Representations					
<p>The figure displays three heatmaps representing STRF Average Representations. The first heatmap, 'Scale-Rate', shows the relationship between Rate (Hz) on the x-axis (ranging from -30 to 30) and Scale (c/b) on the y-axis (ranging from 1 to 8). The second heatmap, 'Frequency-Rate', shows the relationship between Rate (Hz) on the x-axis (ranging from -30 to 30) and Frequency Channel on the y-axis (ranging from 0 to 120). The third heatmap, 'Frequency-Scale', shows the relationship between Scale (c/b) on the x-axis (ranging from 1 to 8) and Frequency Channel on the y-axis (ranging from 0 to 120). Each heatmap includes a color scale legend on its right, indicating the magnitude of the representation.</p>					

test_results_no	30				
audio_filename	el/recording-10b3e523-c2b3-4932-98ea-b4c11b581173.wav				
subject_name	daniel				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	Mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Flattened and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Inactive				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.854	99.91%	0.09%	post
segment_2.wav	2	4.716	99.65%	0.35%	post
segment_3.wav	3	6.421	99.96%	0.04%	post
segment_4.wav	4	6.392	99.95%	0.05%	post
segment_5.wav	5	5.305	99.83%	0.17%	post
segment_6.wav	6	5.575	99.88%	0.12%	post
segment_7.wav	7	4.948	99.74%	0.26%	post
segment_8.wav	8	4.967	99.74%	0.26%	post
avg.	—	5.522	99.83%	0.17%	—
pre (nsd) count	0				
post (sd) count	8				
avg. decision score (sd)	5.522				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.000				

STM Representation

test_results_no	31				
audio_filename	el/recording-10b3e523-c2b3-4932-98ea-b4c11b581173.wav				
subject_name	daniel				
nationality	Filipino				
age	22				
gender	male				
sleep_status	Mildly sleep-deprived				
voice_tone	Flattened and Rough				
speech_script	The Prince (Niccolò Machiavelli), Chapter 3				
bg_noise_reduction	Active (DeepFilterNet3)				
segment_file	feature	decision_score	sd_probability	nsd_probability	pred_class
segment_1.wav	1	5.25	99.82%	0.18%	post
segment_2.wav	2	4.528	99.56%	0.44%	post
segment_3.wav	3	6.131	99.94%	0.06%	post
segment_4.wav	4	6.066	99.93%	0.07%	post
segment_5.wav	5	5.174	99.80%	0.20%	post
segment_6.wav	6	5.062	99.77%	0.23%	post
segment_7.wav	7	4.674	99.63%	0.37%	post
segment_8.wav	8	4.516	99.56%	0.44%	post
avg.	—	5.175	99.75%	0.25%	—
pre (nsd) count	0				
post (sd) count	8				
avg. decision score (sd)	5.175				
avg. decision score (nsd)	0.000				

STM Representation

APPENDIX I

List of APIs and Development Tools.

Tool Used	Purpose	Prompt/Activity	Results	Location
Python	To compile and execute Python scripts for preprocessing, feature extraction, model training, and evaluation metrics.	Run commands to segment, resample, and process audio data into spectro-temporal modulation (STM) features, together with training and evaluation of the SVM classifier.	Production of feature extraction and classification results, which include STM features, accuracy, precision, recall, F1-Score, and BAcc, confusion matrices, and statistical performance measures.	Chapter III, sections 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 3.10, and subsections 3.4.1, 3.5.1, 3.6.1, 3.7.1, 3.7.2, 3.7.3, 3.7.4, 3.7.5, 3.7.6, 3.7.7, 3.8.1, 3.8.2, 3.8.3, 3.10.1, 3.10.2
STRF-like-model	To obtain and visualize the spectro-temporal modulation	Generate frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate visualizations	STM plots and acoustic features	Chapter III, IV, V, section 3.5.1, 4.1, 4.3, 5.3, subsections 4.1.4, Figures 21, 22, 23. Appendix J
Figma	To design and prototype the User Interface (UI) of the mobile application solution.	Develop wireframes and interactive mockups for the application's interfaces, such as Home, Language Selection, Audio Recording, and Output modules.	Visualization of the application's layout, navigation flow, and recording interface, which supports the development phase.	Chapter V, section 4.3
Draw.io	Graphical and tabular representation of frameworks,	Operational, Theoretical & Conceptual Framework,	Diagrams that represent the operational, conceptual,	Chapters II, III, IV, sections 2.10, 3.2, 3.3, 4.1, and Project

	system diagrams, schedules, and PERT table and diagram.	System Decomposition Chart, Sleepy Voices Schedule, and Flow	theoretical, sleepy schedule, flow, and system relationships.	Management E.
React Native	Mobile application front-end development	UI/UX implementation	Mobile prototype with functional interfaces	Chapter IV, sections 4.1, 4.3, subsections 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3, 4.1.3, 4.1.4
Flask	Backend server and API integration	Data flow handling and classification API	Server-side processing for model inference	Chapter IV, sections 4.1, 4.2, subsections 4.1.2, 4.1.3, 4.1.4, 4.2.1, 4.2.3
Nix	To manage dependencies and environments declaratively, ensuring reproducible builds and consistent development across systems.	Declare dependencies inside the "flake.nix" file, such as packages, system libraries, and development tools. This ensures that all contributors and environments use the same configurations for consistent and reproducible development.	Solves the "It works on my machine" problem by providing reproducible environments and consistent builds, ensuring that dependencies, system libraries, and configurations remain the same across different machines and over time.	Chapter IV, section 4.2, subsection 4.2.5
Grammarly	Proofreading of documentation	Grammar and clarity checks	Improved readability and consistency	Throughout documentation
ChatGPT	To expand the paragraph description in order to ensure it meets the minimum requirement of three sentences.	Expand the paragraph description in a minimum of three sentences.	Successfully expanded and refined the paragraph description, enhancing detail and coherence	Chapter III, V, sections 3.10.1, 5.3, Figure 22

	To determine which background noise reduction method to use and to fix the classification that resulted in NSD upon turning on the background noise reduction.	Why use Wiener's algorithm for the background noise reduction?	Gave YouTube and article links relating to the implementation of Wiener's algorithm with Python.	Application-Based
	To make a paragraph description that concludes the overall statements of the chapter.	Make a paragraph description for the concluding part in this Chapter.	Successfully generated a paragraph description of the Chapter's Conclusion.	Chapters 4, Conclusion
	Conversion from another audio format into .wav audio.	How to convert audio into wav in python?	Provided what python library (pydub) and its dependency (ffmpeg) to use along with a small example code	Application-Based
	To generate a tabular format of the SD Experimentation Test Results based on the results logs provided.	Make a tabular format based on the provided results log. The column should consist segment_file, feature, decision_score, sd_probability, nsd_probability,	Provided a Tabular Representation for the SD Experimentation Test Results.	Appendix H

		pred_class		
	To generate a tabular format of the Segmentation Test Results based on the results logs provided.	Make a tabular format based on the provided results log. The column should consist segment, nsd_proba, sd_proba, confidence_score, decision_score, true_class, and pred_class	Provided a concise Tabular Representation for the Segmentation Test Results. It also includes the metadata of the provided results log.	Appendix J
Gemini	To better understand what a Spectro-Temporal Modulation is, by sending images of frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate from the test set	Why in some areas, the colors are prominent (i.e, color green)?	Areas with extreme colors indicate energy being formed within that particular area. Areas with abrupt changes of colors indicate jaggedness of the voice.	Chapter 2, section 2.4
Google Studio AI	To convert the result logs from the terminal into a tabular format.	Convert the logs to tabular form. The column names should be: segment_file, feature, decision_score, sd_probability, nsd_probability, pred_class	Successfully converted the result logs from plain text to tabular format for the research results.	Appendices G, H, and J

APPENDIX J

Segmentation Test Results.

Mildly Sleep-Deprived Voice Test						
Test No. 01						
audio_filename		recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav				
audio_length		2:03 min				
segment_length		5 seconds				
elapsed_time		99.04 seconds				
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	9.90%	90.10%	90.10%	1.859	post	post
2	1.35%	98.65%	98.65%	3.590	post	post
3	2.58%	97.42%	97.42%	3.055	post	post
4	31.67%	68.33%	68.33%	0.668	post	post
5	0.14%	99.86%	99.86%	5.457	post	post
6	10.08%	89.92%	89.92%	1.842	post	post
7	8.20%	91.80%	91.80%	2.030	post	post
8	4.27%	95.73%	95.73%	2.634	post	post
9	1.48%	98.52%	98.52%	3.514	post	post
10	3.59%	96.41%	96.41%	2.779	post	post
11	0.23%	99.77%	99.77%	5.057	post	post
12	0.24%	99.76%	99.76%	5.029	post	post
13	1.62%	98.38%	98.38%	3.440	post	post
14	0.08%	99.92%	99.92%	5.935	post	post
15	0.07%	99.93%	99.93%	6.038	post	post
16	0.06%	99.94%	99.94%	6.220	post	post
17	7.45%	92.55%	92.55%	2.117	post	post
18	0.10%	99.90%	99.90%	5.762	post	post
19	3.19%	96.81%	96.81%	2.879	post	post
20	17.39%	82.61%	82.61%	1.321	post	post
21	3.69%	96.31%	96.31%	2.755	post	post
22	0.08%	99.92%	99.92%	5.915	post	post
23	0.97%	99.03%	99.03%	3.865	post	post
24	1.53%	98.47%	98.47%	3.489	post	post
avg.	4.58%	95.42%	95.42%	3.635	---	---
Test No. 02						

audio_filename		recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav				
audio_length		2:03 min				
segment_length		10 seconds				
elapsed_time		94.19 seconds				
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	5.30%	94.70%	94.70%	2.452	post	post
2	4.41%	95.59%	95.59%	2.607	post	post
3	1.07%	98.93%	98.93%	3.784	post	post
4	1.91%	98.09%	98.09%	3.305	post	post
5	1.18%	98.82%	98.82%	3.707	post	post
6	0.16%	99.84%	99.84%	5.348	post	post
7	0.20%	99.80%	99.80%	5.155	post	post
8	0.06%	99.94%	99.94%	6.222	post	post
9	0.51%	99.49%	99.49%	4.398	post	post
10	2.37%	97.63%	97.63%	3.125	post	post
11	0.38%	99.62%	99.62%	4.644	post	post
12	0.08%	99.92%	99.92%	5.968	post	post
avg.	1.47%	98.53%	98.53%	4.226	---	---
Test No. 03						
audio_filename		recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav				
audio_length		2:03 min				
segment_length		15 seconds				
elapsed_time		78.44 seconds				
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	1.39%	98.61%	98.61%	3.569	post	post
2	3.87%	96.13%	96.13%	2.717	post	post
3	1.05%	98.95%	98.95%	3.799	post	post
4	0.37%	99.63%	99.63%	4.673	post	post
5	0.20%	99.80%	99.80%	5.178	post	post
6	0.15%	99.85%	99.85%	5.415	post	post
7	2.79%	97.21%	97.21%	2.991	post	post
8	0.07%	99.93%	99.93%	5.989	post	post
avg.	1.24%	98.76%	98.76%	4.291	---	---
Test No. 04						
audio_filename		recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav				
audio_length		2:03 min				
segment_length		20 seconds				
elapsed_time		59.51 seconds				

segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	0.017	98.32%	98.32%	3.414	post	post
2	0.026	97.42%	97.42%	3.056	post	post
3	0.004	99.63%	99.63%	4.673	post	post
4	0.001	99.95%	99.95%	6.251	post	post
5	0.021	97.87%	97.87%	3.214	post	post
6	0.001	99.93%	99.93%	5.989	post	post
avg.	0.011	98.85%	98.85%	4.433	---	---
Test No. 05						
audio_filename			recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav			
audio_length			2:03 min			
segment_length			25 seconds			
elapsed_time			39.81 seconds			
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	0.011	98.95%	98.95%	3.799	post	post
2	0.003	99.68%	99.68%	4.789	post	post
3	0.017	98.28%	98.28%	3.391	post	post
4	0.001	99.93%	99.93%	5.989	post	post
avg.	0.008	99.21%	99.21%	4.492	---	---
Test No. 06						
audio_filename			recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav			
audio_length			2:03 min			
segment_length			30 seconds			
elapsed_time			39.20 seconds			
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	0.039	96.13%	96.13%	2.717	post	post
2	0.004	99.63%	99.63%	4.673	post	post
3	0.001	99.85%	99.85%	5.415	post	post
4	0.001	99.93%	99.93%	5.989	post	post
avg.	0.011	98.89%	98.89%	4.698	---	---
Test No. 07						
audio_filename			recording-503376fc-8f6f-4040-935b-95a77e02fa6f.wav			
audio_length			2:03 min			
segment_length			60 seconds			
elapsed_time			19.71 seconds			
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	0.004	99.63%	99.63%	4.673	post	post
2	0.001	99.93%	99.93%	5.989	post	post

avg.	0.002	99.78%	99.78%	5.331	---	---
Non-Sleep-Deprived Voice Test						
Test No. 08						
audio_filename			recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav			
audio_length			2:07 min			
segment_length			5 seconds			
elapsed_time			101.07 seconds			
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	76.44%	23.56%	76.44%	0.942	pre	pre
2	85.18%	14.82%	85.18%	1.414	pre	pre
3	95.38%	4.62%	95.38%	2.471	pre	pre
4	62.70%	37.30%	62.70%	0.390	pre	pre
5	99.70%	0.30%	99.70%	4.771	pre	pre
6	96.27%	3.73%	96.27%	2.656	pre	pre
7	63.19%	36.81%	63.19%	0.406	pre	pre
8	87.69%	12.31%	87.69%	1.591	pre	pre
9	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	6.068	pre	pre
10	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	8.881	pre	pre
11	55.18%	44.82%	55.18%	0.140	pre	pre
12	95.42%	4.58%	95.42%	2.479	pre	pre
13	99.23%	0.77%	99.23%	3.989	pre	pre
14	94.08%	5.92%	94.08%	2.254	pre	pre
15	97.16%	2.84%	97.16%	2.889	pre	pre
16	93.00%	7.00%	93.00%	2.106	pre	pre
17	11.72%	88.28%	88.28%	1.702	pre	post
18	65.43%	34.57%	65.43%	0.496	pre	pre
19	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	5.464	pre	pre
20	17.62%	82.38%	82.38%	1.308	pre	post
21	68.07%	31.93%	68.07%	0.594	pre	pre
22	74.29%	25.71%	74.29%	0.846	pre	pre
23	85.95%	14.05%	85.95%	1.465	pre	pre
24	43.74%	56.26%	56.26%	0.241	pre	post
25	33.14%	66.86%	66.86%	0.626	pre	post
avg.	76.02%	23.98%	83.53%	2.247	---	---
Test No. 09						
audio_filename			recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav			
audio_length			2:07 min			
segment_length			10 seconds			
elapsed_time			93.77 seconds			

segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	94.39%	5.61%	94.39%	2.302	pre	pre
2	98.44%	1.56%	98.44%	3.395	pre	pre
3	95.46%	4.54%	95.46%	2.487	pre	pre
4	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	5.968	pre	pre
5	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	5.864	pre	pre
6	98.69%	1.31%	98.69%	3.542	pre	pre
7	97.85%	2.15%	97.85%	3.127	pre	pre
8	78.88%	21.12%	78.88%	1.058	pre	pre
9	95.52%	4.48%	95.52%	2.498	pre	pre
10	43.11%	56.89%	56.89%	0.262	pre	post
11	88.01%	11.99%	88.01%	1.616	pre	pre
12	45.56%	54.44%	54.44%	0.179	pre	post
avg.	86.33%	13.67%	88.21%	2.691	---	---
Test No. 10						
audio_filename				recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav		
audio_length				2:07 min		
segment_length				15 seconds		
elapsed_time				78.36 seconds		
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	92.89%	7.11%	92.89%	2.093	pre	pre
2	99.50%	0.50%	99.50%	4.341	pre	pre
3	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	8.542	pre	pre
4	97.73%	2.27%	97.73%	3.081	pre	pre
5	98.22%	1.78%	98.22%	3.286	pre	pre
6	87.36%	12.64%	87.36%	1.566	pre	pre
7	76.75%	23.25%	76.75%	0.956	pre	pre
8	78.90%	21.10%	78.90%	1.059	pre	pre
avg.	91.42%	8.58%	91.42%	3.115	---	---
Test No. 11						
audio_filename				recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav		
audio_length				2:07 min		
segment_length				20 seconds		
elapsed_time				58.84 seconds		
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	97.17%	2.83%	97.17%	2.892	pre	pre
2	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	5.508	pre	pre
3	97.73%	2.27%	97.73%	3.081	pre	pre
4	94.94%	5.06%	94.94%	2.393	pre	pre
5	80.92%	19.08%	80.92%	1.163	pre	pre

6	78.90%	21.10%	78.90%	1.059	pre	pre
avg.	91.61%	8.39%	91.61%	2.683	---	---
Test No. 12						
audio_filename		recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav				
audio_length		2:07 min				
segment_length		25 seconds				
elapsed_time		48.86 seconds				
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	97.17%	2.83%	97.17%	2.892	pre	pre
2	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	8.542	pre	pre
3	99.31%	0.69%	99.31%	4.076	pre	pre
4	88.50%	11.50%	88.50%	1.654	pre	pre
5	78.90%	21.10%	78.90%	1.059	pre	pre
avg.	92.78%	7.22%	92.78%	3.645	---	---
Test No. 13						
audio_filename		recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav				
audio_length		2:07 min				
segment_length		30 seconds				
elapsed_time		39.06 seconds				
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	99.50%	0.50%	99.50%	4.341	pre	pre
2	97.73%	2.27%	97.73%	3.081	pre	pre
3	87.36%	12.64%	87.36%	1.566	pre	pre
4	78.90%	21.10%	78.90%	1.059	pre	pre
avg.	90.87%	9.13%	90.87%	2.512	---	---
Test No. 14						
audio_filename		recording-316fe021-4df5-4eea-a524-691c2365ab47.wav				
audio_length		2:07 min				
segment_length		60 seconds				
elapsed_time		19.52 seconds				
segment	nsd_proba	sd_proba	confidence_score	decision_score	true_class	pred_class
1	97.73%	2.27%	97.73%	3.081	pre	pre
2	78.90%	21.10%	78.90%	1.059	pre	pre
avg.	88.32%	11.68%	88.32%	2.070	---	---

APPENDIX K

Minutes of the Thesis Proposal Defense.

December 19, 2024 | 11:30 am – 12:30 pm
 College of Information Technology
 University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

Project Proposal Title	Support Vector Machine (SVM) in Sleep Deprivation Detection
Group Members	Christian L. De la Torre Gian Frans D. Araneta Rafael Jacov C. Medel
Panel Members	Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS Reymund Sabay, Ph.D
Interpellators	Cristina Baliguat Jaenhel Mencidor Ranmie Montecalvo

1. The conference started with a prayer led by Christian L. De la Torre.
2. The group members were introduced by Christian L. De la Torre.
3. The oral presentation was delivered by Christian L. De la Torre.
4. After the presentation, the following are the suggestions, recommendations of the interpellators and the panel members:

Chapter / Section	Recommendations / Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken	Reference / Proof
Title and Front Matters	Total time of being sleep deprived.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Changed the title to include the total hours of being sleep deprived based on the dataset.	Chapter 3: Methodology (3.2 Dataset Collection and Characterization)

Methodology	Need for clear thresholds and scales for determining sleep deprivation levels.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Discussed and provide thresholds of sleep deprivation levels.	Chapter 2, sections 2.3 Vocal Biomarkers, 2.9 Statistical Analysis, Table 1.
Methodology	Revise the distribution of the pre- and post must be balanced.	Elmer T. Haro and Mehreen E. Dolendo	The sample count of each day session is made balanced to not overfit or underfit.	Chapter 3: Methodology (Table 3. Sleepy Voices Annotation Count Per Session.)
System Features and Functionalities	Basis for detection without the text	Reymund Sabay	The system requires the user to read the given sentences to detect SD.	APPENDIX F, and (Figure 10)

5. After the deliberation of the interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with major revisions in the documentation and in the prototype.
6. The conference ended at 12:30 PM.

Transcribed by:

Gian Franso B. Araneta

Department of Science in
COMPUTER
SCIENCE

APPENDIX L

Minutes of the Final Thesis Defense.

May 30, 2025 | 2:30 pm – 4:00 pm
 College of Information Technology
 University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

Project Title	Support Vector Machine (SVM) in 24-Hour Sleep Deprivation Detection
Group Members	Araneta, Gian Frans D. De la Torre, Christian L. Medel, Rafael Jacov C.
Panel Members	Dolendo, Mehreen E., MSCS Haro, Elmer T., Ph.D. Firmeza, Reinhardt D., MIT Candidate
Interpellators	Baliguat, Cristina E. Mencidor, Jaenhel E. Montecalvo, Rannie P.

1. The conference started with a prayer led by Christian L. De la Torre.
2. The group members were introduced by Christian L. De la Torre.
3. The oral presentation was delivered by Christian L. De la Torre, Gian D. Araneta, and Rafael Jacov C. Medel.
4. After the presentation, the following are the suggestions, recommendations of the interpellators and the panel members:

Chapter / Section	Recommendations / Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken	Reference / Proof
Title and Front Matters	Total time of being sleep deprived.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Discussed the mild sleep deprivation based on the dataset and justified it in the document	Introduction: Scope of the Study, Chapter 2 Chapter 3 and Glossary
Review of Related	Justification of the French	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Discussed in the document that French is highly consistent in	Review of Related

Literature	Language in the training set		the properties of speech in language.	Literature (2.4.2 Speech Modulation Spectrum)
Methodology	The duration of segments required to qualify as a whole.	Elemer T. Haro and Mehreen E Dolendo	The researchers empirically experimented with multiple segment-level and performed statistical measurements in different segment levels. Discussed in the document that at least a 15-second segment is sufficient to detect; additional segments are not required for detection. The number of segments used for testing is up to the user's preference.	Chapters 3 and 5, section 3.3, 5.5, Appendix J
	The use of the audio format .flac	Reinhardt D. Firmeza	Discussed in the document that we used .wav for machine-learning compatibility	Methodology (3.3 Pre-processing)
Results, Analysis, and Discussion	Conduct an experiment for the various durations of segments required to qualify as a whole.	Elmer T. Haro, Mehreen E. Dolendo	Conducted an experimentation and discussed in the document.	Chapter VI, Section 5.5, Tables 21, 22, 23, and APPENDIX J
	Conduct an experiment with male and female voices to evaluate the reliability and accuracy of the model prediction.	Elmer T. Haro	Conducted an experimentation and discussed in the document.	Chapter VI, Section 5.5, APPENDIX H
Dataset	Inclusion of male participants	Mahreen E. Dolendo, Reinhardt D. Firmeza, Ranmie Montecalvo,	Discussed in the document that the audio sample consisted of females only. Thus, limits the generalizability and the performance of detection. A dataset of sleep-deprived male	Chapters 1, 5, 6: sections 1.3, 5.5, subsection 6.2.1, Appendix I

		Jaenhel Mencidor	participants could not be included due to privacy restrictions, high acquisition costs, and the unavailability of publicly accessible male datasets for sleep deprivation research. As a result, the researchers empirically experimented with male and female voices to evaluate the reliability and accuracy of the model prediction.	
Application	Make the computation of the prediction process faster.	Elmer T. Haro, Jaenhel Mencidor	Implement concurrent multiprocessing in the server	Flask Server
Application	Visual indicators for 15-second segment recording	Mahreen E. Dolendo	Add a feature toast message to indicate the exceeding segments	Mobile Application
Application	Long-press and pause in the microphone	Mahreen E, Dolendo	Add a feature toast message to guide the user.	Mobile Application
Application	Light Interface	Reinhardt D. Firmeza, Elmer T. Haro	Set the default UI to light theme, and dark theme is optional in the settings	Mobile Application
Application	Difficulty in reading other Filipino and English speech scripts	Mahreen E, Dolendo, Elemer T. Haro	Change the difficult speech script into a convenient and easy-to-read one.	Mobile Application

5. After the deliberation of the interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with major revisions in the documentation and in the prototype.
6. The conference ended at 4:00 PM.

Transcribed by:

Christian L. De la Torre

APPENDIX M

Five-Iteration Cross-Validation and Test of the SVM Classifier.

best_parameter			train_set	val_set	test_set	pre_set	post_set
{ 'C': np.float64(1000.0), 'gamma': np.float64(0.001) }			2176	272	272	139	132
Cross-Validation Performance Metrics							
iteration	accuracy	precision	recall	f1-score		BAcc	
1	0.8591	0.8594	0.8591	0.8592		0.8593	
2	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587		0.8589	
3	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587		0.8589	
4	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587		0.8589	
5	0.8587	0.8590	0.8587	0.8587		0.8589	
average	0.8588	0.8591	0.8588	0.8588		0.8590	
Test Performance Metrics of Both Classes							
1	0.7502	0.7491	0.7524	0.7491		0.7487	
2	0.7502	0.7491	0.7524	0.7491		0.7487	
3	0.7465	0.7454	0.7483	0.7454		0.7451	
4	0.7465	0.7454	0.7483	0.7454		0.7451	
5	0.7502	0.7491	0.7524	0.7491		0.7487	
average	0.7487	0.7476	0.7508	0.7476		0.7473	
Test Performance Metrics of Pre-Session							
1	0.7050	0.7050	1.0000	0.7050		0.8270	
2	0.7050	0.7050	1.0000	0.7050		0.8270	
3	0.7050	0.7050	1.0000	0.7050		0.8270	
4	0.7050	0.7050	1.0000	0.7050		0.8270	
5	0.7050	0.7050	1.0000	0.7050		0.8270	
average	0.7050	0.7050	1.0000	0.7050		0.8270	
Test Performance Metrics of Post-Session							
1	0.7955	0.7955	1.0000	0.7955		0.8861	
2	0.7955	0.7955	1.0000	0.7955		0.8861	
3	0.7879	0.7879	1.0000	0.7879		0.8814	
4	0.7879	0.7879	1.0000	0.7879		0.8814	
5	0.7955	0.7955	1.0000	0.7955		0.8861	
average	0.7924	0.7924	1.0000	0.7924		0.8842	

APPENDIX N

Product Logo.

The logo in the left side incorporates a stylized sound-wave icon enclosed within a frame, which symbolizes a scanning mechanism for mild sleep deprivation detection. Its color palette: purple, cyan, and blue represents the three major dimensions of spectro-temporal modulation, where purple for the frequency, or frequency bands, while cyan for the spectral modulation, or scale, and blue for the temporal modulation, or rate. This logo symbolizes voice analysis and signal processing, which is the core technology behind the system. On the right side, the thesis title “Support Vector Machine in Sleep Deprivation Detection” is presented in bold font weight, modern typography, with the phrase Sleep Deprivation highlighted in cyan-to-blue linear gradient to highlight the central focus of the study. Together, the logo and title create a cohesive visual identity that communicates both the technical foundation and purpose of the study. The design strengthens the goal of the system, which provides an accessible, mild sleep deprivation detection through voice analysis.

APPENDIX O

Group Logo.

The 16 kHz Labs logo represents the identity of the development team, inspired by the resampling rate preprocess used in the study, where audio recordings from the original 44.1 kHz sampling rate were resampled to 16 kHz for optimal speech-processing performance. The bold “16 kHz” visually highlights the logo, which symbolizes the technical foundation of the system, together with the “Labs” reinforces the focus of the group on audio and speech analysis machine learning research. The color palette: purple, cyan, and blue reflects the three major dimensions of spectro-temporal modulation (STM): purple for the frequency bands, cyan for the spectral modulation or scale, and blue for the temporal modulation or rate. Together, these elements create a cohesive and meaningful visual identity that aligns directly with the core acoustic principles and computational methods used throughout the thesis.

APPENDIX P

Product Poster.

SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE IN SLEEP DEPRIVATION DETECTION

ABSTRACT

SLEEP DEPRIVATION (SD)

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

is a growing issue that impairs cognitive, physical, and mental health, and increases the risk of accidents and chronic diseases. Conventional methods of detection are often intrusive, costly, or impractical for daily use. The study developed the use of a **Support Vector Machine (SVM)** classifier that uses **Spectro-Temporal Modulation (STM)** features to classify speech patterns into **sleep-deprived** or **non-sleep-deprived** states. The researchers evaluate system performance across both population and individual levels. By providing a reliable, voice-based detection method, the study contributes to **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 3** by promoting healthy lives and well-being through early detection and awareness of sleep deprivation.

METHODODOLOGY

03 Segmentation

04 Feature Extraction

01 Voice Recordings

02 Data Cleaning

06 Cross-Validation

05 Data Splitting

08 Evaluation Metrics

07 SVM Classification

01 Voice Recordings consist of **24 females** and **144 raw audio** with an **avg. of 316s** audio duration.

02 Data Cleaning involves **Audio Format Conversion** (WAV to MP3) and **Resampling Rate** (44 KHz to 16 KHz).

03 Segmentation results in **A total of 2720 segmented audio** files, **15s each**.

04 Feature Extraction where **2720 features** were extracted using 3-dimensional frequency-rate, frequency-scale, and scale-rate to obtain a spectro-temporal modulation.

05 Data Splitting of **2720 features** into **80% Train**, **10% cross-validation**, and **10% Test**.

06 Cross-Validation using **GridSearchCV with StratifiedKFold** were used to determine **avg. model performance**.

07 SVM Classification distinguishing between **sleep-deprived** and **non-sleep-deprived**.

08 Evaluation Metrics Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and Balanced Accuracy (BAcc) were computed at both **population and individual levels**.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Overall STM Features Performance
POPULATION-LEVEL

- Combined Features: 85.90%
- Frequency-Rate: 82.43%
- Scale-Rate: 68.40%
- Frequency-Scale: 64.00%

Combined Features Performance
POPULATION-LEVEL

Performance metrics are highly consistent between 85.88% and 85.90%. Indicate that the SVM model is stable, balanced, and generalizes effectively.

Learning Curve of Combined Features
POPULATION-LEVEL

Train Score: 85.90%
Test Score: 85.88%
The gap between Train and Test is -9%, which is generally considered reliable for generalization.

Overall STM Features Performance
INDIVIDUAL-LEVEL

- Combined Features: 83.00%
- Frequency-Rate: 77.50%
- Scale-Rate: 56.50%
- Frequency-Scale: 67.50%

Overall Experimental Test Results

The researchers conducted experimental testing using raw audio recordings in **real-world conditions** to evaluate the model's accuracy in mild sleep deprivation detection. A total of **31 test sessions** from **8 subjects** were analyzed, both with and without background noise reduction, to validate system performance.

125 samples

88% sleep-deprived
12% non-sleep-deprived

Out of 125 sleep-deprived samples, the model classified a confidence of 88% to a sleep-deprived and 12% to non-sleep-deprived class.

Conclusion

The SVM model with STM features demonstrates strong potential in mild sleep deprivation detection, which achieved highly consistent and high Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and Balanced Accuracy across cross-validation folds. Results confirm consistent generalization at both population and individual levels, highlighting the reliability of STM-based features for voice-based mild SD detection.

Recommendation

The study recommends including gender and demographic diversity to improve model generalizability, as the current dataset consists of female participants only. Fine-tuning the SVM and deploying it in real-time mobile or web-based applications are also advised for practical implementation.

80 samples

27% sleep-deprived
73% non-sleep-deprived

Out of 80 non-sleep-deprived samples, the model classified a confidence of 73% to sleep-deprived and 27% to non-sleep-deprived.

Development Tools

GIAN FRANS D. ARANETA
CHRISTIAN L. DE LA TORRE
RAFAEL JACOV C. MEDLA

Developed by
16 MHz Labs

SleepSpec

APPENDIX Q

Product Packaging.

APPENDIX M

Sleepy Voices Dataset Metadata.

Legend:

A. session	B. subjectNb	C. daySession	D. iSegment	E. durationSegment	F. filename	G. fs	H. nbSegment	I. lengthAudioSample
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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	pre	1	1	0	15	pre_subject 01_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13548824
2	pre	2	1	0	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
3	pre	3	1	0	15	pre_subject 03_read 01.aiff	44100	21	13967925
4	pre	4	1	0	15	pre_subject 04_read 01.aiff	44100	17	11599819
5	pre	5	1	0	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962
6	pre	6	1	0	15	pre_subject 06_read 01.aiff	44100	22	14760799
7	pre	7	1	0	15	pre_subject 07_read 01.aiff	44100	21	14320325
8	pre	8	1	0	15	pre_subject 08_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16081873
9	pre	9	1	0	15	pre_subject 09_read 01.aiff	44100	19	12929235
10	pre	10	1	0	15	pre_subject 10_read 01.aiff	44100	22	15011373
11	pre	11	1	0	15	pre_subject 11_read 01.aiff	44100	21	14477812
12	pre	13	1	0	15	pre_subject 13_read 01.aiff	44100	17	11513943
13	pre	14	1	0	15	pre_subject 14_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13326255
14	pre	15	1	0	15	pre_subject 15_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13379135
15	pre	17	1	0	15	pre_subject 17_read 01.aiff	44100	15	10301434
16	pre	18	1	0	15	pre_subject 18_read 01.aiff	44100	19	12923456
17	pre	19	1	0	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
18	pre	20	1	0	15	pre_subject 20_read 01.aiff	44100	26	17225806
19	pre	21	1	0	15	pre_subject 21_read 01.aiff	44100	19	13027455
20	pre	22	1	0	15	pre_subject 22_read 01.aiff	44100	25	17037586
21	pre	23	1	0	15	pre_subject 23_read 01.aiff	44100	19	13164757
22	pre	24	1	0	15	pre_subject 24_read 01.aiff	44100	23	15534244
23	pre	1	1	1	15	pre_subject 01_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13548824
24	pre	2	1	1	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
25	pre	3	1	1	15	pre_subject 03_read 01.aiff	44100	21	13967925
26	pre	4	1	1	15	pre_subject 04_read 01.aiff	44100	17	11599819
27	pre	5	1	1	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962
28	pre	6	1	1	15	pre_subject 06_read 01.aiff	44100	22	14760799
29	pre	7	1	1	15	pre_subject 07_read 01.aiff	44100	21	14320325
30	pre	8	1	1	15	pre_subject 08_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16081873
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38	pre	18	1	1	15	pre_subject 18_read 01.aiff	44100	19	12923456
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46	pre	2	1	2	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
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49	pre	5	1	2	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962
50	pre	6	1	2	15	pre_subject 06_read 01.aiff	44100	22	14760799
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52	pre	8	1	2	15	pre_subject 08_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16081873
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54	pre	10	1	2	15	pre_subject 10_read 01.aiff	44100	22	15011373

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
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393	pre	2	1	18	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
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403	pre	15	1	18	15	pre_subject 15_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13379135
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419	pre	11	1	19	15	pre_subject 11_read 01.aiff	44100	21	14477812
420	pre	14	1	19	15	pre_subject 14_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13326255
421	pre	15	1	19	15	pre_subject 15_read 01.aiff	44100	20	13379135
422	pre	19	1	19	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
423	pre	20	1	19	15	pre_subject 20_read 01.aiff	44100	26	17225806
424	pre	22	1	19	15	pre_subject 22_read 01.aiff	44100	25	17037586
425	pre	24	1	19	15	pre_subject 24_read 01.aiff	44100	23	15534244
426	pre	2	1	20	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
427	pre	3	1	20	15	pre_subject 03_read 01.aiff	44100	21	13967925
428	pre	5	1	20	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962
429	pre	6	1	20	15	pre_subject 06_read 01.aiff	44100	22	14760799
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432	pre	10	1	20	15	pre_subject 10_read 01.aiff	44100	22	15011373
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436	pre	22	1	20	15	pre_subject 22_read 01.aiff	44100	25	17037586
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438	pre	2	1	21	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
439	pre	5	1	21	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962
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441	pre	8	1	21	15	pre_subject 08_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16081873
442	pre	10	1	21	15	pre_subject 10_read 01.aiff	44100	22	15011373
443	pre	19	1	21	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
444	pre	20	1	21	15	pre_subject 20_read 01.aiff	44100	26	17225806
445	pre	22	1	21	15	pre_subject 22_read 01.aiff	44100	25	17037586
446	pre	24	1	21	15	pre_subject 24_read 01.aiff	44100	23	15534244
447	pre	2	1	22	15	pre_subject 02_read 01.aiff	44100	24	16255276
448	pre	5	1	22	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962

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453	pre	24	1	22	15	pre_subject 24_read 01.aiff	44100	23	15534244
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455	pre	5	1	23	15	pre_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	24	15890962
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465	pre	19	1	26	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
466	pre	19	1	27	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
467	pre	19	1	28	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
468	pre	19	1	29	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
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470	pre	19	1	31	15	pre_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21735479
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474	post	4	1	0	15	post_subject 04_read 01.aiff	44100	14	9724047
475	post	5	1	0	15	post_subject 05_read 01.aiff	44100	22	14771238
476	post	6	1	0	15	post_subject 06_read 01.aiff	44100	17	11386772
477	post	7	1	0	15	post_subject 07_read 01.aiff	44100	17	11307669
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483	post	14	1	0	15	post_subject 14_read 01.aiff	44100	15	10458954
484	post	15	1	0	15	post_subject 15_read 01.aiff	44100	6	4272109
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487	post	19	1	0	15	post_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21692784
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496	post	4	1	1	15	post_subject 04_read 01.aiff	44100	14	9724047
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505	post	14	1	1	15	post_subject 14_read 01.aiff	44100	15	10458954
506	post	15	1	1	15	post_subject 15_read 01.aiff	44100	6	4272109
507	post	17	1	1	15	post_subject 17_read 01.aiff	44100	18	12469208
508	post	18	1	1	15	post_subject 18_read 01.aiff	44100	18	12089816
509	post	19	1	1	15	post_subject 19_read 01.aiff	44100	32	21692784
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511	post	21	1	1	15	post_subject 21_read 01.aiff	44100	18	12107036
512	post	22	1	1	15	post_subject 22_read 01.aiff	44100	19	13126788
513	post	23	1	1	15	post_subject 23_read 01.aiff	44100		

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790	post	24	1	14	15	post subject 24 read 01.aiff	44100	19	12901029
791	post	1	1	15	15	post subject 01 read 01.aiff	44100	26	17255317
792	post	2	1	15	15	post subject 02 read 01.aiff	44100	22	15153391
793	post	3	1	15	15	post subject 03 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14185092
794	post	5	1	15	15	post subject 05 read 01.aiff	44100	22	14771238
795	post	6	1	15	15	post subject 06 read 01.aiff	44100	17	11386772
796	post	7	1	15	15	post subject 07 read 01.aiff	44100	17	11307669
797	post	8	1	15	15	post subject 08 read 01.aiff	44100	19	13118735
798	post	9	1	15	15	post subject 09 read 01.aiff	44100	20	13791949
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801	post	13	1	15	15	post subject 13 read 01.aiff	44100	16	10634218
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803	post	18	1	15	15	post subject 18 read 01.aiff	44100	18	12089816
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817	post	9	1	16	15	post subject 09 read 01.aiff	44100	20	13791949
818	post	10	1	16	15	post subject 10 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14485228
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833	post	9	1	17	15	post subject 09 read 01.aiff	44100	20	13791949
834	post	10	1	17	15	post subject 10 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14485228
835	post	11	1	17	15	post subject 11 read 01.aiff	44100	21	13960754
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839	post	20	1	17	15	post subject 20 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14267356
840	post	21	1	17	15	post subject 21 read 01.aiff	44100	18	12107036
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845	post	2	1	18	15	post subject 02 read 01.aiff	44100	22	15153391
846	post	3	1	18	15	post subject 03 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14185092
847	post	5	1	18	15	post subject 05 read 01.aiff	44100	22	14771238
848	post	8	1	18	15	post subject 08 read 01.aiff	44100	19	13118735
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853	post	20	1	18	15	post subject 20 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14267356
854	post	22	1	18	15	post subject 22 read 01.aiff	44100	19	13126788
855	post	24	1	18	15	post subject 24 read 01.aiff	44100	19	12901029
856	post	1	1	19	15	post subject 01 read 01.aiff	44100	26	17255317

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863	post	19	1	19	15	post subject 19 read 01.aiff	44100	32	21692784
864	post	20	1	19	15	post subject 20 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14267356
865	post	1	1	20	15	post subject 01 read 01.aiff	44100	26	17255317
866	post	2	1	20	15	post subject 02 read 01.aiff	44100	22	15153391
867	post	3	1	20	15	post subject 03 read 01.aiff	44100	21	14185092
868	post	5	1	20	15	post subject 05 read 01.aiff	44100	22	14771238
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870	post	11	1	20	15	post subject 11 read 01.aiff	44100	21	13960754
871	post	19	1	20	15	post subject 19 read 01.aiff	44100	32	21692784
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874	post	2	1	21	15	post subject 02 read 01.aiff	44100	22	15153391
875	post	5	1	21	15	post subject 05 read 01.aiff	44100	22	14771238
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892	pre	2	2	0	15	pre subject 02 read 02.aiff	44100	15	9997322
893	pre	3	2	0	15	pre subject 03 read 02.aiff	44100	22	14725504
894	pre	4	2	0	15	pre subject 04 read 02.aiff	44100	18	11926646
895	pre	5	2	0	15	pre subject 05 read 02.aiff	44100	25	16681772
896	pre	6	2	0	15	pre subject 06 read 02.aiff	44100	19	12878583
897	pre	7	2	0	15	pre subject 07 read 02.aiff	44100	21	14008286
898	pre	8	2	0	15	pre subject 08 read 02.aiff	44100	23	15706512
899	pre	9	2	0	15	pre subject 09 read 02.aiff	44100	24	15972471
900	pre	10	2	0	15	pre subject 10 read 02.aiff	44100	22	15125766
901	pre	11	2	0	15	pre subject 11 read 02.aiff	44100	19	12827727
902	pre	13	2	0	15	pre subject 13 read 02.aiff	44100	18	11929882
903	pre	14	2	0	15	pre subject 14 read 02.aiff	44100	18	12005240
904	pre	15	2	0	15	pre subject 15 read 02.aiff	44100	19	13136655
905	pre	17	2	0	15	pre subject 17 read 02.aiff	44100	19	12580644
906	pre	18	2	0	15	pre subject 18 read 02.aiff	44100	18	12525477
907	pre	19	2	0	15	pre subject 19 read 02.aiff	44100	29	19312631
908	pre	20	2	0	15	pre subject 20 read 02.aiff	44100	27	18234220
909	pre	21	2	0	15	pre subject 21 read 02.aiff	44100	21	14406308
910	pre	22	2	0	15	pre subject 22 read 02.aiff	44100	23	15333540
911	pre	23	2	0	15	pre subject 23 read 02.aiff	44100	19	13019465
912	pre	24	2	0	15	pre subject 24 read 02.aiff	44100	23	15355535
913	pre	1	2	1	15	pre subject 01 read 02.aiff	44100	26	17647476
914	pre	2	2	1	15	pre subject 02 read 02.aiff	44100	15	9997322
915	pre	3	2	1	15	pre subject 03 read 02.aiff	44100	22	14725504
916	pre	4	2	1	15	pre subject 04 read 02.aiff	44100	18	11926646
917	pre	5	2	1	15	pre subject 05 read 02.aiff	44100	25	16681772
918	pre	6	2	1	15	pre subject 06 read 02.aiff	44100	19	12878583
919	pre	7	2	1	15	pre subject 07 read 02.aiff	44100	21	14008286
920	pre	8	2	1	15	pre subject 08 read 02.aiff	44100	23	15706512
921	pre	9	2	1	15	pre subject 09 read 02.aiff	44100		

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2149	pre	9	3	15	15	pre_subject 09_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14890591
2150	pre	10	3	15	15	pre_subject 10_read 03.aiff	44100	17	11557607
2151	pre	11	3	15	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2152	pre	13	3	15	15	pre_subject 13_read 03.aiff	44100	16	10969825
2153	pre	14	3	15	15	pre_subject 14_read 03.aiff	44100	17	11635640
2154	pre	15	3	15	15	pre_subject 15_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13242427
2155	pre	17	3	15	15	pre_subject 17_read 03.aiff	44100	18	11945354
2156	pre	19	3	15	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2157	pre	20	3	15	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
2158	pre	21	3	15	15	pre_subject 21_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12467474
2159	pre	22	3	15	15	pre_subject 22_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14232222
2160	pre	23	3	15	15	pre_subject 23_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13657286
2161	pre	24	3	15	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2162	pre	1	3	16	15	pre_subject 01_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14799322
2163	pre	2	3	16	15	pre_subject 02_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12237210
2164	pre	3	3	16	15	pre_subject 03_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14903094
2165	pre	4	3	16	15	pre_subject 04_read 03.aiff	44100	17	11611400
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2167	pre	6	3	16	15	pre_subject 06_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12074861
2168	pre	7	3	16	15	pre_subject 07_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13852835
2169	pre	8	3	16	15	pre_subject 08_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16206402
2170	pre	9	3	16	15	pre_subject 09_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14890591
2171	pre	10	3	16	15	pre_subject 10_read 03.aiff	44100	17	11557607
2172	pre	11	3	16	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2173	pre	14	3	16	15	pre_subject 14_read 03.aiff	44100	17	11635640
2174	pre	15	3	16	15	pre_subject 15_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13242427
2175	pre	17	3	16	15	pre_subject 17_read 03.aiff	44100	18	11945354
2176	pre	19	3	16	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2177	pre	20	3	16	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
2178	pre	21	3	16	15	pre_subject 21_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12467474
2179	pre	22	3	16	15	pre_subject 22_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14232222
2180	pre	23	3	16	15	pre_subject 23_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13657286
2181	pre	24	3	16	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2182	pre	1	3	17	15	pre_subject 01_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14799322
2183	pre	2	3	17	15	pre_subject 02_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12237210
2184	pre	3	3	17	15	pre_subject 03_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14903094
2185	pre	5	3	17	15	pre_subject 05_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13775798
2186	pre	6	3	17	15	pre_subject 06_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12074861
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2188	pre	8	3	17	15	pre_subject 08_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16206402
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2190	pre	11	3	17	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2191	pre	15	3	17	15	pre_subject 15_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13242427
2192	pre	17	3	17	15	pre_subject 17_read 03.aiff	44100	18	11945354
2193	pre	19	3	17	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2194	pre	20	3	17	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
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2197	pre	23	3	17	15	pre_subject 23_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13657286
2198	pre	24	3	17	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
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2208	pre	20	3	18	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
2209	pre	22	3	18	15	pre_subject 22_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14232222
2210	pre	23	3	18	15	pre_subject 23_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13657286
2211	pre	24	3	18	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2212	pre	1	3	19	15	pre_subject 01_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14799322
2213	pre	3	3	19	15	pre_subject 03_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14903094
2214	pre	5	3	19	15	pre_subject 05_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13775798
2215	pre	7	3	19	15	pre_subject 07_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13852835
2216	pre	8	3	19	15	pre_subject 08_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16206402

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2220	pre	19	3	19	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2221	pre	20	3	19	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
2222	pre	22	3	19	15	pre_subject 22_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14232222
2223	pre	23	3	19	15	pre_subject 23_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13657286
2224	pre	24	3	19	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2225	pre	1	3	20	15	pre_subject 01_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14799322
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2229	pre	11	3	20	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2230	pre	19	3	20	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2231	pre	20	3	20	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
2232	pre	22	3	20	15	pre_subject 22_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14232222
2233	pre	24	3	20	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2234	pre	1	3	21	15	pre_subject 01_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14799322
2235	pre	3	3	21	15	pre_subject 03_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14903094
2236	pre	8	3	21	15	pre_subject 08_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16206402
2237	pre	9	3	21	15	pre_subject 09_read 03.aiff	44100	22	14890591
2238	pre	11	3	21	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2239	pre	19	3	21	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
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2241	pre	24	3	21	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2242	pre	8	3	22	15	pre_subject 08_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16206402
2243	pre	11	3	22	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2244	pre	19	3	22	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2245	pre	20	3	22	15	pre_subject 20_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16262176
2246	pre	24	3	22	15	pre_subject 24_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16210826
2247	pre	8	3	23	15	pre_subject 08_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16206402
2248	pre	11	3	23	15	pre_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	24	16256438
2249	pre	19	3	23	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
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2252	pre	19	3	24	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
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2256	pre	19	3	28	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
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2258	pre	19	3	30	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2259	pre	19	3	31	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2260	pre	19	3	32	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2261	pre	19	3	33	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2262	pre	19	3	34	15	pre_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	35	23293967
2263	post	1	3	0	15	post_subject 01_read 03.aiff	44100	26	17449629
2264	post	2	3	0	15	post_subject 02_read 03.aiff	44100	22	15121137
2265	post	3	3	0	15	post_subject 03_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14295257
2266	post	4	3	0	15	post_subject 04_read 03.aiff	44100	16	10876851
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2272	post	10	3	0	15	post_subject 10_read 03.aiff	44100	22	15104220
2273	post	11	3	0	15	post_subject 11_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14503840
2274	post	13	3	0	15	post_subject 13_read 03.aiff	44100	17	11311746
2275	post	14	3	0	15	post_subject 14_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12516127
2276	post	15	3	0	15	post_subject 15_read 03.aiff	44100	21	14536445
2277	post	17	3	0	15	post_subject 17_read 03.aiff	44100	20	13259870
2278	post	18	3	0	15	post_subject 18_read 03.aiff	44100	18	12065762
2279	post	19	3	0	15	post_subject 19_read 03.aiff	44100	31	21133930

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2693	post	19	3	21	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2694	post	20	3	21	15	post_subject_20_read_03.aiff	44100	25	17070108
2695	post	24	3	21	15	post_subject_24_read_03.aiff	44100	24	16530186
2696	post	1	3	22	15	post_subject_01_read_03.aiff	44100	26	17449629
2697	post	19	3	22	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2698	post	20	3	22	15	post_subject_20_read_03.aiff	44100	25	17070108
2699	post	24	3	22	15	post_subject_24_read_03.aiff	44100	24	16530186
2700	post	1	3	23	15	post_subject_01_read_03.aiff	44100	26	17449629
2701	post	19	3	23	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2702	post	20	3	23	15	post_subject_20_read_03.aiff	44100	25	17070108
2703	post	24	3	23	15	post_subject_24_read_03.aiff	44100	24	16530186
2704	post	1	3	24	15	post_subject_01_read_03.aiff	44100	26	17449629
2705	post	19	3	24	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2706	post	20	3	24	15	post_subject_20_read_03.aiff	44100	25	17070108

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2707	post	1	3	25	15	post_subject_01_read_03.aiff	44100	26	17449629
2708	post	19	3	25	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2709	post	19	3	26	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2710	post	19	3	27	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2711	post	19	3	28	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2712	post	19	3	29	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2713	post	19	3	30	15	post_subject_19_read_03.aiff	44100	31	21133930
2714	pre	2	02b	0	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723
2715	pre	2	02b	1	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723
2716	pre	2	02b	2	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723
2717	pre	2	02b	3	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723
2718	pre	2	02b	4	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723
2719	pre	2	02b	5	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723
2720	pre	2	02b	6	15	pre_subject_02_read_02b.aiff	44100	7	5215723

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